

**Shifting agency of Aśvins and dynamics of
Atirātra/Āśvina Śastra rituals as described in the
Brāhmaṇas and Śrauta Sūtras of Ṛgveda**

Master thesis to obtain the degree of Master of Arts at the Ruprecht Karl University of
Heidelberg, Faculty of Philosophy and History,
South Asia Institute, Dept. of Cultural and Religious History of South Asia

Submitted by:	Natālija Burišina
Program:	M.A. Cultural and Religious History of South Asia
Enrolment number:	3626660
Submitted on:	July 27, 2023
1 st supervisor:	Prof. Dr. Ute Hüsken
2 nd supervisor:	Dr. Anand Mishra

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my gratitude to all the professors and docents whose lectures and seminars I had an opportunity to attend while studying at Heidelberg University. And yet, a very special thanks is devoted to Dr. Mudagamuwe Maithrimurthi, who was my teacher of Sanskrit and Pāli languages at Heidelberg and relentlessly shared his vast knowledge on Buddhism and Sanskrit literature. I also owe a lot to my first supervisor, Prof. Dr. Ute Hüsken, for an amazing and comprehensive course on Hinduism and rituals as well as clearcut and concise recommendations and guidance while writing my thesis. Likewise, I address my appreciation and gratitude to my second supervisor, Dr. Anand Mishra, for numerous study courses on Indian philosophy, rituals, Indian metrical patterns of poems etc., and patient guiding and valuable advices throughout.

I am particularly indebted to Dr. Werner Knobl and Dr. Leonid Kulikov for inducting me into Vedic Sanskrit and continuously sharing their ocean of knowledge. I am especially grateful for your unceasing support and valuable comments.

A separate thanks I devote to a Latvian astronomer, Dr. Ilgonis Vilks, a researcher at the Institute of Astronomy, the University of Latvia, for his support and advice in the field of astronomy, in particular with regard to the apparitions and cycles of Venus and solar eclipses.

Last but not least, my warm regards and special thanks goes to Dr. Marianne Stazie Lissy Oort who conveyed my questions to an expert of Vedic Sanskrit, and a wonderful translator of the Ṛgveda — Dr. Stephany W. Jamison, who returned all the precious and invaluable answers necessary for this study.

I am grateful to all of you...

Table of Contents

List of Abbreviations	3
Introduction	5
Chapter 1: On Aśvins – the divine twins of Vedic pantheon	10
1.1. Aśvins: notion, semantics, and etymology	10
1.2. Locus of celestial deities – Aśvins – in Indo-European cosmology	18
Chapter 2: Invocation of Aśvins – Āśvina Śastra	31
2.1 Solar mythologeme — an insight into Indo-European mythologies	31
2.2 Solar mythologeme — as described in Ṛgveda:	36
2.2.1 Aśvins — the bridegrooms of Sun Maiden	37
2.2.2 Aśvins — brothers and companions of Dawn	40
2.2.3 Aśvins — the wooers of Soma (Moon god)	43
2.3 Āśvina Śastra – Solar mythologeme – as described in the Brāhmaṇas of Ṛgveda	49
Chapter 3: Some conjectures on astronomical dating of Vedic Solar mythologeme	54
Chapter 4: Invocation of Aśvins during Atirātra as described in the Śrauta Sūtras of Ṛgveda:	60
4.1. Locus of Āśvina Śastra within Atirātra ritual	61
4.2. Āśvina Śastra — contents and locus et modus operandi of Aśvins	64
4.3. Invocation of Aśvins – as described in Āśvalāyana Śrauta Sūtra	65
4.4. Invocation of Aśvins – as described in Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra	65
Chapter 5: Conclusions	67
Appendix 1: English translation of selected Ṛgveda hymns by Jamison & Brereton	74
Appendix 2: English translation of the selected excerpts by the author:	77
• Solar mythologeme in Aitareya Brāhmaṇa, IV.17.7-9;	
• Solar mythologeme in Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇa, 18.1.1-18;	
• Āśvina Śastra in Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra, Adhyāya 9 Kaṇḍikā 20.1-35.	
Bibliography	91
Primary Sources	91
Secondary Sources	91
Online Sources	96

List of Abbreviations

adj.	adjective
adv.	adverb
AitBr	Aitareya Brāhmaṇa
AŚ	Aśvina Śastra
ĀŚS	Āśvalāyana Śrauta Sūtra
ĀGS	Āśvalāyana Gṛhya Sūtra
Du.	Dual number
ind.	indeclinable
KB	Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇa
f.	feminine gender
Gr.	Greek
IE	Indo-European
m.	masculine gender
MSS	Manuscripts; MS — one manuscript.
MW	Monier-Williams, M. 1899. A Sanskrit-English Dictionary: Etymologically and Philologically Arranged with Special Reference to Cognate Indo-European Languages. Oxford: The Clarendon Press.
n.	neuter gender
Nom.	Nominative case
Lat.	Latin
Latv.	Latvian
Lith.	Lithuanian
Eulexis	Eulexis-web — Lemmatiser for ancient Greek texts (online app)
Pers.	Persian
Pl.	Plural number
PW	Böhtlingk, O. 1855. Sanskrit Wörterbuch, herausgegeben von der kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften, bearbeitet von Otto Böhtlingk und Rudolph Roth. St-Petersburg: Eggers.
RV	Ṛgveda
Sg.	Singular number

Skt.	Sanskrit
Slav.	Slavonic or Slavonian
ŚŚS	Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra
ŚGS	Śāṅkhāyana Gṛhya Sūtra

Introduction

Why the Aśvins? Who are the Aśvins? What was their *loci et modus operandi* in Vedic ontology? Since the dawn of Western Indology these celestial deities have captivated minds of scholars as they being divine twins exhibit homologies with other well-known twin deities in Indo-European (IE) mythologies to begin with the famous Graeco-Roman horse patrons *Dioskuoroi* (Διόσκουροι) — Castor and Pollux, the Baltic — Sons of God (*Dieva dēli*), Germanic – Raos and Raptos, Hengst and Horse, in the Norse mythology - Njörðr (Old Norse: Njǫrðr) and Freyr, the Slavic – Lel and Lelpol, the Celtic – *Dioskuoroi* (the tradition in question), and Indo-Aryan (Ward, 1968). Likewise, there are several couple deities in the Vedic pantheon, namely Maitrāvaruṇa (Mitra & Varuṇa), Indrāgnī (Indra & Agni), and the Aśvins — the main subject of this study.

The Aśvins are the fourth most prominent deities after atmospheric Sky-God Indra, Agni and Soma separately or coupled in the Vedic mythological pantheon of the Ṛgveda (RV) where they are mentioned or invoked 449 times in 52 hymns (Keith, 1920: 36–42). The answers to the posed questions on the notion, semantics and etymology of the Aśvins, as well as their *loci* and multifunctional agency in (RV) and Indo-European (IE) cosmology; and also, a brief survey of the 200-year scholarship on the matter dedicated to the Aśvins question will be unfolded in Chapter 1.

Chapter 2 will give an insight into the epistemology of the solar mythologeme in IE context as well as draw to the relevant passages from RV that describe the main heroes of this study, the Aśvins, in the role of bridegrooms or husbands of the Sun Maiden, brothers and companions of Dawn; and also, the wooers on behalf of Soma, the Moon God. A further development of solar mythologeme as described in the ritual milieu of Āśvina Śāstra (AŚ) will be investigated in the two Brāhmaṇas of RV — Aitareya (AitBr) and Kauṣītaki (KB). AŚ is the most voluminous one as it comprises 1000 lauding stanzas. Hence, I will give a synopsis of AŚ and *modus operandi* of the Aśvins within it as well as their functional area and benefits to the commissioner of the sacrifice i.e., *Yajamāna*. Since it entails with detailed descriptions of all the involved actors of the sacrifice, an English translation of AŚ in KB, 18.1.1-18 and AitBr, IV.17.7-9 will be produced in Appendix 2.

Chapter 3 will examine solar mythologeme and its relation to calendric systems and astronomic phenomena. Hence, it will draw some conjectures on astronomical dating of Vedic Solar mythologeme.

The focal part of Chapter 4 will be devoted to the sacrificial ground, where I will investigate at length a concluding part of the Atirātra injunction — AŚ as described in the two ancillary Śrauta Sūtras of RV: Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra (ŚŚS) and Āśvalāyana Śrauta Sūtra (ĀŚS). Atirātra is one of the seven constituents of Jyotiṣṭoma sacrifices that is a one-day-and-night Soma ritual. In order to investigate the dynamics of the ritual, an English translation of AŚ in ŚŚS by the author will be provided in Appendix 2. ŚŚS has been selected for translation owing to the reason that Fritz Staal's comprehensive study on the Atirātra proves to be complementary and perfectly suffices to this study.

In the final Chapter 5, the results of the study will be summarized and synthesized to draw on the research outcome.

Appendix 1 contains English translations by Stephanie Jamison & Joel Brereton (2014) of all the selected RV passages.

Appendix 2 contains new English translations of the solar mythologem in AitBr and KB, and also, AŚ in ŚŚS by the author of this study. To perform the translations two online dictionaries have been used: Monier-Williams Sanskrit-English Dictionary (MW) and Böhtlingk, O. 1855. Sanskrit Wörterbuch, herausgegeben von der kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften, bearbeitet von Otto Böhtlingk und Rudolph Roth. St-Petersburg: Eggers (PW). The aim of this translation is to produce the result that would be balancing between the exact grammatical, semantic, and stylistic accuracy of the source language — Sanskrit — and “naturally” sounding target language — English, bearing in mind that the translator is not a native speaker. Furthermore, whenever in doubt, the semantic and grammatical accuracy will prevail over the native English style and aesthetics. See the relevant translator's note before the translation of the selected excerpt.

In order to conduct this study, I have carefully selected the primary sources considering available critical editions and up to date academically recognized translations. The foundation source of the mythological context is the RV, being itself the oldest of the four Vedas. However, both of the Brāhmaṇas and Śrauta Sūtra texts related to the RV would serve as the source for the mythological and ritual context. Furthermore, they give references to the particular hymns of RV that are employed in the ritual.

Based on the information given in Caraṇavyūha, there were five śākhās (schools) of RV, namely Śākala, Bāṣkala, Āśvalāyana, Śāṅkhāyana, and Māṇḍūkāyana (elsewhere called the Māṇḍūkeya or Māṇḍukeya). However, other sources vary the number of śākhās from seven to 21 and even 24.

As a result, until today the actual number of *śākhā*, is unknown. Nevertheless, only two recensions of RV have survived until today: Śākala and Bāṣkala. Due to scarcity of Bāṣkala manuscripts, the most well-known and recited by the Vedic practitioners and studied by scholars is Śākala recension (Brereton and Jamison, 2020a: 197–198; cf. Renou, 1947: 18–19). Hence, to consult the primary text of RV in the source language — Sanskrit, and also to elicit number of occurrences of the terms selected, I will use the online text based on the edition by a German Indologist Theodor Aufrecht (1877) that is provided in Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL) (Autores Varii, 2022). Accordingly, all the passages from RV will be quoted from GRETIL, retaining its orthography and accentuation. As concerns translations, I have selected the existing academically recognised ones in the languages that I have a good command of, namely by Stephany Jamison & Joel Brereton’s (2014) in English, three volumes including extensive commentaries by Tatyana Elizarenkova (1999) in Russian, and when in doubt somewhat hesitantly also the German translation by Karl Geldner (1951). Since my German language knowledge is not yet sufficient, I will consult Geldner’s translation in the cases, when the fragments selected for analyses of the English and Russian translations would differ significantly. However, in particular cases that require special attention due to the disparities of translations I might occasionally consult other existing translations, for instance, 225 hymns translated by Paul Thieme “Gedichte aus dem Rig-Veda” (1964), by Hermann Grassmann (1877), and also by Alfred Ludwig (1876-1883).

RV has four ancillary texts belonging to two surviving *śākhā*s, namely, AitBr and ĀŚS are associated with Śākala school, therefore their practitioners are named Aitareyins; whereas, KB is typically coupled with Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra (ŚŚS) that is considered to be an off-shoot of Bāṣkala śākhā. However, this point of view is still controversial as Jan Gonda enlists valid arguments pointing that in some cases (ĀŚS) is in greater conformity to KB than to AitBr. Keith points out numerous grammatical, structural, historical and geopolitical evidences thus stating that KB being much better arranged is historically younger than Aitareya. Although, as it is highlighted by Gonda, Hillebrandt, Keith, and Sarma ŚŚS must have been an independent tradition from that of KB, which eventually converged and found its way via Kauṣītakins. Moreover, Hillebrandt and Keith presume ŚŚS is older than ĀŚS, and may even predate or could be arranged simultaneously with KB. Furthermore, Gonda states that the relation between ŚŚS and KB is much stronger than that between ĀŚS and AitBr¹. Though it was not popular at that time, yet its tradition alongside

¹ More on this controversy see in (Gonda, 1977: 530–533; Hillebrandt, 1888: viii–ix; Keith, 1920: 36–42; Sarma and Staal, 1983: 161–162).

with Aitareyins had spread to South India from the North, and has survived among Nambudiri priests that allows to study it diachronically. Hence, I have selected Alfred Aufrecht's critical edition of AitBr (1879) "Das Aitareya Brāhmaṇa. Mit Auszügen aus dem Commentare von Sāyaṇācārya und anderen Beilagen" as a primary source. For the translation purposes I have consulted two available English translations by Arthur Berriedale Keith (1920) and Martin Haug (1863). Although, Keith harshly criticized Haug's translation, it is valuable for the reason that Haug had a rare chance to eye-whiteness the rituals, which he generously commented in footnotes.

Now, on the selection of the KB text that belongs to Bāṣkala *śākhā* of RV. Currently, there are only two translations available in English. A complete one by Keith (1920), and another one by E. R. Sreekrisha Sarma of Adhyāyas (chapters) 14-17 (Edholm, 2021).² Unfortunately, this translation does not cover Adhyāya 18, which is of particular interest for this study. Keith's translation is valuable also for the reason that he used the MSS of KB available in Bodleian Library alongside with the Aufrecht's edition that includes commentaries by Vinākayabhaṭṭa. (Keith, 1920: 37). Nevertheless, Keith looked critically not only at the Aufrecht's edition, but he also consulted the subsequent editions. Moreover, Keith provides a comprehensive information on the dating, interrelations of the two Brāhmaṇas with other texts related to other *śākhās*, metrics, rituals, and the geopolitical and linguistic background of the time period covered in these texts. And last but not least, Keith draws his conclusions upon the work carried by earlier Indologists, for instance, A.A. Macdonell, J. Eggeling, W. Caland, V. Henry, A. Hillebrandt, H. Oldenberg, W.D. Whitney, C.R. Lanman a. o. For critical analyses on the editions, I will also use the most recent critical edition by an Indian Indologist E.R. Sreekrishna Sarma (Wiesbaden 1968; VOHD, Suppl. 9,1) that is also available online by Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL).

As a source for ŚŚS I have selected two volumes by Alfred Hillebrandt's critical edition that also contains the commentaries of Varadattasuta Ānārtīya (1888-1889). Alongside with that, I am also going to use the *sūtra* input provided by Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (*Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL)*, 1995). Unfortunately, there exist only two translations into English: a complete one by Willem Caland, and another one by Jan Gonda (1983) covering solely Adhyāya 14. I -13³ (Edholm, 2021). Thus,

² Sarma, E. R. Sreekrishna. 1983. Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇa on the Atirātra. Staal, Frits (ed.), Agni: The Vedic Ritual Q/ the Fire Altar. 11. 1st Indian ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 676-699.

³ Gonda, Jan. 1982. The Haviryajñāḥ somāḥ. Interrelations of the Vedic Solemn Sacrifices: Śāṅkhāyana Srautasūtra 14. I -13. Translation and Notes. Verhandelingen der Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen. Afd. Letterkunde 113. Amsterdam: North-Holland.

for the translation — only Willem Caland’s English translation is used, which was edited by Raghu Vira and Lokesh Chandra postmortem; and firstly, published in the annals of Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, a concise variant in 1951; later followed by the translation with extensive commentaries in 1953.

For all primary sources and other most frequently employed in the study, I will use abbreviations, the list of which is provided right before the introduction. As a rule, by the first mention, a full title of the source will be given with its abbreviation in brackets. Thereafter, only respective abbreviation will be used. Whereas, for all Sanskrit notions, terms and titles I will use the IAST alphabet⁴, where necessary giving English counterpart in the round brackets.

As the title already suggests in the course of this study, I am intending to investigate at length **1) How the agency and significance of the celestial twin deities — the Aśvins — has shifted within mythopoetic cosmology and ritual ontology of Āśvina Śastra that forms a concluding part of the Atirātra ritual; 2) How it is reflected in the Ṛgveda and its two Brāhmaṇas and two Śrauta sutras.**

In order to conduct this study, I am going to employ combined methodology. For the primary sources — content analyses and hermeneutic approach have been chosen to critically analyse the selected excerpts diachronically; likewise, the translations of the selected excerpts from the primary sources will be conducive in drawing on conclusions; and literature review for the secondary sources. The results will be concluded via analyses and synthesis.

⁴ The International Alphabet of Sanskrit Transliteration (IAST) is a transliteration alphabet that allows to romanize Indic scripts preserving their original phonetic values.

Chapter 1: On Aśvins – the divine twins of Vedic pantheon

1.1. Aśvins: notion, semantics, and etymology

Before delving into the realm of semantics and etymology, at least some general insights on their *loci et modus operandi* as well as importance in the Vedic pantheon should be given, which will be further elaborated in the corresponding subsections. The Aśvins are very ancient deities who were worshipped already by Indo-Iranians and even Proto-Indo-Europeans as noted by Asko Parpola, and eventually they engaged into the ritual scene of Soma (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 47; Parpola, 2015: 92). The entire 52 hymns of RV are dedicated to the Aśvins who are described as **celestial twin deities; the riders of a tripartite golden chariot; sons of Dyaus⁵ (Heaven, Sky) (RV 1.182.01); brothers of Uṣas (Dawn); patrons of horses; honey-drinkers and givers; protectors of men; wonder makers; bestowers of horses, cows and wealth; bestowers of a good journey; two sacrificial priests Adhvaryu; divine healers etc.** The Aśvins or Nāsatyas lauded in RV were worshipped particularly by the poets of Kāṇva and Atri family (Maṇḍala 5) clans, and also by a single poet Vasiṣṭha Maitrāvaruṇi (Maṇḍala 7). According to Parpola, Kāṇva and Atri poets were the inhabitants of Gandhāra land representing the early immigration wave of the Indo-Aryan speakers (Parpola, 2005: 2). See image No. 1.

However, as pointed out by Jamison & Brereton, the interrelations of Kāṇva⁶ and Āṅgīrasa clans apparently resulted in linking Maṇḍala 8 with Maṇḍala 1. Geographically, the Atri clan cover the territory from the rivers in the northwest, including the Kabul (*Kubhā*) and Kurram (*Krumu*) rivers, extending to the Yamunā in the east (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 659; 1019).

The study by Michael Witzel demonstrates linguistic evidences that

[...] the older portions of AitBr, books 1-5 were composed in the West, in an area close to that of the *Kaṭha*, "where the rivers flow westwards most copiously (Witzel, 1989: 39).

⁵ Dyaus — is a Nom. Sg. form of stems: *div*, *dyut*, or *dyo* by native grammarians — m., very rarely f. in Vedic; f. in later Sanskrit, in the sense — heaven, the sky (regarded in Vedic as rising in three tiers (*avama*, *madhyama*, *uttama* or *ṛtīya*), and generally as the father e.g. *dyaus pitā*. (MONIER-WILLIAMS, 1899: ID=92231)

⁶ One of the most skillful poets lauding the Aśvins is *Kakṣivant Dairghatamasa*. See more on his kinship and poetic mastery in (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 267–268).

Image No. 1 The map of Gandhāra

Credit: Asia Society, 2015 (Society, 2015).

Furthermore, as it was a common practice in Vedic texts to address a deity with different epithets that describe its nature, origins, functions etc., hence, I will provide a comprehensive insight into the epithets used to address the Aśvins. It is noteworthy to mention the impressive list of 176 epithets that were employed by the poets to address the Aśvins in RV (Pischel and Geldner, 1897: 56–57). For the sake of brevity, however, I will provide only the most prominent and most frequently used ones in RV:

- 1) *Aśvinau* or *Aśvinā*⁷ (m. Nom. Du.) or— possessors of horses, divine charioteers (RV 1.183.06 etc., **in total 449 mentions**);
- 2) *Dasrā* — wonder-makers (1.3.3; 1.92.18; 5,075.02; 8.5.11; 8.8.1; 8.22.17 etc., **in total 52 mentions**), often in combination with
- 3) *Hiraṇyavartanī* — the Aśvins are the only deities called — golden-pathed (1.92.18; 8.5.11; 8.8.1; 8.87.5; 5.75.02-03, **in total six mentions**);

⁷ See the footnotes No. 14-15 for an elaborate linguistic discussion.

- 4) *Nāsatyā*⁸ — ‘rescuer, saviour’ or ‘true and not false’ (na-asatya) (1.3.3; 1.182.04; 10.41.02, etc., **in total 102 mentions**) and also;
- 5) *Dīvo Napātā* — Heaven’s sons or grandsons (1.117.12; 1,182.1; 1,184.1; 3.38.5; 4.44.2; 10.61.4, **in total six mentions**);
- 6) *Mādhvī* — honey-loving ones (1.184.4; 4.43.4-5; 5.75.1-9; 6.63.8; 7.67.4; 7.67.7; 7.71.2, **in total 16 mentions**);
- 7) *Madhupau* — honey-drinkers (1.180.2); also, *Madhupātama*⁹ — the ones who drink honey most (8.22.17, **in total two mentions**; more mentions in connection with honey drinking);
- 8) *Madhuvarṇā* — honey-hued (5.77.3; 8.26.6, **in total two mentions**);
- 9) *Śubhas patī* — lords of beauty (1.3.1; 1.34.6; 1.47.5; 1.120.6; 5.75.8; 8.5.5; 8.5.11; 8. 22.4; 8.22.6; 8.22.14; 8.26.6; 8.59.3; 8.59.5; 8.87.5; 10.40.4; 10.40.12-14; 10.85.15; 10.93.6; 10.131.4, **in total 21 mentions**);
- 10) *Rudravartanī* — the only ones called ‘the red pathed’¹⁰ (MacDonell, 1897: 49; Pischel and Geldner, 1897: 55–60); cf. Thieme ‘of Rudra’s path’ or ‘of terrible [chariot] path’ (Thieme, 1960: 315) (1.3.3; 8.22.1; 8.22.14; 10.39.11, **in total four mentions**);
- 11) *Parijmānā*¹¹ — going round [the earth] (1.46.14 (verbal form); 1.117.6; 10.106.3, **in total three times**), and

⁸ *Nāsatyā* — according to Paul Thieme and Brunnhofer in Macdonell’s — ‘rescuers, saviours,’ Asko Parpola explains it as ‘safe return home’ being a derivative of *nasatī-, which belongs to the same Proto-Indo-European root *nes- as the Greek agent noun *Néstōr* — known from Homer as a *hippóta* and a ‘masterly charioteer’ — the task of whom is to bring the hero safely back from the battle (cf. Gotō, 2009, p. 205; Parpola, 2005, p. 12); cf. also in-depth historical linguistic analyses by (Frame, 2020; Güntert, 1925: 259); whereas, Yāska’s etymology of the name *Nāsatya* given in *Nirukta* (6.13) explains that they were considered as ‘the guardians of the truth’ (RV 8.35.12 and 1.120.8). Therefore, the *Āsvins* are ‘true and not false (na-asatya),’ says *Aurṇavābha* (*satyāv eva nāsatyāv ity aurṇavabha*); ‘they are promoters of the truth,’ says *Āgrāyaṇa* (*satyasya praṇetārāv ity agrāyaṇa*). However, this interpretation was already rejected by Güntert and also contemporary scholars. A peace treaty *Boghazkōi* between the Hittite king *Suppiluliuma I* and the Mitanni king *Šattivaza* in 1350 BCE mentions four Indo-Aryan deities that were asked to be a divine witness of the treaty: *Mitra* (Mi-it-ra-), *Varuṇa* (A-ru-na-), *Indra* (In-da-ra-), and the *Nāsatya* twins (Na-aš ša-at-ti-ya-) (Parpola, 2015, pp. 77; 94); cf. Latv. *nest* ‘to carry, bear’, *nēsāt* ‘carry about, bear’; (*at*)(*no*)*nākt* ‘to come; reach’ (Spektors, 2009); ‘keepers of peace and treaty’ in RV 8.120.8a; 8.35.12 (Gotō, n.d., p. 199; Thieme, 1960, p. 315); also encountered in *Avesta* as *Nāḥhaiθya*. Similarly, the Greek *Dioskuroi* were also oath deities (Jamison & Brereton, 2014, p. 47; Macdonell, 1897, p. 49); frequently mentioned as the guardians of truths (RV 1.46.14 etc.); cf. Livonian tradition of using a horse by a soothsayer to predict the future, which was attested in ‘The Chronicle of Henry of Livonia’ that covers period from 1180-1227 CE. It describes the event during which the life of a Christian monk, namely, the life of Brother Theodorik from the Order of Cistercians was saved owing to the fact that the horse involved in fortune telling as first moved the right or ‘life saving’ foreleg (Livonijas Indriķis, 1993: 27–28, 1993: 51); cf. multiple ancient Latvian beliefs related to breeding and using horses to tell the fortune (*Latviešu tautas ticējumi*, 1997).

⁹ *Madhupātama* - the superlative m. Pl. of *madhupas*.

¹⁰ *Rudravartanī* — Pischel & Geldner interpret the verbal root *rud* as ‘red’; moreover, this colour is attributed to the *Āsvins* as they follow morning glow. Jamison & Brereton translates in (1.3.3; 8.22.1; 8.22.14) as ‘o you who follow the course of the Rudras [=Maruts]’ (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 92; 1073–1074).

¹¹ *Parijmānā* — Jamison & Brereton translates ‘like two encircling the earth’; *Parijman* — this epithet is also used to address *Indra* (Thunder God; 1.6.9; 1,063.08 (in comparison with water circles) etc.), *Vāta* (air, wind god; 1.79.3; 1.112.4; 1.122.3; 4.22.4; 7.40.6; possibly 10.93.4; 10.93.7), *Vāyu* (wind god), and *Rudra* (storm god) (Böhtlingk and Roth, 1855: 523–524); *Agni* (in comparison to

12) **Rudrā** — Rudras¹²; the red ones; the terrible ones (5.75.03; 8.22.14(?); 8.26.5; 10.93.7, **in total four mentions**) (MacDonell, 1897: 49–51).

13) **Vṛṣaṇā** — bulls¹³; (1.117.4; 1.117.18; 8.26.1-2, **in total four mentions**).

Thus, it is evident that out of the 13 epithets investigated, the three most prominent ones are — *Nāsatyā* with 102 mentions, followed by *Dasrā* with 52 mentions, and *Śubhas patī* with 21 mentions respectively.

It is also necessary to clarify the spelling of their name into English, which I will thus employ henceforth. At first, let me give the main morphological differences between the Sanskrit and English. Sanskrit being synthetic language has eight cases and three numbers: Singular, Dual, and Plural. Whereas, modern English being an analytical language has only three cases: subjective, possessive and objective, and two numbers: Singular and Plural. Since the Aśvins represent the twin deities, in the Nom. case it requires the Du. number ending. However, there are two grammatical forms represented in RV: Aśvinau¹⁴ and Aśvinā. Moreover, the endings may vary depending on the case and number. In addition, when it is necessary to demonstrate the relation or possession, different morphological rules apply. In the case of the Aśvins, one could mention *Āśvina Śastra* (invocation of the Aśvins) that is related to or possessed by the Aśvins, which is represented by lengthening of the initial vowel. In order to avoid further ambiguity imposed by grammatical peculiarities, henceforth in English I will employ the term the Aśvins to denominate the twin deities, whereas, to express the relation or possession, the form — Aśvina Śastra will be employed.

Now, on semantics. For a lemma ‘aśvin’ MW gives following entries: 1) m.f.n. possessed of horses, consisting of horses; 2) mounted on horseback; 3) m. a cavalier; 4) m. horse-tamer; 5) m. Du. ‘the two charioteers’, name of two divinities (who appear in the sky before the dawn in a

Heaven 1.127.2; 3.2.9; like earth-encircling lightning bolts 5.10.5; 5.41.12; compared to a herdsman 7.14.3); rivers (2.28.4); god (2.38.2); unidentified deity (8.72.10; (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 1066–1067); perhaps *Parjāñya* (10.92.5; (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 1543).

¹² *Rudrā* – Jamison & Brereton leave this epithet untranslated, however, Macdonell translates as ‘The Red Ones’; MW gives the principal semantic value ‘terrible, horrible’, which is reflected in 10.93.07. This sense contributes to their protective function, namely, the Aśvins being the ‘Terrible Ones’ who fight against evil (Thieme, 1960: 315).

¹³ *Vṛṣaṇā* — grammatically this is an adj., meaning ‘bullish’; however, Jamison & Brereton takes it as ‘[you] bulls’; this epithet is also frequently used to address other deities, for instance, Maruts (7.58.6; 8.96.14), Agni and Soma (only twice 1.93.1; 10.66.7), Soma and Pūṣan (only once in 2.40.3), Indra and Varuṇa (6.69.11; 7.83.9 etc.), Indra and Agni (1.108.3 etc.), Mitra and Varuṇa (7.60.10), Indra and Soma (7.104.1).

¹⁴ Aśvinau — almost all forms in -au occur before a vowel, where they end in -āv before non-u- or -ū- on the one hand, and, on the other, in -ā before u- or -ū-; the ending -ā from -āv by dissimilation. The only exception, with -au before a consonant, is attested in a very late hymn of RV 10.184.2c. From personal communication with Werner Knobl & Leonid Kulikov.

golden carriage drawn by horses or birds; they bring treasures to men and avert misfortune and sickness; they are considered as the physicians of heaven); 6) in astronomy – a name of *nakṣatra*¹⁵ presided over by the Aśvins; 7) n. (= *aśvavat*) richness in horses; 7) f. *aśvinī* name of the wife of the two The Aśvins (who in later times was considered as their mother; 9) in *Jyotiṣa* (astronomy) – f. *aśvinī* the head of Aries or the first of the 28 *Nakṣatras*.

In addition to the aforementioned, PW gives other meanings: 10) m. two horse riders, and also informs on its nominal stem, namely the notion *aśvin* has derived from *aśva*. Thus, both MW and PW give following senses to it: 1) *aśva* m., f. a horse, stallion; 2) the horse (in the game of chess); 3) the number ‘seven’ (that being the number of the horses of the sun); 4) the archer (in the Zodiac); 5) f. *aśvā* a mare.

Now, on etymology. PW points to *aśan*, which PW and MW both translate as 1) m. (**connected with √*aś* and *aśnas*, perhaps derived from *aśman***) — stone, rock; 2) a stone for slinging, missile stone. As PW explains it, seemingly *aśani*, *aśva* and *āśu* have all derived from *aś*, which implies a quick movement. Hence, MW gives following senses for *āśu* 1) m.f.n. fast, quick, going quickly; 2) m. Vedic — the quick one, a horse; 3) ind., quickly, quick, immediately, directly.

PW gives the following additional senses: 4) adv., quickly, urgently, on the spot, immediately; 5) adj. quick to put together, quick to reconcile; 6) m. the swift one, the steed.

Cf. Gk. ὤκύς, ὄκιστος; Lat. *acu* in *acupedius*, *ocissimus*: of the same origin may be the Lat. *aquila* and *accipiter*; Latv. *ašs* ‘quick’; Lith. *ašva* ‘sharp’.

Noteworthy is the fact that in modern Latvian language an adj. for ‘quick’ is *ašs*, and adv. ‘quickly’ is *aši*. Whereas, there is no counterpart in modern Lithuanian.

Another cognate — *aśman*— given by both MW and PW stands for 1) m. an eater; 2) m. a stone, rock; 3) a precious stone; 4) any instrument made of stone (as a hammer etc.); 5) thunderbolt; 6) a cloud; 7) the firmament.

Cf. Zenda *asman*; Pers. *ašmān*; Latv. *asmens*, *akmens*; Lith. *ašmuo*, *ašmenys*, *akmuo*; Slav. *kamenj* (камень)].

Being a native Latvian speaker, I can elaborate on the Latvian notions that are still in use, namely, *asmens* stands for ‘a sharp edge’ of any cutting, chopping, or stabbing tool or weapon, and *akmens* stands for ‘stone’ or ‘rock’. Lithuanian lexemes have even retained closer phonetic resemblance.

¹⁵ Nakṣatra — here, an asterism or constellation through which the moon passes, a lunar mansion (27, later 28). (MONIER-WILLIAMS, 1899).

Mayrhofer gives following etymology to *ásani*: f. Donnerkeil ‘Thunderbolt’, Pfeilspitze, ‘arrowhead’, *aśanimant-* mit Donnerkeil versehen ‘fitted with thunderbolt’; Indo-Germanic *h₂ek — escharf ‘sharp’, spitz ‘pointed’ (~*ásman-*, *ásri-*); cf. similar formations in Gk. ἄχων m. Wurfspieß ‘spear’, f. Wetzstein ‘whetstone’ (Mayrhofer, 1986: 136).

As regards to *aśva*, Mayrhofer gives the same principal meanings as MW and PW. I will only specifically point out an etymological thread of cognates in other languages.

Cf. Indo-Aryan in an ancient Near East **ašua-* ‘horse’ in a name as *Bi-ri-da-aš-ua*, *Bi-ri-ja-aš-šu-ua* (= **prīta-aśva-*, **priya-aśva-* Vedic *áśvān prī-*, Avestan *Frināspa* — a proper name; An Iranian proper name; in Elamite rendition it is (*Pir-ri-ya-iš-ba*); Indo-Iranian, Young Avestan *aspa-* m. ‘horse’; Old Avestan, Young Avestan f. *aspā* ‘mare’; Old Persian m. *asa* ‘horse’; Khotanian *aśśa*; Sogdia *'sp*. There are many textual figures in Indo-Iranian ‘*ásva-* ... *arušá-*, *áśvānām árvatām*, cf. to Vedic *áśv-ásva-* = Young avestan *āsu.aspa-* and the same *āśú*. Vedic *viṣita aśva*; Old Avestan, Young Avesta *Vīštāspa* - Old Persian *vīštasp*); a proper name in Lith; Young Avestan *aspaiia* — descended from the horse, from steeds standing. Indo-German m. *epicoenum*, hence not f. ‘equa’; Lat. *Equos*; Old Irisch *ech*; Old English *eoh* etc.

On top of that, Mayrhofer points out possible origins of the lemma *aśva* from a Hittite text on the horse training “Kikkuli” where *assussanni*¹⁶ ‘a horse trainer’ is mentioned, which probably originates from Hurroid and could be a derivative from a West Semitic **susu* ‘horse’. However, Mayrhofer, based on the studies by Diakonoff and T. V. Gamkrelidze - V. V. Ivanov, also concedes borrowing of this stem from Old-Iranian into Anatolian languages (Mayrhofer, 1986: 139–140).

In their voluminous study, the Russian linguists T. V. Gamkrelidze and V. V. Ivanov provide a reconstructed Proto-IE term for the horse, namely **ek^hwos* — without a distinction between grammatical genders, which is attested in all early IE dialects. Luwian *á-sù-wa* ‘horse’; Mitannian Aryan ^{LÚ}*a-aš-šu-uš-ša-an-ni* ‘horse trainer’ (equivalent to Sanskrit *aśvasani-* ‘groom’), literally ‘acquirer of horses’. In addition to the samples given by Mayrhofer, their study provides many more cognates, for example: Wakhi *yaš*; Ossetic *Jæfs*; Gk. (Mycenian) *i-qa* ‘horse’; Homeric *híppos* ‘horse’ (with geminate -pp- from **-k^hw-*); Venetic *eku-* in the compound *ekupeθaris*, apparently originally ‘pertaining to a wheelwright’; Lat. *equus* “horse’; Old Irish *ech*; Gaulish, *epo-* ‘horse’ in names like *Epo-na* “mulionum dea’ – ‘goddess of coachmen’, i. e. ‘horse goddess’; Old English *eoh* “horse’; Old Icelandic *jór*; Gothic *aílva-* “horse’; Tocharian A *yuk*, B *yakwe*

¹⁶ Cf. Asko Parpola; *aššuššanni* = Indo-Aryan *aśva-śā-ḥ* (Parpola, 2015: 75–76).

‘horse’. It is also noted that in some dialects independently emerged special feminine forms for ‘mare’: in Sanskrit *áśvā*; Avestan *aspā-*; Lat. *equa*, Lith. *ešvā, ašvā*. Furthermore, the evolution of languages yields other ancient derivatives in -n- related to horses. Thus, in Lat. *equinus* ‘equine’; pertaining (cf. Umbrian *ekvine*); Lith. *ašvīenis* ‘workhorse’; Old Prussian *aswinan* ‘horse's milk; kumiss’, Sanskrit, also Vedic *aśvin-* ‘having horses’ (Gamkrelidze et al., 1994: 463–464).

In addition, Lithuanian mythological deities *Ašvieniai* are not only linguistic cognates, but also bear functional and ontological homologies with the Vedic *Aśvins*. Furthermore, from a personal communication with my fellow from the University of Latvia, I learned that at the end of 1960s/beginning of 70s, in the Southeastern part of Latvia, Latgale, and in particular in *Kozīne* village (*Kozīnes ciems*), Vilaka (*Viļaka*) district, a ‘workhorse’ was called *ašviņš*.

Noteworthy is to mention here, that Plato dedicated an entire dialogue ‘Cratylus’ to this theme of word formation. There, he elaborates at great length on the derivation and origins of the words based on the motion of the objects. Particularly relevant in this context is his explanation on the origins of one of the names of goddess Athena.

[406e-407a] “[...] who think this name is derived from armed dances, for lifting oneself or anything else from the ground or [407a] in the hands is called shaking (πάλλειν) and being shaken, or dancing and being danced. [...] So that is the reason she is called Pallas” (Plato, 1921).

Hence, this lengthy prelude on etymology can help to draw particular conclusions on the origin of the Sanskrit (Vedic) notion *aśvin* within IE geographical and linguistic area, and beyond its boundaries. Thus, a tentative preliminary conclusion could be drawn that the notion for a quick or swift (movement) could have been derived from a hissing sound of the swift motion of a stone age weapon. In turn, most likely it was then projected to the swiftness of the horse-ride; and hence, a domesticized horse acquired its designation containing such basic morphemes as: **-as/-aš; -asv- /ašv-**. See diagram No. 1.

Another point supporting this hypothesis is that in RV the *Aśvins* are typically described as:

1) the swift ones:

c.d. tābhir no maḥsū tūyām aśvinā gātam bhiṣajyataṁ yad ātūram || (RV 8.22.10)¹

or

2) their weapons, chariot, or their horses having the attributes of swiftness:

c.d. **br̥haspatīm víśván devām aham̐ hūva indrāviṣṇū āśvīnāv āśuheṣasā¹⁷ || (RV 8.10.2)**

Diagram No. 1. Etymology of the proper name of the *Āśvins*

[Monier-Williams, 1899; Böhtlingk & Roth, 1855; Cambridge et al., 1994; Mayrhofer 1986; Jamison & Brereton, 2014; Parpola 2015; <http://assyrianlanguages.org>; <http://psdmuseum.upenn.edu>; <https://rekalbat.h>]

Created by **Natalija Burdina** © 2022

Presented with XMind

¹⁷ Jamison & Brereton's translation of *āśuheṣasā* as 'swift missiles' is arguable as both members of the *Karmadhāraya* type of compound, *āśu* carries the meaning of 'quick, fast, swift' and *hēṣas* 'quickness, vigour, fire'; also 'wound'. However, PW derives it from verbal root *hiš* related to *hiḍ*, *hiṭ* meaning 'make angry, vex, offend', whereas MW relates it to *heṣ*, meaning 'to neigh, whinny' and if connected to *hi* — 'to be quick or strong or fiery' (Böhtlingk and Roth, 1855; MONIER-WILLIAMS, 1899). Onomastically, neighing is the sound attributed to horses; hence, more probable translation would be then 'with the swift *neighers*' — an epithet of their swift horses. Cf. Heinrich Lüders who translates it as a *Bahuvrīhi* 'whose weapon is swift' (in Thieme, 1960, p. 315).

1.2 Locus of celestial deities – Aśvins – in IE cosmology

Twin deities are known across the cultures, and as such always represent some unique characteristics. Using Donald Ward’s terminology, the Aśvins can be categorized as *parallel twins*¹⁸ i.e., the same sex twins who are well attested in IE tradition. Donald Ward points out several universalisms that accompany the birth and life of the divine twins, such as having different fathers — one of whom is a celestial divinity; the twins have different character traits; they are invoked to defend their mistreated mother; and they are also worshipped as divinities responsible for fertility.

However, not all of these universalisms are represented in the case of the Aśvins. Since, the focus of this study is to investigate the shifting agency of the Aśvins playing a role in the *Dioskuric* pattern (Ward, 1968: 3–6), therefore, only the universalisms that fall into this pattern will be enlisted here:

1) Dual paternity where one of the fathers is a celestial divinity.

- c.d. *nānā jātāv arepasā sam asme bandhum eyāthuh* || (RV 5.73.4)²
- a.b. *ihehā jātā sam āvāvaśūtām arepasā tanvā₃ nāmābhiḥ svaiḥ* | (RV 1.181.4)³

2) They manifest different character traits; and thus, explicitly are responsible for different functional areas RV 1.181.4 cd.

- c.d. *jīṣṇur vām anyah sumākhasya sūrir dīvo anyah subhagāḥ putra ūhe* || (RV 1.181.4)⁴

Stig Wikander in his article “Nakula et Sahadeva” demonstrates these differences on the example of the mythic descendants of the Aśvins — Nakula and Sahadeva — described in an Indian epic Mahābhārata. He also corroborates his findings with Geldner’s remark, where he states that the words *nāsatyā* and *dīvo napātā* should be analysed as Dvandva compound. Hence, it should be considered as the Nāsatyā and the Son of Heaven; and as such, the epithets of the Aśvins the Nāsatyā and the Dasra should be treated as *ekāśeṣa*. Consequently, according to Wikander, in RV 1.184.4c Nāsatyā should be considered as the heavenly son of *Dasra* (Wikander, 1957).

3) Twice they are mentioned separately, namely — Nāsatyā¹⁹ — grammatically it is expressed in Sg. Thus, describing only one of the twins.

¹⁸ Another category according to Ward — *cross twins* — those of opposite sex, for instance — the Vedic Yama and Yamī, the Norse Askr and Embl; and also African two sets of cross twins, the integral protagonists of Creation myth, namely, Ogo (male) with its unnamed female twin and Nommo with its unnamed twin, both being sons of Supreme God (Iloanusi, 1984: 130–134; Ward, 1968: 3).

¹⁹ Nāsatyāya — here, grammatically it is in m. Dat. Sg.; cf. Thieme (Thieme, 1960: 315); Elizarenkova (Elizarenkova, 1999: 362); Geldner (Geldner, 1951: 420) — they all translate as one Nāsatyā in Sg.

- c.d. *parijmaṅe nāsatyāya kṣe bravaḥ kad āgne ruḍrāyā nṛghne* || (RV4.3.6)⁵
- a.b. *ā me āsya prātīvyā |m indranāsatyā²⁰ gatam* |
c.d. *devā devebhir ādya śacānāstamā* || (RV 8.26.8)⁶

4) They may have different parents:

- **Heaven** (RV 1.117.12; 1,182.1; 1,184.1; 3.38.5; 4.43.3; 4.44.2; 10.61.4).
c.d. *dhīyamjinvā dhiṣṇyā viśpalāvasū dīvo napātā sukṛte śucivratā* || (RV1.182.1)⁷
- **The River Sindhu as their mother.**
a.b. *yā dāsrā sindhūmātarā maṅtarā rayīnām* |
c.d. *dhīyā devā vāsūvidā* || (RV1.46.2)⁸
- **Vivasvant (father) and Saraṇyū (mother).**
a.b. *apāgūhann amrtām martyēbhyaḥ kṛtvī savārnām adadur vivāsvate* |
c.d. *utāśvināv abharḡd yat tad āsīd ajāhād u dvā mithunā saraṇyūḥ* || (RV 10.17.2)⁹

The Aśvins are also invoked in connection with Vivasvant and the Soma drink (RV 1.46.13); and yoking of their chariot induces the birth of Dawn and the halves of the day whose ruler is Vivasvant (RV 10.39.12).

- **They are fathers of Pūṣan.**

- a.b. *yad āsvinā pṛcchamānāv ayātām tricakreṇā vahaṭum sūryāyāḥ* |
c.d. *viśve devā anu tad vām ajānan putrah pītarāv avṛṇīta pūṣā* || (RV 10.85.14)¹⁰

5) Both bear one name either in Sg. or in Du. See sub-chapter 1.1, pp. 10-12.

6) They are immortal (RV 5.43.17).

7) Uṣas (Dawn) is their sister²¹ (RV 1.180.2;

- c.d. *svasā yad vām viśvagūrti bharātī vājīyeṭṭe madhupāv iṣe cā* || (RV 1.180.2)¹¹

- Being Aśvins' sister, Uṣas is also called the Daughter of Dyaus (Heaven) — **Dīvo dūhītā** (1.92.5; 1.113.7; 1.124.3; 5.80.5; 7.75.4; 7.78.4); **Dīvo duhītā** (7.79.3; 7.80.1, 3, 5); **Dīvo dūhītur** (7.67.2); **Dīvo duhitaḥ** (6.65.6); **Dīvo duhitar**

²⁰ Indra and Nāsatyas — according to Thieme this should be translated as a Du. Dvandvā compound i.d., 'Indra & (one) Nāsatyā'; cf. also Konow with the statement supported by Thieme that Du. form *Nāsatyau* was developed in India (Thieme, 1960: 315); Macdonell explicitly states: "When two sing. subjects have one verb, the latter in most cases is in the dual" (Macdonell, 1916: 289); cf. Jamison & Brereton's commentary: "VIII.26.8: This vs. is somewhat curiously constructed. It contains, probably, a dual Dvandva whose second member is itself dual: *indra-nāsatyā* 'o Indra and the two Nāsatyas'. Since the form is in the Voc. it is actually impossible to determine if it is in fact a dual Dvandva or two separate Voc., *indra nāsatyā*, Sg. and Du. Although in most dual Dvandvas the first member also has dual inflection (type *indrā-vāruṇā*), see *indra-vāyū*, with stem form in the first member and a single second member accent; its Voc. is *indra-vāyū*, which would match the template found here. In any case, the verb is dual (*gatam*), and the rest of the verse (*pāda c*) is couched in the dual. This either means that Indra is being ignored (which is possible, since the hymn is dedicated to the Aśvins) or that the dual *dvandva* *indra-nāsatyā* is being treated as if it contained two entities, rather than one+two (which is also possible)" (Jamison and Brereton, n.d.).

²¹ Uṣas — is also a sister to Bhaga, and close like a sister to Varuṇa (RV 1.123.5).

(6.64.4); **Divo duhitar** (6.64.5); **Divo duhitar** (7.77.6; 7.81.5); **Dūhītā dīvo** (5.80.6); **Dīvo devī dūhītā** (7.79.3); **Duhītā divo** (6.65.1); **Duhitar divaḥ**²² (1.30.22; 1.48.1; 1.48.9; 5.79.2-3; 5.79.8; 8.47.15) **Dūhitar divaḥ** (1.49.2; 8.47.14; 10.127.8); **Duhitar divo** (5.79.9); **Duhitar diva** (7.81.3); **Duhītā dīva** (1.48.8); **Duhītā dīvaḥ** (7.81.1). Daughters of Heaven in plural four times — **Dīvo dūhitaro** (4.51.1); **Divo duhitaro** (4.51.10); **Divo duhitaro** (4.51.11); **Dīvo dūhitrā** (10.70.6); and also the Aśvins' companion four times. (1.180.1; **Dīvo dūhitrā** 1.183.2; 4.52.2-3; 8.5.2). Thus, collectively the Uṣas is addressed as the Daughter(s) of Heaven 37 times and the companions of the Aśvins four times.

However, there are a few instances that unmistakably narrate the incest between Dyaus and his daughter Uṣas (RV 1.71.5,8; 10.61.5-7); and also alluding to Uṣas being a beloved one of Sūrya, the Sun God (RV 1.92.11; 7.75.4); cf. Jamison & Brereton (2014); Geldner (1953); cf. Grassmann (1877); cf. Elizarenkova (1999). The relationships of the Aśvins with Dawn and the Sun Maiden, also called the daughter or sister of the Sun, in the role of husbands and wooers reflected in the RV will be elaborated in Chapter 2.

Let us begin by giving an insight into the universal Divine Twin pattern²³. As a rule, they are horse patrons, and they drive a chariot that brings the sun and sunlight to all the living beings, hence, these celestial deities are considered the divinities of Light. Their chariot is also associated and seen above the water bodies; they function as rescuers, helpers, and wonder makers. They usually have different fathers/parents; one of them is Heaven (father), the other — mortal; thus, they are called Sons of God/Heaven. They have a bride/sister — the Sun Maiden, and sister — Dawn; in some traditions the dimension of incest and polyandria is also present, namely, the twin brothers may be also depicted as suitors or husbands of the Sun Maiden who is typically their sister (MacDonell, 1897: 49–54; Ward, 1968: 9–29; Zeller, 1990: 111).

The Graeco-Roman tradition displays an array of twin sets — heroic and divine, which are well documented by Herodotus, Pausanias, Plutarch a. o. Among them, however, the most famous pair, are the Spartan *Dioskuoroi* (*Castor*²⁴ & *Polydeuces*²⁵; lat. *Pollux*), the Horsemen, who were patrons of seamen and warriors. The cult of the *Dioskuoroi* was already attested in the eleventh

²² Duhitar Divaḥ — O, Daughter of Heaven; duhitar — f. Voc. Sg.; divaḥ m. Gen. Sg. (Kielhorn, 1880: 51; 53)

²³ See more in (Güntert, 1925: 253–276; cf. Ward, 1968).

²⁴ Castor — ancient Gr.: Κάστωρ, romanized: Kástōr, literary 'beaver'; 'Castor fiber' (*Biblissima Toolkit*, n.d.).

²⁵ Polydeuces — ancient Gr.: Πολυδεύκης, romanized: Polydeúkēs, lit. 'very sweet' (*Biblissima Toolkit*, n.d.).

book of the Odyssey (11.298–304) (Larson, 2007: 189). Eventually, their cult spread across all Mediterranean areas; and was also adopted and attested in the Roman tradition (Ward, 1968: 9). One of the greatest conundrums posed to the scholarship starting from the early native commentator Yāska and ending with contemporary researchers elsewhere, it has been the identification of the Aśvins with natural or superhuman phenomena. Numerous theories and assumptions have been proposed, which will be enlisted here in order to provide a foundation on the research covering more than 200 years. Hopefully, this study will contribute in adding a new perspective to the existing scholarship; and thus, will elucidate a potentially new vision on this IE Divine Twins pattern when localized in ancient India.

In the first section I will expound on the theories proposed by the Indian native scholar Yāska and further on developed by the Western scholarship covering the time frame up to the middle of the 20th century.

I. Theories proposed from ca. 500-700 BCE up to 1900s.

Max Friedrich Müller first mentions the resemblance of the Vedic Aśvins to the Greek *Dioskuoroi* in 1868.

She, the Dawn, whose cart is drawn by white horses, is carried away in triumph by the two Asvins,' as the Leukippides are carried off by the *Dioskuoroi* (Müller, 1868, pp. 94–95).

Nevertheless, it was Wilhelm Mannhardt who first published series of articles published in “*Zeitschrift für Ethnologie*” elucidating the similarities spotted in Latvian folksongs, namely, that the Latvian and Lithuanian Sons of God, according to him, represent Morning and Evening Star — the planet Venus (Mannhardt, 1875b: 305–306). Mannhardt concludes his fourth article on the Latvian²⁶ Sun myth asserting that it is a well-preserved IE sun mythology, which corresponds to the old Aryan and old Greek one:

Ausserdem aber stimmt im Ganzen der lettische Sonnen mythus so genau mit dem altarischen im Veda und dem altgriechischen überein, dass derjenige schwerlich auf Widerspruch stossen wird, welcher in ihm ein ziemlich treu erhaltenes Nachbild der proethnischen, indoeuropäischen Sonnenmythologie vor sich zu haben vermuthen mochte (Mannhardt, 1875c: 329).

Although, the majority of the researchers support this phenomenon to have sprung from the common IE past, and some even claim it to go back to Proto-IE period, there are a few scholars who raise objections based on factual discrepancies that cannot be applied to this representation. Thus, Helmut Rosenfield rightly points out the impossibility of the twin divinities to be the

²⁶ The title of the articles — ‘Die lettischen Sonnenmythen’ — is misleading, in fact, Mannhardt includes in his analyses also the Lithuanian folklore materials and Estonian that formally does not belong to the Indo-European tradition both linguistically and culturally.

representation of the Morning and Evening Star. See Chapter 3 that elaborates on astronomical data. See image No 2.

Image No. 2 Venus and the Moon in the night sky

Photo: Natālija Burišina, on the 26th April, 2020, time: 21:41, place: Heidelberg, Germany.

Despite of this modern-day logic, which is based on the empirical facts of astronomy, Ward finds proofs to Mannhardt's and others' conjecture in the traditional beliefs of North and South American Indians as well as in Latvian dainas²⁷. This daina clears the ambiguity by describing the Sun and the Moon riding one and the same steed; and dainas No. 33898-1,2; 33854-0 explicitly narrate that the Moon does not needs steeds, as the Morning and Evening Star are his steeds. However, this should not be a deciding factor, since elsewhere the Sons of God (*Dieva dēli*) are not recognized as the Morning or Evening Star.

²⁷ *I saulīte, i mēnesniņš,
Jāj uz viena kumeliņa;
Jau saulīte noseģloja,
Mēnesniņš apseģloja.* (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 54915).

English translation by the author; an improved version to the one given in Ward: Both the Sun and the Moon, ride on one steed; Already [as soon as] the Sun dismounted, the Moon mounted on [was ready to go] (Ward, 1968: 16).

Although, Helmut Günther in his voluminous study elucidates on many disparities between the Greek *Dioskuoroi* and the Vedic *Aśvins* induced under the influence of local developments, in general, he justly places the *Aśvins* within the IE Dioskuric pattern (Güntert, 1925: 260–266).

Up to this date the *Aśvins* have been identified mostly as the representation of nature phenomena.

1. In this frequently cited passage from Nirukta: “*Atha ato dyusthānāḥ | tāsām Aśvinau prathamāgāminau bhavataḥ | Aśvinau yad vyaśnuvāte sarvaṃ rasena anyo jyotiṣā anyāḥ | Aśvair aśvināv ity Aurnānbāvaḥ | tat kāv Aśvinau | dyāvāpṛthiviyāv ity eke | ‘horātrāv ity eke | sūryacandramasāv ity eke | rajānau puṇyaktāv ity aitihāskāḥ | tayoh kālah ūrdvham urdhvarātrāt prakāśībhāvasya anuviṣṭambham anu | tamobhāgo hi madhyamo jyotirbhāgaḥ ādityaḥ || 1 || [...] Tayoh kālah suryodīyaparyantaḥ tasminn anyā devata āpyante [...] || 5 ||,*” Yāska reflects the account of his contemporaries by narrating: Now, on the deities whose sphere is the heaven ; of these the *Aśvins* are the first to arrive. They are called the *Aśvins*, because they pervade everything, the one with moisture, the other with light. Aurnābhāva [says they are called] the *Aśvins*, (because they possess horses). Who, then, are these *Aśvins*? **Some [say they are] Heaven & Earth, some — Day & Night, some — the Sun & the Moon, [and] itihāsa — the two benevolent kings.**

Their time is subsequent to midnight, whilst the manifestation of light is delayed; [and ends with the rising of the sun, *ibid.* xii. 5]. The dark portion [of this time] denotes the inter-mediate (god= Indra?), the light portion Aditya (the Sun)" (Muir, 1870: 234; Yāska, 1942: 1099; 1104).

2. Based on this passage Rudolf von Roth concludes that in Yāska’s view the *Aśvins* represent Indra and the Sun (ādityaḥ) (in Muir, 1870, p. 235).

3. Morning/Evening Star hypothesis has been mostly favoured among scholars starting with Mannhardt (Mannhardt, 1875a, pp. 305–306), followed by Hermann Oldenberg (Oldenberg, 1988, pp. 108–109), Güntert whose strong conviction towards this theory was based on Mannhardt’s study of the Latvian folk songs, where he admittedly recognizes the most ancient and purest repository of the IE mythological characters and patterns (Güntert, 1925: 266); and finally, Friedrich Bollensen whose explanation of this phenomena is following. Despite being only one star — Venus — its morning appearance precedes the sun’s rising in the West, and as the Evening Star it follows the sun in the East. As their chariot is three seated (*tribandhura*²⁸; *sic.*) the Dawn

²⁸ This must be misspelled for *trivandhurá*, which could possibly be rendered as ‘with three standing places’; cf. Jamison & Brereton (2014); cf. Geldner (1951); cf. Grassmann (1877). This is a typical depiction in ancient Indian iconography. See iconography on this website: <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/1269/chariots-in-ancient-indian-warfare> (Lal, 2018); This compound occurs in RV 1.47.2; 1.118.1-2; 1.157.3; 1.183.1; 7.69.2; 7.71.4; 8.22.5; 8.85.8; 9.62.17. *Tribandhur* — *tri* + *bandhu*, meaning ‘triple kinship/relations/bonds (MONIER-WILLIAMS, 1899). This compound occurs only once in the RV 7.37.7, which is dedicated to Indra.

(*Uṣas*) sits in between them, so that one *Aśvin*, the Morning Star, sits before her, and the other, the Evening Star, behind her. She herself sits in the middle of both; and thus, the process in nature is preserved (Bollensen, 1887: 497).

4. Although, Leopold von Schroeder finds Oldenberg's research results completely accurate (Schroeder, 1895: 129), he admittedly points out that it is based on Mannhardt's study. In preceding pages, he also expresses conjecture that **the *Aśvins* could represent the Moon who marries the Sun Maiden (*Sūryā*)** (Ibid., 126).

Alfred Hillebrandt in analysing this theory was more sceptical to draw parallels between the three groups of the Vedic *Aśvins*, Greek *Dioskuoroi*, and Baltic *Dieva dēli* with the Morning and Evening Star, and, therefore, drops it until more substantial proofs are put forward.

5. Another popular theory was that **the *Aśvins* represent the star constellation known in the Western world as Gemini, namely the two stars: Castor²⁹ (Alpha (α) Geminorum) & Pollux³⁰ (Beta (β) Geminorum)**. See image No. 2. Albrecht Weber sympathizes it and even draws his conclusion based on the fact the *Aśvins*, or as he names them — the Light Geniuses — because they are always accompanied by *Uṣas*, and as such, they connect two points in the sky; of them the first lights up at dawn, and being the prototype of youth and beauty, therefore, one could recognise in them the double stars of the Greek *Dioskuoroi*. As this star constellation is visible in the Northern Hemisphere, it was considered as the saviour among the sailors in stormy nights; whereas, for the Aryan shepherds as they were eventually penetrating deeper into the southern regions of India, this constellation lost its importance. In the end, however, he concludes that there is no support found in RV for this theory; hence, it requires more examination (Weber, 1862: 234–235). Later, in the same volume, Weber refers to Wilhelm Julius Foerster's calculations for the upper part of the Panjab, where at the altitude of 34° pole height, according to which Gemini (Twins) could possibly be located there around 1200 BCE from the end of April, or around 2200 BCE from the first third of April, or around 3200 BCE from mid-March onwards; and thus, were considered morning stars for 4-6 weeks i.e., standing for 2-3 hours before the sun rises in the morning sky (Ibid., 266). Alfred Hillebrandt adds that further on, Weber returns to Foerster's calculations, and then finds out that Gemini were visible in Armenia during vernal equinox ca. 6000 BCE, and finally finds a proper grounding for this theory. Hillebrandt favours this theory as

²⁹ Castor — seemingly looking as a single star to the naked eye is in fact a complex multiple star. With a magnification of 100x, a 3-inch or larger scope should split Castor into two similar-looking stars, one mag. +1.9 (Castor A) and the other mag. +3.0 (Castor B) (Lawrence, 2023).

³⁰ Pollux — despite its beta status, mag. +1.2 Pollux (Beta (β) Geminorum) is the brightest star in Gemini and the 17th brightest star in the night sky (Ibid.).

it includes the connection with Dawn, which draws onto analogy with the Greek *Dioskuoroi*. Concomitantly, he draws attention to two striking idiosyncrasies: 1) that no other star has risen to the pedestal in IE mythology; 2) that the Greeks and Indians have retained it as the only spring heralding stars since 6000 BCE; 3) and no other constellations that have been described, have ever taken such a prominent role mythologically. Hillebrandt rightly remarks another discrepancy in this theory, namely, number three with which their chariot is usually associated. Without providing any substantial proofs he correlates it with the three seasons (Hillebrandt, 1902: 388–389).

Image No.3 Castor & Pollux

Image credit: <https://www.nasa.gov> (Jet Propulsion Laboratory, 2012)

6. The Aśvins — initially humans, the famous warriors and healers who were divinized, purely of Indian origin; not representing any astronomical phenomena visible in the sky.

Thus, in Theodor Goldstücker’s opinion two distinct elements, namely, cosmical and human became blended into one:

The historical or human element in it, I believe, is represented by those legends which refer to the wonderful cures effected by the Aśvins, and to their performances of a kindred sort; the cosmical element is that relating to their luminous nature. [...] It would appear then that these Aśvins, like the *Ṛibhus* (sic.), were originally renowned mortals, who, in the course of time, were translated into the companionship of the gods [...] (in Muir, 1870: 255–257).

Of similar views was Karl F. Geldner who majorly relied on Sāyana’s commentary and, therefore, elaborated this concept by discussing the battle scenes and related vocabulary (Pischel and Geldner, 1897: 31–42).

7. The Aśvins as the Rain Gods. This theory was proposed by Hans Sofus Vodskov in which he attempts to demonstrate that etymologically their name is rather derived from *aśu* — ‘fast’ —

attributing them with a special characteristic of swiftness, than *aṣva* that most of the scholars have adopted in their theories, namely, ‘the possessing of horses’. Another argument to corroborate his theory is that they are described in the RV pouring moisture and mead on to the lands, which Vodskov considers synonymous with ghee and thus rain. According to him, the Vedic Rain Gods are Light Gods, and being invoked in the morning they had their own relationship with the sun (Vodskov, 1897: 485–503).

8. Edward Hopkins on his part, presumes that the dual nature of the Aśvins is best explained by surmising them to be **twilight**:

[...] the twinlights or twilight, before dawn, half dark and half bright [...]. Their duality represents, then, not successive stages but one stage in day’s approach, when light is dark and dark is light. [...] but no less is there a triality in connection with them which often in describing them has been ignored. This is that threefold light which opens day; and, as in many cases they join with Dawn, so their color is inseparable. Strictly speaking, the break of red is the dawn and the white and yellow lights precede this.

He finds support to this presumption in Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa 5.4.1., where a red-white goat is sacrificed to them, because the Aśvins themselves are of red-white colour. He concludes with the statement that one of **their chief functions was finding and restoring the vanished light** (Hopkins, 1895: 82–83).

His predecessor Laurentios Myriantheus, 20 years earlier had come to the same conclusions in the monograph dedicated to the Aśvins “*Die Aṣvins oder arischen Dioskuren*,” i.e., that the twinlights have given rise to the origins, and hence deification of the Aśvins. As the chariot riders they take part both in the dark and the light when their chariot goes to Savitar’s daughter Sūryā, which he considers to be a counterpart of Uṣas (Myriantheus, 1876, p. 34). In his later work “Comparative Mythology”, Müller consents and elaborates Yāska’s view (i.e., the twins that are born together before early twilight), namely:

Nature in her twofold aspect of daily change — morning and evening, light and darkness — aspects which in time may expand into those of spring and winter, life and death; nay, even of good and evil (Müller, 1913, pp. 611–612).

See No. 10, where Müller in his earlier works opines on the Sun & Moon theory.

9. In his earlier writings, Mannhardt based on his research on the Latvian solar mythologeme, concluded that the evening twilight and the morning twilight, and therefore also the evening and the morning gloaming, appear as a coherent, unified phenomenon (Mannhardt, 1875b, p. 232). Similarly, he asserted about the Sons of God who were apparently a double apparition as the Evening and Morning Star, which was sometimes taken as single and called the Son of God in Sg., and sometimes leading to the assumption of two Sons of God, who then infrequently, be it in the evening or in the morning acting collectively (Mannhardt, 1875b, p. 306). This view in general

lines was also supported by Max Müller in relation to the *Aśvins*. **Thus, in 1863 and later in 1887 Müller still maintains the idea that the two *Aśvins* as male deities represent light and darkness** as well as temporality representing all that happens during the day (Müller, 1897, pp. 558; 583, 1913, p. 606). He then further evolves his hypothesis by claiming the *Aśvins* to be viewed as the sons of *Uṣas* through patronymic interpretation of their name i.e., the sons of *Aśvā* — one of the frequently used epithets to address *Uṣas*; or descendants of the sun, which is clearly insufficiently corroborated assumption (Müller, 1897, p. 564).

10. The *Aśvins* as the Sun & Moon. This theory was propounded by Alfred Ludwig in which he linked it to the myth of the *Ṛbhus*³¹ who stayed at *Savitar*'s house; thus, he locates it temporally to winter solstice when the seasons stand still (RV 1.161.13)¹². In spite of the fact that the stanza clearly states the *Ṛbhus* spent there one year, Ludwig points to 12 days mentioned in the RV 4.33.7. From the fact that the *Ṛbhus* spent at *Agohya*'s house he infers implicit indication to three seasons in the RV 1.34.2¹³, which is a farfetched conclusion, to my mind. Similarly, Ludwig's theory lacks details on the *Aśvins* connection with the moon (Ludwig, 1876: 234–235). An extended analyses of solar & lunar primordial twinship that has been reflected in numerous IE mythologies was expounded by Max Müller in 1881 as well as in his translation of the RV 1.92.17 he mentions that occasionally they can be identified with the sun and moon (Müller, 1869: 599–614, 1869: 124; 239). More overtly, however, Ludwig expressed this identification referring his analyses to the RV *Maṇḍala* 10, the hymn 29. Thus, he concludes that both *Nāsatyas* here represent *Indra* and *Soma*, hence, the sun and the moon (Ludwig, 1883: 195). Allusion to the *Aśvins* in this hymn, as the deities invoked at dawn, has been likewise noticed by Jamison & Brereton (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 1420).

Nearly 20 years later, Edmund Hardy also inclines towards this hypothesis, noting however, that provided the sun and the moon are considered the twins. Concomitantly, he admits that the majority of Comparative Mythology researchers are in favour of other conjectures. Hardy built his line of argument based on numerous epithets that describe them as the divinities of Light; and as such they are referred without distinction as the sons of *Dyaus* (Heaven) (RV 1.182.1; cf. 10.61.4; 4.43, 3.44.2), but one is described as a victorious hero (*sumakhasya*), the other considered rich as Heaven's son (RV 1.181.4). Heaven's son is specified as the sun in RV 10.37.1, but the sun itself is considered a hero (*makha*) (RV 1.6.8; 1.138.1; 6.71.1), hence the son of the sun is referred to as the moon. The first objection goes against RV 3.44.2. — the entire hymn is dedicated to *Indra*

³¹ *Ṛbhus* — the creators of the *Aśvins* chariot (RV 1.20.3).

(Hardy, 1893: 47–49). The sun’s identification with Heaven’s son is referred to in Maṇḍala 10, which is in *communis opinio* a rather late addition to the family core hymns of RV. Therefore, this is a very thin line of argument even to further considering that the son of the sun is to be inferred as the moon.

Although, Hillebrandt devotes the largest section on discussing the Aśvins identification with the Sun & Moon, his own stance remains unclear. He solely refutes their identification with ‘Benevolent Kings’, yet admittedly surrenders to propose another theory (Hillebrandt, 1902: 390–396).

11. Releasing of the Sun from darkness.

In a very detailed analyses of the mythical legends, where the Aśvins are described as the wonder makers, Theodor Baunack introduces another view — this is a phenomenon of the light or the sun being rescued from darkness during the 12 days of winter solstice. Baunack compares it with the human birth process, namely the 10th day on which Bhujū was rescued, represents the 10 months of the confinement in the darkness of a female womb. In addition to that, the numbers three, four, and 100 very intricately, according to Baunack, refer also to the division of the year following the embryonic development in the womb, where the remaining 12 days and nights during winter solstice is the time when the sun is reborn (Baunack, 1896: 263; 286, 1898: 541–544). Alluding to the Aśvins, Max Müller interprets *tamās tīrah* as ‘having dispersed the darkness’ in RV 1.46.6b (Müller, 1869: 124).

II. Theories proposed from 1900s up to present day.

Attempts and speculations to identify the nature and actual source for the nomination of the Aśvins into the Vedic pantheon has continued ever since up to a present day. However, only a few scholars have proposed brand new theories substantiated with satisfactory and convincing evidences. In most cases, scholars have simply enlisted already existing speculations. Among them, Arthur Berriedale Keith, in 1925 explains the obscurity of their mythical origins due to the antiquity of their phenomenon. Moreover, they gained a greater personality over the course of transmission of their cult, which, in sum, prevents from recognizing the natural substratum. Nevertheless, Keith proposes the Aśvins could have been once regarded as horses themselves; and thus, the sun was conceived as a horse. Then, according to an old tradition, the Aśvins mother was called a mare (Keith, 1998a: 113–119).

In 1960 Paul Thieme convincingly demonstrates the affinity of *Mitrā-Varuṇā*, *Indraḥ*, *Nāsatyā* with a warrior cult also attested in Mitanni-Hatti treaties, where these Aryan deities were

mentioned as the guardians of a contract in exactly the same order (Thieme, 1960, pp. 315–317). See also footnote No. 8.

Thirty years later, in her encompassing doctoral dissertation “Die Vedischen Zwillingsgötter” entirely devoted to the *Aśvins* theme, Gabriele Zeller investigates nearly all proposed theories at length. Although, she does not bring forward a new theory, she admits the *Aśvins* being the counterparts of the Greek *Dioskuoroi* as well as *Sūryā aka Uṣas* to be the third entity that corresponds to the description of the *Aśvins* tripartite vehicle. At the same time, Zeller neither supports the theory of the Morning/Evening Star nor the stellar nature of the *Aśvins* as the *Aśvinī nakṣatra* became a heralding star constellation of spring equinox rather late. Moreover, the Vedic astronomic treaties were composed comparatively late, namely, during the first centuries of CE majority of which were heavily influenced by the Greek astronomy. She also points out the historical and cultural discrepancies to identify them with the star constellation Gemini, which was seen in Armenia 6000 BCE (Zeller, 1990: 91–99).

A brand-new perspective in the *Aśvins* research quest was cast by Asko Parpola in his voluminous study that demonstrated determinately the *Aśvins* cult firstly had represented dual kingship of a deified two-man chariot team in the Sintashta-Arkaim culture of the Volga steppes and the southern Urals ca. 2000 BCE, which was eventually spread to Proto-Greeks, Proto-Balts and to the Proto-Finno-Ugrians of the mid-Volga and mid-Urals, who were ruled by a Proto-Aryan-speaking elite and most plausibly their initial functions as saviours and funeral gods. He corroborates his hypothesis with the corresponding passages from RV.

A funerary function for the *Aśvins* is suggested by the stories of Atri, Kakṣivant, Cyavāna, Vandana and several other persons whom the *Aśvins* rescued from distress or rejuvenated, though they were lying buried as if dead. In other words, as “healers” and “saviours”, the *Aśvins* were largely psychopomps and revivers of the dead. The rejuvenation accomplished by the *Aśvins* is several times compared to the renovation of an old chariot (Parpola, 2005: 30).

Parpola provides various details on the Geek burial tradition that involved either horse sacrificing on a funerary pyre or athletic contests of the horse drawn chariots. Likewise, he draws attention on Willem Caland’s study that narrated the pre-Christian traditions of the Baltic peoples that entailed horse races on the day of the burial, namely,

The prize consisted either of money placed on the top of the goal post, or of property of the deceased, divided and placed at certain intervals along the route. The burial day ended in a drinking bout (Ibid., 31).

To corroborate his theory Parpola proposes new interpretation of the frequently cited RV hymn 1.116 that describes the chariot race, namely, that this is an actual evidence of a funerary chariot race held in ancient India (Ibid., 31-32). In sum, Parpola's hypothesis is following:

Particularly important is the term *stambha*, which denoted the turning post of chariot races and the world mountain around which the two Aśvins, as the day and night aspects of the sun, make their daily circles. The sun and the fire represented these white and black aspects of the sun, symbolized by the wheel, the chariot, and the horse. The night sky was imagined to be an ocean, and the night-sun, or fire, was hiding as a man- or horse-shaped embryo in its womb (Ibid.).

Toshifumi Gotō in his article “Aśvin and Nāsatya in the Rigveda and their Prehistoric Background” published in 2006, considers the Morning/Evening Star theory most viable, where the Aśvins chariot carries the Sun God³²; and likewise, elaborates on their miraculous saviour nature. In essence, the Aśvins rescue the sun during its setting time. Moreover, the etymological explanation of the name Nāsatya i.e., ‘safe return home’ is investigated as rooting from Mitanni-Hatti treaties ca. 1400 BCE (Gotō, 2006 in; Witzel, 2018). Three years later, Gotō furthers his research and leans towards Hesperus-Lucifer³³ theory earlier proposed by Oldenberg and Günther despite of critique presented by Hillebrandt.

³² The Sun God — Savitar, according to Herman Oldenberg, is the oldest theonym that in fact represents the abstract notion of impelling. Savitar is mostly represented in the oldest layer of the RV i.e., family books, while majority dedicated to Sūrya are in the first and tenth books that are considered newer additions. Thus, Sūrya is a newer linguistic formation used to designate the Sun god in the RV. Macdonell, however, is of the opposing opinion (MacDonell, 1897: 32–35; Oldenberg, 1988b: 34–35).

³³ Hesperus — ancient Gr. Ἑσπερος, also called Vesper, in Greco-Roman mythology, the evening star; although initially considered to be the son of Eos (the Dawn) and the Titan Astraeus, he was later said to be the son or brother of Atlas. He was later identified with the morning star, Phosphorus, or Eosphorus (Latin: Lucifer), the bringer of light (later discovered by astronomers to be the planet Venus). Hesperus is variously described by different authors as the father or brother of the Hesperides (the guardians of the golden apples) or of their mother, Hesperis. ‘When Ceyx, the son of Hesperus (or Lucifer) and Philonis, perished in a shipwreck, his wife, Alcyone, the daughter of Aeolus and Aegiale, hurled herself into the sea out of love for him. The gods pitied both of them and turned them into birds, which are called halcyons. In wintertime these birds make their nest on the sea, produce their eggs, and give birth to their young, all within seven days’ time. During this period the sea is calm; sailors call these the “Halcyon Days” (Britannica, 2012; Trzaskoma et al., 2004: 501; 235).

Chapter 2: Invocation of Aśvins – Aśvina Śāstra

2.1. Solar mythologeme — an insight into Indo-European mythologies

A theory of common IE Solar Mythologeme was first brought to the limelight by Max Müller in the middle of the 19th century. By virtue of his work Müller became known as the father of Comparative Mythology and ardent propagator of culture evolutionism. Although, initially his theory gained a vivid interest and zealous followers, for instance, a British historian George William Cox. Other scholars, for instance, Edward Burnett Tylor and James George Frazer were also strong propagators of culture evolutionism. However, as Abram Smythe Palmer claims it at the foreword of the essay “Comparative Mythology”, by the turn of the 20th century it was refuted completely (Müller, 1909: vi). A similar fate of falling into decline of popularity by the middle of the 20th century, experienced the theory of diffusionism represented by George Elliot Smith and William James Perry in Great Britain, and by Father Peter Schmidt and Father Wilhelm Koppers. In his recent study, Kazuo Matsumura has not only rehabilitated Müller’s Solar Mythologeme, but also, based on the latest scientific discoveries in the fields of genetics, the collapse of colonial administrations, and putting aside of “romantic dream” of the researcher, presented substantial evidences for the revival of diffusionist theory (Matsumura, 2019). Since the research advancement in the fields of archeogenetics related to IE homeland issue is rather pointing to the Yamnaya culture or else known as Steppe pastoralists, therefore, the author of this research cannot agree with Matsumura’s view, who placed Tarim Basin as the dispersal source of IE (Lazaridis et al., 2022: 1; Matsumura, 2019: 48; Narasimhan et al., 2019: 1).

Now, for the sake of brevity, a synopsis of only three most prominent solar mythologeme models is exemplified here, namely, the Graeco-Roman, Baltic, and the Vedic one. Of the ancient Greek trio deities, it is worth to mention:

1. Amphion, Zethos, and Antiope in Thebes (parents, Zeus (Epepeus) and Antiope).
3. Dardanos, Jasion, and Harmonia in Arkadia (parents, Zeus (Korytos) and Elektra).
4. Pelias, Neleus, in Pylos (parents, Poseidon (Kretheus) and Tyro).
5. Herakles, Iphikles, and Alkmene in Thebes (parents, Zeus (Amphitryon) and Alkmene) (Müller, 1897: 578).

As pointed out by Donald Ward, the most striking homologies manifested in a typical solar mythologeme are following: 1) Divine twins have a heavenly father. The common source can be discerned not only at a functional level, but also at a linguistic one. Thus, the name of Heavenly Father is expressed in Skt. as *Dyaus pitā* (Voc. *pitar*), Gr. *Zeus pàter*, Latv. *Dievs*.

2) Divine twins have a sister — Dawn and a bride — the Sun Maiden. The Aśvins have a sister Uṣas (Dawn) and explicitly their bride is (the Sun Maiden) — or Sūryā addressed in RV as Duhitā sūryasya/Sūryasya duhitā/Sūre duhitā³⁴ (1.34.05; 1.117.13; 1.118.05; 3.53.15; 4.43.02; 6.63.5; 9.1.06; 9.113.3); sometimes also addressed as their companion (RV 1.116.17); implicitly, however, the Sun Maiden can also be considered their sister, for the Sun God, Sūrya, is mentioned as the son of Heaven (RV 10.37.1), though once. Thus, in fact, Sūryā is Heaven’s granddaughter. Likewise, the epithet of the Aśvins, *Divo napātā*, actually stands for ‘grandsons of Heaven’, which, in turn, implies close kinship with Sūryā.

Precisely the same parallel has been preserved in the Baltic mythology, where Sun Maiden — *Saules meita* in the Latvian tradition and *Saulės dūkterys* in the Lithuanian — is the bride of Sons of God.³⁵ There are several scenarios of the relationship between the celestial deities in the Latvian tradition. Hence, in another occasion the Sun Maiden is described straightforward as a bride of the Morning Star (*Auseklis*) (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 34009–0), elsewhere the Moon God abducts the bride (the Sun Maiden) of the Morning Star (*Ibid.*, 33950-0).

Similarly, in Greek mythology, the sister of *Dioskuoroi* is Helen (Ἑλένη, ἡς), whose name can be rendered as ‘torch’ or ‘St. Elmo’s fire’³⁶ (*Biblissima Toolkit*, n.d.). In some references she is attested as a the daughter of Helios i.e., the Sun God (Ward, 1968: 11). Already Euripides (*Or.* 1635–43, 1688; *Hel.* 1667–70) mentions the belief that Helen together with her twin brothers were celestial saviours of mariners, and that all three of them received libations and *xenia* (ritual hospitality). The local traditions of Attica, where *Castor* and *Polydeuces* were worshiped as the Anakes, Helen was believed to take birth at Rhamnous; she was abducted by Theseus and then rescued by the *Dioskuoroi*³⁷. The abduction of the young Helen was connected with *Aphrodite Nymphia* (Bridal Aphrodite), namely, marriage traditions (Larson, 2007: 191–192; 125).

³⁴ In *sūre* the archaic sandhi of final -as > -e before initial dental is preserved that is in fact not Dat., but Gen. *sūras (Jamison, 2010: 159–160; Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 139).

³⁵

<i>Celies agri, Saules meita,</i>	Get up early, Sun maiden,
<i>Mazgā baltu liepas galdu,</i>	Clean linden table white,
<i>Agri jāš Dieva dēli</i>	Sons of God will ride early
<i>Saules meitas lūkoties.</i>	To choose the Sun maiden (Author’s translation).

(*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 34032–3)

³⁶ According to Eulexis, etymology is Pre-Greek. The same phenomenon was alluded to *Dioskouroi*, too (Trzaskoma et al., 2004: 210). “Saint Elmo’s fire, luminosity accompanying brush like discharges of atmospheric electricity that sometimes appears as a faint light on the extremities of pointed objects such as church towers or the masts of ships during stormy weather, or along electric power lines. It is commonly accompanied by a crackling or hissing noise. [...] The name St. Elmo is an Italian corruption, through Sant’ Ermo, of St. Erasmus, the patron saint of Mediterranean sailors, who regarded St. Elmo’s fire as the visible sign of his guardianship over them. The phenomenon was considered to be a token of good luck because it is most pronounced near the end of a storm” (Britannica, 2020).

³⁷ For more details on the Greek myths see (Trzaskoma et al., 2004: 239).

3) Another idiosyncrasy pertinent to the triad of the solar mythologeme is incestuous and/or polyandrous relationships between them or their kinsmen. Thus, legend has it that Helen was a fruit of union between Zeus and his daughter Nemesis (Ibid., 179). Similar parallels can be discerned in RV, where Heaven (Dyaus) commits incestuous act towards his daughter Uṣas (Dawn) (RV 1.72.5,8; 1.164.8; 10.61.5–7); Pūṣan is a lover of his sister Sūryā (the Sun Maiden) (RV 6.55.4-5), the Sun God is incestuous towards Dawn (RV 1.115.2) who can be either his daughter or wife (RV 7.75.5), or explicitly his sister (RV 10.3.3).

The *Dioskuoroi* never had incestuous, and thus polyandrous relationship with Helen. However, in the case of the Aśvins and Sūryā there is clear evidence of polyandrous relationship (RV 8.29.8). Identical model is also observed in the Latvian folklore with sporadic exceptions, when there is indication of the Sun Maiden(s) that could be Du. or Pl. (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 34017–1; 33959–0 etc.).

4) The twin brothers as a rule rescue their sister/beloved one. Thus, Euripides describes how the *Dioskuoroi* carry off Helen in a horse-driven chariot.

[1495] May you come at last, speeding over your horses' path through the sky, sons of Tyndareus, under the whirling of the radiant stars; you who dwell in heaven, Helen's rescuers [...] (Coleridge, 1938).

Similarly, Sūryā mounts the chariot of the Aśvins and traverses the sky together with them (RV 1.117.13; 1.118.5; 7.73.5 etc.); occasionally they can arrive from the sea (RV 1.47.6) or in boats (RV 1.116.3), they can also make a boat to rescue Bhujyu (RV 1.180.5), or indirectly depict a river-dolphin (*Delphinus Gangeticus*; or else: crocodile) as their yoking animal (RV 1.116.18). Whereas, in the Latvian tradition the Sons of God rescue the Sun Maiden by sailing her in a boat (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 33969–0). It is evident that the mode of transportation i.e., boat or chariot is a local adjustment of the same phenomenon.

Their cosmic wedding served as a wedding prototype in profane rituals of the ancient Greece.

Hence, according to Larson it

[p]rovided a model for Spartan matrimony through their capture of the daughters of the Messenian king *Leukippos* (White Horse). These maidens, *Hilaeira* (Softly Shining) and *Phoibe* (Radiant), are ideal female counterparts of the brilliant twins. Spartan marriage customs included a ritual kidnapping that must have evoked this myth, an Archaic favorite often illustrated in Lakonian contexts (Larson, 2007: 190).

In the Latvian folksongs, both cosmic and human wedding models are intertwined similarly as it is in the wedding hymn 10.85 of RV, which will be elaborated in the next sub-chapter.

5) Another striking parallel that can be drawn between Greek and Vedic patterns is that both Uṣas and Helen are depicted as brides having a self-choice husband.

As for Helen, she was wooed by a great host of suitors from different cities because of her outstanding beauty. Tyndareus was afraid that Agamemnon would reject his daughter Clytaemnestra and feared that the whole thing would end in chaos, so he took Ulysses' advice and swore an oath, putting the decision in the hands of Helen herself, who was to place a crown on the head of the man she wanted to marry (Trzaskoma et al., 2004: 239).

Stephanie Jamison's comparative study on *svayamvara* or self-choice marriage within Indo-European milieu demonstrates that the very name of Helena was spelled with a digamma i.e., *Ἑλένης* in a Lakonian inscription dated ca. 7th century CE. Based on this etymology, Jamison concludes it might have been derived from IE root **uelh₁* just as Skt. *vr̥ṇītè*, which means — 'the chooser'. Concomitantly, she admits that the Greek verb *ἐλέσθαι*³⁸ 'take to oneself; choose' is not etymologically cognate to Skt. *vr̥ṇītè* (Jamison, 2001: 313–314).

6) Another phenomenon necessary to elucidate on this is the abduction of the Sun Maiden that has found its way to become a deep-rooted rite of a bride abduction among many Indo-European cultures. For instance, Müller cites McLennan's work (1865) "On Primitive Marriage," where the following phrases are typically used in the sense of ancient marriage customs: the Old Norse word *quân-fang* 'wife-catching', and the German *brût-loufti* 'bride-racing' (Müller, 1868: 264–265). Mythological kidnapping of Helen in the Greek tradition has already been discussed. Although, it is not attested in RV, Herodotus (ca. 480-ca. 420 BCE) provides a following account from the Persians, who were certainly in close contact with the peoples of ancient India.

[1.4] The abduction of women is, of course, quite wrong, but only fools make a great fuss about it, while wise men pay little heed; for it's obvious that women would not be carried off unless they themselves were willing. The Persians say that the peoples of Asia paid little regard to the seizure of their women, whereas the Greeks, merely for the sake of a Spartan woman, gathered a great army, invaded Asia, and destroyed the kingdom of Priam. Thereafter they have always regarded Greece as an enemy, for the Persians consider Asia, and the peoples dwelling there, as their concern, while Europe and the Greeks are something apart (Trzaskoma et al., 2004: 124).

Consensual and unconsensual bride kidnapping was a wide-spread tradition among the ancient Baltic tribes, numerous records of which can be found in the Latvian folklore materials (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 24309–0; 29509–0; 13384–0 etc.). This tradition has been preserved up to present day in the form of a ritually reenacted bride kidnapping during the traditional weddings in order to get ransom.

7) Despite of *communis opinio* to consider the divine twin pattern as a triad, in reality, in particular speaking of the Vedic *Aśvins*, it would be more accurate to call them a quartet for the reason that alongside the Sun Maiden (*Sūryā*) who is explicitly the bride of the *Aśvins*, Dawn (*Uṣas*) also plays a significant role as their sister and companion. In RV, except for a few instances, the *Aśvins*

³⁸ It is Imperative 3rd Pl. from *αιπέω* (*Biblissima Toolkit*, n.d.).

are usually mentioned either with Sūryā or with Uṣas, but in the ancillary Brāhmaṇas — AitBr and KB, except for *Prātaranuvāka* (Morning Prayer), where the Aśvins are propitiated alongside Uṣas and Agni (Fire God), AŚ begins with the mythological legend that narrates the wedding of Sūryā. Whereas, the central actors of a ritual scene that follows the legend are: Indra, Agni, the Aśvins, and Uṣas. Hence, in AŚ the main actors of the *Dioskuric* pattern are four: Sūryā, the two Aśvins and Uṣas. Their interrelations will be elaborated at length further on.

In contrast, the Greek and Baltic mythological legends do have a female deity Dawn, however, they have their own mythological dominion of legends, which hardly ever intersect with the Sun Maiden. Thus, the Greek Dawn is Eos (Ἠώς), whose counterpart in Roman tradition is *Aurōra*. Eos is described in a number of legends, and is also frequently mentioned in such classical Greek epics as *Iliad* (Homer, 1924: Hom. Il. 11.1); however, in *Odysseus* Eos is mentioned a few times alongside Helen (Homer, 2004: IV:155-219; 290-350), Eos alone is frequently lauded in Homeric Hymns ca. 7-6th centuries BCE (*The Homeric Hymns*, 2020, v. V: 217, 221, 224, XXXI: 8) etc.; likewise, in Hesiod's *Theogony* ca. 8th century BCE (Hesiod, 2021: 20, 421, 427, 430, 1090) etc. Ancient Greek mythology trichotomized the temporal functions of a daybreak into three respective deities: Eos and her two sons: *Eōsphoros* (Ἐωσφόρος) — the god of the Morning Star (the planet Venus) heralding the dawn (Roman name — Luciferus, Lucifer) and *Hesperos* (Ἑσπερος) — the god of the Evening Star (Roman name — Vesperus, Vesper; her siblings were a brother *Helios* (Ἥλιος) — the Sun God and sister *Selene* (Σελήνη) — the Moon Goddess. Nevertheless, little is known of the cults dedicated to Eos.

Etymologically Eos goes back to Proto-Greek **áwhós* of IE **h₂eus-ós* (*Biblissima Toolkit*, n.d.); cf. **Hausōs-Ø* in (Gamkrelidze et al., 1994: 159) and to PIE **aus-*, **us-* in (Ibid., 193); cf. *-aug* in (Pokorny, 2007: 200). Cf. Lat. *aurōr-a*, Skt. *uśás-*; Avestan *ušā*; v. *αὔριον*; Lith. *aūšti* ‘to dawn’ (full grade), *Aušra* ‘Dawn’, *Aušrinė* f. ‘Morning Star’; Latv. *aust* ‘to dawn’, *Austra* ‘Dawn’, *Auseklis* ‘Morning Star’, Hittite *auš-*, *uš-* ‘see’.

Similarly, in the Latvian mythological folksongs, among the most prominent deities is the Sun Maiden who is lauded separately in 135 folksongs. Whereas, *Austriņa* that is diminutive of *Austra* is mentioned only four times. Her mythological role eventually was overtaken by a male deity *Auseklis* (two occasions), or its diminutive forms *Auseklītis* (22 occasions), and *Ausekliņš* (four occasions) (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.).

To sum it up, it can be concluded that despite of *communis opinio* to consider the *Dioskuric* pattern to consist of a triad — the divine twins and the Sun Maiden, the Vedic pattern rather demonstrates

a quartet: the divine twins Aśvins, the Sun Maiden and Dawn. Of the similarities one can point the presence of incestuous and/or polyandrous relationship that are attested in all three traditions. Bride kidnapping is explicit in the Greek and Baltic traditions with only indirect sources giving reports on practicing it in ancient India.

2.2. Solar mythologeme — as described in Ṛgveda

As it has already been mentioned in the introduction, there are 52 hymns in RV dedicated to the Aśvins by various Rigvedic sages or divine poets. Out of them 18 hymns involve the solar mythologeme, where Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, mounts the chariot of the Aśvins thus demonstrating her self-choice (*svayamvara*)³⁹ by selecting them as her husbands; she is carried away as a bride; or else is explicitly named as their newly-wed wife or bride, the mistress etc. Already in the poetical milieu of RV, emerges a rather distinct dichotomy of a sacrificial ground with a typical entourage of deities and arena of purely cosmological or astronomical events that employ another set of deities. Thus, *purely* cosmological are poetical narratives of the divine wedding between Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, to the divine twins — Aśvins, or later on Soma, the Moon God in RV 10.85. In contrast, Uṣas, when lauded together with Agni and the Aśvins, most often is invoked to the sacrificial ground to bestow wealth, children, protection, and long life to the sacrificer. Nonetheless, there are a few exceptions, when the divine participants of both realms intersect within the boundaries of one hymn, however, even then their areas of responsibility are dichotomized rather distinctly. There are two instances when the composition of the divine set on ritual arena is atypical and extended (RV 8.9.16-18; 8.35). Another remarkable feature that distinguishes the social and kinship roles of Uṣas from Sūryā, is the self-choice that is expressed by mounting the chariot of husbands to be. Although, Uṣas has been depicted as the maiden who goes to *svayamvara* (RV 1.124.8; 1.121.2cd), she never mounts the chariot of the Aśvins. Furthermore, in spite of the fact that the poets address both of them with the Sanskrit word *sakhī* a female ‘companion’ or *sakhyā* ‘companionship’, which can be referred either to a wife, sister, or a friend, however, it is only Sūryā who mounts the chariot of the Aśvins as the bride.

Now, I will enlist all the passages mentioning the solar mythologem and its cosmic and sacrificial protagonists in RV starting from I to X Maṇḍala.

³⁹ See more on *svayamvara* in (Jamison, 2001: 313–314, 2003; Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 276–277).

2.2.1 Aśvins — the bridegrooms of Sun Maiden

I Maṇḍala

1) Stanza five of RV 1.34 by *Hiraṇyastūpa Āṅgīrasa* describes the Sun Maiden to have mounted the chariot of the Aśvins, thus manifesting her self-choice to accept them as her husbands.

**c.d. triḥ saubhagaṭvaṃ trir ūta śravāmsi nas triṣṭhaṃ vāṃ sūrē duhitā rūhaḍ rathāṃ ||
1.34.5¹⁴**

2) Stanza 17 of RV 1.116 by *Kakṣīvant Dairghatamasa* describes the Sun Maiden to have mounted the chariot of the Aśvins, and also gives an allusion to the race described in AŚ of AitBr, the act of which is also approved by all the gods.

**ā vāṃ rathāṃ duhitā sūryāsya kārṣmévātiṣṭhaḍ arvātā jayāntī |
viśvé devā anv āmanyanta hṛdbhiḥ sam ū śriyā nāsatyā sacethe ||1.116.17¹⁵**

3) Stanza 13 of RV 1.117 by *Kakṣīvant Dairghatamasa* describes the Sun Maiden choosing the chariot of the Aśvins.

c.d. yuvo rathāṃ duhitā sūryāsya saha śriyā nāsatyāvṛṇīta || 1.117.13¹⁶

4) Stanza five of RV 1.118 by *Kakṣīvant Dairghatamasa* describes the Sun Maiden mounting the chariot of the Aśvins.

a.b. ā vāṃ rathāṃ yuvaṭis tiṣṭhaḍ atrā juṣṭvī nārā duhitā sūryāsya | 1.118.5¹⁷

5) Stanza two of RV 1.119 by *Kakṣīvant Dairghatamasa* describes the Sun Maiden to have mounted the chariot of the Aśvins.

c.d. svadāmi ghaṛmam prati yanty ūtaya ā vāṃ ūrjānī rathāṃ aśvināruhat || 1.119.2¹⁸

6) Stanza three of RV 1.119 describes the Sun Maiden being carried by the Aśvins. Cf. Geldner (1951) and Elizarenkova (1999) who render *sūrim* as ‘mistress’; cf. Grassmann (1876) who takes it as ‘goods’.

**saṃ yan mithaḥ pāsprdhānāso agmāta śubhe maḥhā amitā jāyavo raṇé |
yuvor ahā pravaṇe cēkite ratho yad aśvinā vahāthaḥ sūrim ā varāṃ || 1.119.3¹⁹**

7) Stanza five of RV 1.119 describes the Sun Maiden having a self-choice marriage with the Aśvins.

**yuvor aśvinā vapuṣe yuvāyujāṃ rathāṃ vāṇī yematur asya śardhyāṃ |
ā vāṃ patitvaṃ sakhyāyā jagmuṣī yoṣāvṛṇīta jenyā yuvāṃ patī || 1.119.5²⁰**

8) Stanza three of RV 1.184 by *Agastya Maitrāvaruṇi* lauds the wedding procession of the Sun Maiden, where the Aśvins could be either her wooers or bridegrooms.

śriye pūṣann iṣukṛtēva devā nāsātyā vahaṭum sūryāyāḥ |
vaçyantē vām kakuhā apsu jātā yugā jūrṇeva varuṇasya bhūrēḥ || 1.184.3²¹

IV Maṇḍala

9) Stanza two of RV 4.43 by *Purumīḥa Sauhotra* and *Ajamīḥa Sauhotra* mentions the self-choice of Sūryā; whereas, in stanza six, the poets laud the wedding of Sūryā to the Aśvins using the verb in present tense, which is in sharp contrast to the previous ones that refer to the mythical past.

c.d. ratham kam āhur dravadāsvam āsum yaṁ sūryāsya duhitāvṛṇīta || 4.43.2²²
c.d. tad ū ṣu vām ajiram ceti yānam yena patī bhavāthaḥ sūryāyāḥ || 4.43.6²³

10) Stanza one of RV 4.44 by the previous authors again praises Sūryā as the bride or wife of the Aśvins in present tense.

c.d. yaḥ sūryām vahāti vandhurāyur girvāhasam purutamam vasūyum || 4.44.1²⁴

11) Stanza one of RV 4.45 by *Vāmadeva Gautama* concludes the solar wedding theme commenced in 4.43 by intricately referring to the married trio — the Aśvins and Sūryā — as a Sanskrit word *mithunā* is oftentimes used to designate a pair of a man and a woman as well as the act of copulation. Cf. Grassmann who takes them as horses (Grassmann, 1876: 152). Another idiosyncrasy of this hymn is that Uṣas, although implicitly, is mentioned alongside, with Sūryā.

c.d. pṛkṣāsó asmin mithunā adhi trayo dṛtis turīyo madhuno vi rapāte || 4.45.1²⁵

V Maṇḍala

12) Stanza five of RV 5.73 by *Paura Ātreya* again praising Sūryā mounting the chariot of the Aśvins. Quite remarkably the poet has used Present Injunctive⁴⁰ for the verb *sthā*, which in its unaugmented form, especially unaugmented aorists, implies something between the subjunctive ‘requisition’ and of the optative ‘wish’ (Macdonell, 1910: 316). Hence, implicitly ‘let her mount’ or ‘she should mount’, which is quite impossible to render in English given the adverbial pronoun ‘when’. Another idiosyncrasy spotted in this hymn is unordinary number of wheels of the Aśvins chariot i.e., two mentioned in stanza three, one of which Jamison & Brereton render as the sacrificial fire, another as the sun. Cf. Geldner (1951), Elizarenkova (1999), Grassmann (1876).

ā yad vām sūryā ratham tiṣṭhād raghuṣyadam sadā |
pari vām aruṣā vayó ghrṇā vāranta ātapāḥ || 5.73.5²⁶

⁴⁰ See the rendition of RV 5.73.8 in Karl Hoffmann (Hoffmann, 1967: 129), where he renders it as “so that you may [...]”.

VI Maṇḍala

13) Stanza five of RV 6.63 by *Bharadvāja Bārhaspatya* again lauds the self-choice marriage of Sūryā, who mounts the Aśvins chariot.

a.b. adhi śriye duhitā sūryāsyā ratham tasthau purubhujā śatotim | 6.63.5²⁷

VII Maṇḍala

14) Stanza three of RV 7.68 by *Vasiṣṭha Maitrāvaruṇi* explicitly narrates Sūryā to be either their possession; cf. Geldner (1951); Elizarenkova (1999), or wife according to (Grassmann, 1876: 355).

**pra vām ratho manōjavā iyarti tiro rajāmsy aśvinā śatotiḥ |
asmabhyam sūryāvasū iyānaḥ || 7.68.3²⁸**

15) Stanzas three and four of RV 7.69 by *Vasiṣṭha Maitrāvaruṇi* narrates the journey of the Aśvins with their newly wedded wife — Sūryā, where the phrase “made her choice” in the decisive moment in great probability describes a particular astronomical phenomenon.

c.d. vi vām ratho vadhvāḥ yādāmāno 'ntān divo bād hate vartanibhyām || 7.69.3²⁹

a.b. yuvoh śriyam pari yoṣāvṛṇīta sūro duhitā paritakmyāyam | 7.69.4³⁰

VIII Maṇḍala

16) Stanza 10 of RV 8.8 by *Sadhvaṃsa Kāṇva* (or *Vatsa* as he is referred throughout the hymn) briefly alludes to Sūryā who mounted the chariot of the Aśvins.

a.b. ā yad vām yoṣāṇā ratham atiṣṭhad vājinīvasū | 8.8.10³¹

17) Stanza one of RV 8.22 by *Sobhari Kāṇva* narrates slightly twisted wedding motif, where the Aśvins mount the chariot perhaps to journey after their bride — Sūryā. Stanza three again tells of two wheels, one of which speeds around, and another, although at rest, drives forward; and only in stanza four a typical number three is designated to the three-boxes of their chariot.

**o tyam ahva ā ratham adyā daṃsiṣṭham ūtayē |
yam aśvinā suhavā rudravartanī ā sūryāyai tasthathuḥ || 8.22.1³²**

X Maṇḍala

18) Stanzas 11-12 of RV 10.39 by *Ghoṣā Kākṣivati* — one of the few female poets ascribed by Anukramaṇī, who evidently belongs to the kin of the skilled poet *Kakṣivant Dairghatamasa*, lauds the journey of the wedded couple; and stanza 12 an ordinary trio of the morning sacrifice: Uṣas and the Aśvins. Stanza 14 resonates with the wedding or sexual union motif narrated in 7.69.3. In fact, all the three hymns 10.39-41 ascribed to her and her son indulge into the wedding theme and thus already prepares the audience for the domestic wedding ritual unfolded in RV 10.85.

c.d. yam aśvinā suhavā rudravartanī puroratham kṛṇuthaḥ patnyā saha || 10.39.11³³

ā tenā yātam manāso javīyasā ratham yam vām ṛbhavās cakrur aśvinā |

yasya yogé duhitā jāyāte dīva ubhe ahānī sudiné vīvasvātaḥ || 10.39.12³⁴

c.d. ny āmrkṣāma yoṣāṇām na marye nityam na sūnum tanāyam dadhānāḥ || 10.39.14³⁵

Other passages clearly or opaquely related to the solar mythologeme or sacrificial ground of the morning rituals that are mentioned in the hymns dedicated to the other deities:

The Aśvins in the role of husbands:

1) Stanza four of RV 2.31 by *Gṛtsamada* dedicated to All Gods, indirectly alludes to the triad of the solar mythologeme, where the Aśvins are mentioned as husbands — either of the Sun Maiden (implicitly) or Dawn as she is mentioned in the next stanza.

**Ūta sya devo bhuvānasya sakṣaṇis tvaṣṭā gnābhiḥ sajoṣā jūjuvaḍ rathām |
iḷā bhagó bṛhaddivota rodāsī pūṣā purāndhir aśvināv adhā patī || 2.31.4³⁶**

2) Stanza two of RV 2.39 by *Gṛtsamada* dedicated to the Aśvins has incorporated a mundane motif of a wedded couple, although not directly referable to the solar mythologeme. Cf. Elizarenkova (1999) who renders as two masters of the house.

**Prātaryāvāṇā rathyéva vīrājevā yamā varam ā śacethe |
mené iva tanvāṣṭṣumbhāmāne dampātīva kratuvidā janēṣu || 2.39.2³⁷**

3) Stanza eight of RV 8.29 by *Manu Vaivasvata* or *Kaśyapa Mārīca* dedicated to All Gods lauds the married trio — the Aśvins with Sūryā in a riddled form.

Vibhir dvā cārataḥ ekāyā saha pra pravāsevā vasataḥ || 8.29.8³⁸

2.2.2 Aśvins — brothers and companions of Dawn

I Maṇḍala

1) Stanza two of RV 1.180 by *Agastya Maitrāvaruṇi* refers Dawn as their sister.

c.d. svasā yad vām viśvagūrti bharāti vājāyette madhupāv iṣe ca || 1.180.2³⁹

2) Stanza two of RV 1.182 by *Agastya Maitrāvaruṇi* on the surface implies a mere companionship, however, it is an infrequent trope employed by the poets of RV to implicitly treat Dawn as the wife of the Aśvins.

**suṽrd rathó vartate yann abhi kṣām yat tiṣṭhāthāḥ kratumāntānū pṛkṣe |
vapūr vapuṣyā śacātām iyam gīr dīvo dūhitroṣasā sacethe || 1.183.2⁴⁰**

III Maṇḍala

3) Stanza one of RV 3.58 by *Viśvāmitra Gāthin* lauds a ritual quartet of the solar mythologeme: Uṣas, Agni and the two Aśvins. However, Grassmann renders the milk-cow as a female kindling stick out which Agni (fire) is born (Grassmann, 1876: 101).

**dhenuḥ praṅnasya kāmyam duhānāntaḥ putras carati dakṣiṇāyāḥ |
ā dyōtanim vāhati śubhrayāmoṣasaḥ stomō aśvināv ajīgaḥ || 3.58.1⁴¹**

4) Stanza one of RV 5.76 by *Atri Bhauma* praises a usual trio present at a sacrificial ground: Agni, Uṣas, and the two Aśvins. Similarly, it is in RV 5.77.2 cd, just except for Agni

a.b. ā bhāty agnir uṣasām anīkam ud viprāṇām devayā vācō asthuḥ | 5.76.1⁴²

VIII Maṇḍala

5) Stanzas 16-18 of RV 8.9 by *Śaśakarṇa Kāṇva* invoke atypical group of deities: the Aśvins, Uṣas, and Agni, alongside with Sūrya.

a.b. abhūtsy u pra devyā sākam vācāham aśvinoh | 8.9.16⁴³

pra bōdhayoṣo aśvinā pra devī sūrte mahi |

pra yājñathe Hotar ānuṣak pra madāya śravō bṛhat || 8.9.17⁴⁴

a.b. yad uṣo yāsi bhānunā sam sūryeṇa rocasa | 8.9.18⁴⁵

6) Stanza one of RV 8.35.1 by *Śyāvāśva Ātreya* invoke extended pantheon of deities to the sacrificial ground: Agni, Indra, Varuṇa, Viṣṇu, the Ādityas, the Rudras, the Vasus, Uṣas, Sūrya, and the Aśvins; as well as Waters, the Maruts, and the Bhṛgus in stanza three. Stanzas two to 21 laud atypical quartet of the morning sacrifice as a refrain in padas cd: Uṣas, Sūrya, and the Aśvins

agninendreṇa varuṇeṇa viṣṇunādītyai rudrair vasubhiḥ sacābhuvā |

sajoṣāsā uṣasā sūryeṇa ca somam pibatam aśvinā || 8.35.1⁴⁶

Another passage beyond the scope of the hymns dedicated to the Aśvins.

7) Stanzas two to three of RV 4.52 by *Vāmadeva Gautama* dedicated to Uṣas laud her as a companion of the Aśvins, and in stanza one the poet addresses her as either their sister, or wife; cf. Elizarenkova.

c.d. sakhābhūd aśvinōr uṣāḥ || 4.52.2⁴⁷

a.b. uta sakhāsya aśvinōr uta mātā gavām asi | 4.52.3⁴⁸

8) Stanzas seven to eight of RV 124 by *Kakṣivant Dairghatamasa* dedicated to Uṣas describe her acting as a brotherless girl who wishes to get married. According to Jamison & Brereton the sociological behaviour depicted in this hymn, is similar to — *svayaṃvara* — an assembly of groom

candidates, where the maiden puts herself at display in order to select a future husband, a domestic rite, which was later on practiced among royals (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 277–278).

Other passages clearly or opaquely related to the solar mythologeme or sacrificial ground of the morning rituals that are mentioned in the hymns dedicated to the other deities.

Atypical sets of deities invoked during morning rituals:

1) Stanza one of RV 4.13 by *Vāmadeva Gautama* lauds another type of quartet of the ritual scene: Agni, Dawn(s), the Aśvins, and Sūrya. Similarly, the poet does in 4.14.1. Moreover, these two hymns are the rare exception when Sūrya and Savitar are both lauded together.

**praty agnir uṣasām agrām akhyad vibhātīnām sumanā ratnadhayām |
yātam aśvinā sukṛto duroṇam ut sūryo jyotiṣā deva eti || 4.13.1⁴⁹**

2) Stanza eight of RV 5.51 by *Svastyātreya Ātreya* dedicated to All Gods lauds a typical trio of the morning sacrificial ground: the Aśvins, Uṣas, and Agni.

**sajūr viśvebhīr devebhīr aśvibhyām uṣasā sajuh |
ā yāhy agne atrivat sute raṇa || 5.51.8⁵⁰**

3) Stanza one of RV 7.44 by *Vasiṣṭha Maitrāvaruṇi* dedicated to *Dadhikrā* alongside the other deities, invokes a usual morning trio: the Aśvins, Uṣas, and Agni.

**a.b. dadhikrām vaḥ prathamam aśvinoṣasām agniṁ samiddham bhagām utayē huve |
7.44.1⁵¹**

4) Stanzas four to 11 of RV 4.30 by *Vāmadeva Gautama* dedicated to Indra reveal an original evolution of the solar mythologeme that has apparently been localized to depict a rare astronomical event that occurred during the battle with the indigenous people of the Indian subcontinent. Grassmann suggests it could be a thunderstorm (Grassmann, 1876: 136). Moreover, here one can also observe how Indra overtakes the earlier deities from their prominence. In essence, Indra who is elsewhere regarded as the Sun God, here steals the wheel of Sūrya in 4.30.4, and also smites Uṣas and her bridal cart in 4.30.8-9; similar motifs are lauded in 5.29.10; 5.31.11. The Sanskrit word *ānas* in RV is usually employed to describe a cart that brings a bride home (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 291). The main actors of this solar mythologeme are: Indra who destroys the wedding of Sūrya with Uṣas.

c.d. muṣāya indra sūryām || 4.30.4⁵²

a.b. yatrota martyāya kam ariṇā indra sūryām | 4.30.6⁵³

c.d. striyaṁ yad dūrhaṇāyuvam vadhīr duhitaram dīvaḥ || 4.30.8⁵⁴

dīvaś cid ghā duhitaram mahān mahīyamānām |

uṣāsám indra sam piṅak || 4.30.9⁵⁵
 apoṣā anāsaḥ sarat sampiṣṭād ahā bibhyuṣī |
 ni yat sīm śiśnathad vṛṣā || 4.30.10⁵⁶
 etad āsyā anāḥ śaye susāmpīṣṭam vipāśy ā |
 sasāra sīm parāvataḥ || 4.30.11⁵⁷

Allusions to the mythological legend that depicts the race of deities, which is of purely Indian origin and was elucidated later in AitBr:

- 1) c.d. kadā yogó vājino rāsabhasya yenā yajñam nāsatyopayāthaḥ || 1.34.9⁵⁸
- 2) c.d. harī te yuñjā pṛṣatī abhūtām upāsthād vājī dhuri rāsabhasya || 1.162.21⁵⁹
- 3) c.d. sahasram śamsā uta ye gaviṣṭau sarvām it tām upā yātā pibādhyai || 8.57.3⁶⁰
- 4) Stanzas 14-15 of RV 8.73 by *Gopavana Ātreya* or *Saptavadhri Ātreya* also allude to a bridal gift, narrated in the AŚ of AitBr.

a.b. ā no gavyēbhīr āsvyaiḥ sahasrair upā gacchatam | 8.73.14⁶¹

a.b. mā no gavyēbhīr āsvyaiḥ sahasrēbhīr ati khyatam | 8.73.15⁶²

- 5) Stanza seven of RV 8.85 by *Kṛṣṇa Āngirasa* also alludes to the racing for a bridal gift narrated in the AŚ of AitBr.

a.b. yuñjāthām rāsabham rathē vīdvāṅge vṛṣaṅvasū | 8.85.7⁶³

- 7) Stanzas three and four of RV 10.73 by *Gaurivīti Śaktyā* dedicated to Indra allude to the bridal gift and abundance, likewise hinting to fertility narrated in the AŚ of AitBr; whereas, stanzas six and nine recall the smashing of Dawn's cart and stealing of the Sun's wheel already praised in 4.30.4;6;8-9 and 5.29.10; 5.31.11.

a.b. sanāmānā cid dhvasayo ny āsmā avāhann indra uṣaso yathānāḥ | 10.73.6⁶⁴

a.b. cakram yad āsyāpsv ā niṣattam uto tad āsmai madhv ic cacchadyāt | 10.73.9⁶⁵

2.2.3 Aśvins — the wooers of Soma (the Moon God)

The entire hymn of RV 10.85 with 47 stanzas by a fanciful poet *Sūryā Sāvitrī* is dedicated to both cosmic wedding and a domestic wedding rite. A later text — the Atharvaveda (Śaunaka's recension) likewise contains wedding hymns (14.1–2). These wedding rites are further elaborated and explicated in the corresponding *Grhya* sūtras of RV: *Āśvalāyana (Adhyāya I, Khāṇḍa 4-9)* and *Śāṅkhāyana (Adhyāya I, Khāṇḍa 5-19)*.

This hymn is a culmination and quintessence of previously discussed poetic narratives on the wedding theme by virtue of the eloquence of the poets from the Kakṣivants' clan, namely, *Kakṣivant Dairghatamasa* and *Ghoṣā Kākṣivatī*. Their oeuvre is particularly productive pertinent

to describing the female roles and behaviour in both cosmic and domestic wedding rites. Particularly remarkable are the hymns RV 10.39 and 10.40 by *Ghoṣā Kākṣīvatī*, where the poetess gives a glimpse into a social life of a woman having no relatives who implores the Aśvins to bestow her a husband (10.39.6), thus fusing the cosmic and domestic realms into one. The hymns 10.39-40 have become a matter of scholarly contestation; thus, Jamison holds it that the scenes depicted in stanzas 5-11 give a description of *svayaṃvara*, which had already been discussed earlier, and also unmistakably vivid imagery of marriage consummation (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 1441–1442). In contrast, Brereton’s stance is that both hymns 10.39-40 are constituent of the concluding part of the overnight Soma ritual Atirātra, namely, AŚ, where the Aśvins are invoked to receive the final portion of Soma.

One of the themes of the Third Pressing in the classical soma rites is the fertility of the sacrificing couple. Since this is a relatively late hymn, the Wife of the Sacrificer may already have been a participant in the rite for which these hymns were composed. Therefore, the hymns might have been an appeal to the Aśvins to help make the marriage of the sacrificing couple a success by giving them a son. (Ibid., 1443).

I am personally more inclined towards Jamison’s view; however, it may not be improbable that the fusion of both views might find their place, and thus laid a foundation for the famous wedding hymn 10.85, which I will discuss now within the scope of this research topic, namely the agency of the divine twins — Aśvins that is shifted within the frame of this hymn. Based on the quotes from the so-called family books and the oldest layer of Maṇḍala 1, it is evident that the Aśvins were addressed as either the bridegrooms or husbands of Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, in the oldest layer of RV, except for RV 1.34.5 and 10.39-41. Thus, there is almost a unanimous view among scholars to consider the hymns of book 1.51–191 and family books 2-8 as the oldest layer of RV, which demonstrate poetic virtuosity and rather homogeneous structure. Whereas, the hymns of the books 1.1–50 and book 10 to be later additions (Brereton and Jamison, 2020b: 27–29; Grassmann, 1876: v; Witzel, 2003: 69). Cf. Geldner and Grassmann who even offer a more detailed breakdown of the books (Geldner, 1951: xiv–xix; Grassmann, 1877: 1).

Remarkably, however, that unlike all the previous instances, where the Aśvins were lauded as bridegrooms or husbands of Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, in RV 10.85, all of a sudden, the Aśvins are down shifted to the role of wooers to Sūryā during her betrothal. Moreover, Soma has now not only overtaken the role of the bridegroom, but also entered a domain of celestial deities by becoming the Moon God.

Now, let me briefly discuss the contents and division of this hymn, which is multifaceted and multi-layered text that contains mythological, cosmological, astronomical and domestic dimensions pertinent to the wedding rituals.

Thus, stanzas 1-5 induct Soma, who was previously known as an inebriating beverage made from the plant with the same name and eponymous deity representing this plant/beverage, to the new role — he is now celebrated as — the Moon God. Alongside, the audience is prepared to witness the solemn wedding vows, as the age-old triad of Ādityas⁴¹ — Mitra, Varuṇa and Aryaman — enter the cosmic arena as protectors of truth (RV 2.27.8), and thus, implicitly the protectors of the marriage contract. Their presence is revealed in 17ab, with other Ādityas emerging, too, in 9c, 13bcd, 23cd, 24ab, 36cd, 43b.

satyenottābhītā bhūmīḥ sūryeṇottābhītā dyauḥ |
ṛtenādītyās tiṣṭhanti dīvi somo adhi śrītaḥ || 10.85.1⁶⁶

Concomitantly, in stanza 5, the poet announces that the time is counted following the moon waxing and waning phases, which emphasizes the prominence of the newly acquired status of Soma. Although, lunar mythology predates the solar one, and was known to pre-agricultural societies to recreate time via its cyclical rhythm of waxing and waning moon, in its later development, the moon phases are observed by agricultural societies, to plan the sowing or harvesting times accordingly (Eliade, 1961: 71–73). This can also be deduced from the description of Sūryā's chariot that is made of two ears in 11c. Thus, perhaps the new role of Soma, the Moon, marks a new era of a semi sedentary life-style of the Vedic peoples who were gradually assimilating with the indigenous peoples of the Indian subcontinent at the end of the Bronze Age.

yat tvā deva prapibānti tata ā pyāyase punaḥ |
vāyuḥ somāsyā rakṣitā samānām māsa ākṛtiḥ || 10.85.5⁶⁷

Stanzas 6-19 are majorly concerned with the actors of the cosmic wedding, and yet, 6-8 give a glimpse into the adornments and a vehicle of the bride — the human counterpart in the profane arena. Stanzas 8-9 and 14-15 clearly declare the novel role and status of the Aśvins, thus their agency is evidently downgraded from the previous role of the bridegrooms to the wooers to Sūryā. Moreover, the entire cohort of deities — the actors of solar mythologeme — has been replaced,

⁴¹ Initially there are two Ādityas: Mitra, Varuṇa (RV 5.69.4), then three: Mitra, Varuṇa and Aryaman (7.51.2; 7.60.4-6; 10.185.1-3); five: Savitar, Bhaga, Varuṇa, Mitra and Aryaman in (8.18.3); six: Varuṇa, Mitra, Bahaga, Dakṣa, Aṃśa, and Aryaman in (2.27.1); the later added parts of RV, Āditi has seven sons according to RV 10.72.8-9; also in 9.114.3); later texts mention even 24, which is clearly an artificially added number to fit the pattern eight Vasus, 11 Rudras and 24 Ādityas. For more see (Hillebrandt, 1902: 97–102; Oldenberg, 1988b: 95; 160). Cf. Hillebrandt, Hardy and Oldenberg who attempted to identify Varuṇa with Moon God or different manifestations of sun in the course of the day or year ((Müller, 1897: 554; 545–556)

except for Sūryā. And, thus, the new solar mythologeme has emerged, where now two protagonists — Sūryā and Soma, and three backstage actors — Savitar, the impelling aspect of Sūrya, the Sun God, who took the role of the bride’s father, the flames of Agni leading up or across the sky, and the Aśvins as the wooers are present.

stomā āsan pratīdhayāḥ kurīraṁ chandā opaśaḥ |

sūryāyā aśvinā varāgnir āsīt purogavaḥ || 10.85.8⁶⁸

somó vadhūyur ābhavad aśvināstām ubhā varā |

sūryām yat patye śamsantīm manāsā savitādādāt || 10.85.9⁶⁹

Yet another event marks the status change of the Aśvins — they become step-fathers of Pūṣan, at his will. Besides this hymn, nothing is known of Pūṣan’s mother, nor the discernible circumstances that have induced such a radical shift in familial relationships of the divine pantheon of celestial deities.

yad aśvinā pṛcchamānāv ayātaṁ tricakraṇā vahaṭum sūryāyāḥ |

viśve devā anu tad vām ajānan putraḥ pitarāv avṛṇīta pūṣā || 10.85.14⁷⁰

Stanza 15 informs the audience on the fact that during wooing the chariot of the Aśvins has lost its one wheel, thus clearly indicating to significant astronomical events, namely the changed kaleidoscope of the early morning sky visible to the poet at some point in past, which is now lauded in this hymn.

yad ayātaṁ śubhas patī vareyaṁ sūryām upā |

kvaikāṁ cakraṁ vām āsīt kvā deṣṭrāyā tastathuḥ || 10.85.15⁷¹

Noteworthy to mention that Müller, for instance, did not distinguish between Sūryā and Uṣas as he considered them to be the animated representations of one and the same nature phenomenon — Dawn personified (Müller, 1897: 573).

To conclude subchapter 2.2, the celestial deities Aśvins were most likely the representations of the planet Venus. In the oldest layers of mythopoetics of RV they were depicted as the central actors in the solar mythologeme. Namely, they were the bridegrooms of Sūryā. Whereas, in RV 10.85 they are downshifted by the Moon God, Soma, who has just ascended to this new position. In fact, the entire hymn consisting of 47 stanzas is a mythopoetic archetype of wedding, where sacred and profane realms, divine and mundane planes are artistically interwoven to set the role model for human beings. Alongside with that, the hymn contains a plethora of hints marking the beginning

of a new era of the Vedic peoples; or, in fact, the ontological turn that has been documented in this hymn.

Among many cultures across the world, lunar and solar myths are typically linked to calendric systems developed by a certain culture given climatic and geographical disposition. In their narrow sense they represent a season cycle of the year, or astral myth, which is usually depicted by dying and resurrection of a god or an animal (Braginskaja, 2008: 502). Vyacheslav Ivanov asserts that lunar mythology began to expand across the cultures of the world since palaeolith, and similarly to solar myths they narrate legends, where the lunar deity has a certain relationship with a solar deity, which can be represented by both genders: female and/or male; also, frequently being in blood relations as brother and sister, twins, or spouses.

According to Rubinstein, the solar myths narrate the legends that could be broadly dichotomized into two categories: the more archaic ones related to seasonal changes, and newer ones, where the sun fights with darkness and evil, which is embodied in the form of ogres and terrifying beasts, especially the snakes (Rubinstein, 2008: 351).

In the case of divine wedding poetically narrated in RV 10.85, there are several fundamental aspects pertinent to ontological turn. A fiercely contested term adopted by Anthropologists and perhaps best defined by Paolo Heywood is very applicable to describe the ontological turn that is immortalized in RV 10.85, and thus opens avenue for the discussion.

Proponents of the ontological turn argue that 'culture' carries with it significant metaphysical baggage. In particular, they point out that it implies that although human beings may differ in their ideas about or viewpoints on the world and other material or natural objects, such objects themselves do not vary with these ideas. 'Cultures' may differ, but nature does not. The ontological turn proposes that we dispense with these metaphysical implications, in favour of a radical methodological openness to difference of all kinds, be it what we would call cultural and epistemological or natural and, indeed, ontological. (Heywood, 2017)

In order to corroborate the applicability of the term to the selected mythopoetic realm of RV I will enlist the physical and metaphysical elements that, according to my perception of this term, wonderfully feeds into the scheme. Thus, RV 10.85 unmistakably demonstrates the shift of roles among the mythological deities, which has been fostered by an array of changes in socioeconomic and political life of the Bronze Age Vedic peoples — the newcomers, who have now opted for a more sedentary life-style in the new homeland.

It is not uncommon that significant astronomical phenomenon, such as lunar or solar eclipse, were immortalized in the folk memory via mythopoetic legends and folk tales. Moreover, lunar or solar eclipse usually were seen as harbingers of significant events. It is evident that RV 10.85 narrates

the legend of solar eclipse that can be deduced by analysing the mythological “story line”. However, it must be admitted that such great socioeconomic overturn does not happen overnight, but rather as an aggregate of the emerging changes during several hundreds of years. As a result, the continuous interactions between the “newcomers” and the indigenous peoples of the Indian subcontinent were conducive to adopting new life style, namely, farming of new types of grains and vegetables; and thus, new agricultural techniques. Although, RV mentions barley, it has hardly any details on its growing other than sowing seeds. However, already among the oldest core of RV, “the family books” Maṇḍala 4 in hymn 57 outlines agricultural deities, a neologism to denote a plough in RV 4.57.4b, namely, *lāṅgala* that has apparently replaced an earlier *kr̥ṣṭi* for ploughing in RV 1.23.15d; and also, a furrow *sītā* in RV 4.57.7a that was a typical demarcation of the community boundaries. According to Jamison & Brereton the RV hymn 4.57 is a rather late addition (Brereton and Jamison, 2020b: 174), likewise the hymns of Maṇḍala 1.1-50 and the entire Maṇḍala 10.

The Moon God — newly pronounced Soma — marries the Sun Maiden, the daughter of Sun God, Sūrya; the Aśvins loose one wheel in 15cd; 16cd; Allusions to the stolen Sun’s wheel by Indra are displayed in 43cd, 44cd, where Sūryā is invited to be or replace that stolen wheel. Indra’s presence and prominence as the new Sun God is mentioned in 25 and 45ab. Savitar, whose role is typically to be an impeller of the events, is a very minor one here. As usually, Savitar impels the new course of the sun⁴², which is mentioned latently in 13; this hymn provides important calendric data by informing that a cow sacrifice is to be effected in the month of Aghās or Māgha (contemporary January-February), which marks the selection of and the day of a bridal procession to her husband’s home in *Arjunīs* or *Phālguna* the month during which the moon is full (February-March).

In 44ab she is implored not to smite her husband, the Moon God, for covering her during eclipse. Both the sun and the moon are described being together simultaneously as her draft-oxen in 10cd. Stanzas 28-30 create a vivid picture of intertwined mythological, astronomical and mundane realms, where the blood-stained bride’s garment, manifest both the red solar eclipse and the result of successful consummation of the marriage. See image No. 4.

⁴² The auspicious time for wedding according to gr̥hya sūtras is “During the northern course of the sun, in the time of the increasing moon, on an auspicious day he shall seize the hand of a girl” (ŚGS 1.5.5; cf. ĀGS 1.4.1) (Oldenberg, 1886, p. 20).

Image No. 4. Full annular solar eclipse

Full annular solar eclipse seen in Bangui, Central African Republic, on 15 January 2010, at 05:19:04 GMT (6:19 a.m. local time)⁴³.

Credit: By Tino Kreuzer - Own work, CC BY 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=8988428>

A similar imagery of the red sun or red coloured woollen shall as a marker of defloration, and solar eclipse is expressed by the Sun (*Saule*) beating the Moon (*Mēness*) as well as the Thunder God (*Pērkons*) smiting the Sun that was already highlighted by Mannhardt in the Baltic folklore (Mannhardt, 1875a: 232). Another striking parallel with the Latvian folklore is found in the folksong, where the Sun beats the Moon, while the Sons of God (*Dieva dēli*) are watching the process through the poppy leaves, being left downshifted to the backstage of the cosmic show (*Dainu skapis*, n.d.: 33926–0).

Other than mentioned earlier, stanzas 20-47 are out of the scope of this research as they further elaborate the cosmic-profane wedding beyond solar mythologeme. Therefore, they will not be discussed here.

2.3 Aśvina Śastra – Solar mythologeme – as described in the Brāhmaṇas of Ṛgveda

The mythological axes of Aś in AitBr and KB — the two ancillary Brāhmaṇas of RV— is doubtlessly the solar mythologeme that was discussed in the previous sub-chapter. Aś is the focal point of this study, and its literal translation is ‘invocation of the Aśvins’. In KB it begins by mentioning the most suitable time for its conduct, namely when Soma (plant) is in abundance, thus implicitly stating it is a seasonal rite. It comprises an IE Solar mythologeme, which is conveyed in

⁴³ See more images of solar eclipses here: <https://www.nasa.gov/eclipsephotos> [Accessed on 23 July, 2023].

its condensed version compared to Aitareya Brāhmaṇa. The story is narrated in the third person, and it goes like this. The god Savitar gave his daughter Sūryā to the king Soma, who represents the Moon deity, as if she was Prajāpati's daughter, too. A thousand verses are given over to the deities as a bridal gift.

AŚ constitutes the concluding part of the overnight Soma ritual Atirātra, namely, it follows the third sacrificial round, and the ritual injunctions prescribed here are designated to the officiating priest of the RV school — the Hotar (*Hotr*).

Keith, based on the linguistic analyses, namely the use of Imperfect and Perfect, as well as the more organized and logically ordered contents of KB clearly demonstrates that AitBr is older than KB, and actually the oldest of all the Brāhmaṇas. The perplexed use of Sandhi rules to count the syllables in AitBr 3.12 vs KB 14.3 as well as their absence in *Aitareya Āraṇyaka* 1.3.4 vs the same text in RV led to a conclusion that AitBr was redacted before *orthoepic diaskeuasis* of RV by Śākalya. Both of the Brāhmaṇas are certainly pre-Paninian as both are mentioned in his work. Similarly, they both are already indirectly mentioned in Yāska's Nirukta, who is quite unanimously considered among scholars to have lived ca. 700-500 BCE. The geographical coverage of KB alongside with *Śāṅkhāyāna śākhā* seems to be attested in the Northern Gujarat. Hence, its doctrines are well preserved in *Śāṅkhāyāna* tradition, which explains why it is so congruent with ŚŚS. However, its doctrines were not very well recognized by the contemporary priesthood. One top of that they were called inauspicious (*akuśalān*) and controversial (*vyāhatān*) (Keith, 1920: 38; 42–44; 46). Sreekrishna Sarma, the translator of Adhyāyas 14-17 dealing with Atirātra ritual, is of the same opinion regarding the age of both Brāhmaṇas, he highlights the main difference between two texts, namely,

KB covers the entire field of (*anuṣṭhāna-krama*), srāuta rites in the order of their performance (not in the (*pāṭhā-krama*) order of their mention in the Yajurveda (Sarma and Staal, 1983: 161).

As concerns the geography, Sreekrishna Sarma adds that nowadays the school of Kauṣītakins is still followed in Kerala, Gujarat, and to a more limited extent in Maharashtra (Ibid).

Aitareya Brāhmaṇa contains eight *Pañcikās* (each consisting of five Adhyāyas (chapters)), which makes 40 Adhyāyas; this number is also mentioned by Pāṇini (Keith, 1920: 35). AŚ is described in Pañcikā 4, Adhyāya 17.7.-11. AitBr unanimously is viewed older than KB, therefore, unsurprisingly it narrates an extended version of a legend that contains the solar mythologeme, the glimpses of which were sporadically scattered around the ten books of RV, culminating in RV 10.85. The nucleus of the solar mythologeme is expounded in paragraphs 7-8; the main deity to be propitiated in paragraph 9. As a rule, the Brāhmaṇa text commences with a synopsis of the

mythological legend, which is followed by a brief insight into the ritual actions and their hermeneutics, which is furthered by a detailed narrative of the race between gods for a bridal gift of Sūryā, namely, 1000 verses — the constituent of AŚ, which makes it the lengthiest śāstra (invocation) among all. An allusion to it is once conveyed in RV 1.119.1cd

cd sahasrāketuṃ vaṇināṃ śatadvāsuṃ śruṣṭivānāṃ varivodhām abhi prayāḥ ||⁷²

The nucleus of the solar mythologeme is reflected in Paragraphs 7-8; then comes the interpolation with the instructions to begin the invocation with propitiating verses to Agni from RV (6.15.18 and 10.18.8); in Paragraph 8 the metaphor of the race is continued, the Aśvins make their way as the winners by offering a portion in the sacrifice first to Agni, then Uṣas, and finally to Indra. This particular passage slightly unveils some sociological aspects by demonstrating the superiority of Indra as a male deity compared to the female deity Uṣas. It also demonstrates the prominence of Indra among other deities, however, here he plays a very minor role. Paragraphs 9-11 continue the narrative that is interwoven with the explanations of the meters employed to address the respective deities. Even though, the two Aśvins possess this invocation *per se* and are the quasi-protagonists of the ritual scene, here they take merely the role of wooers, with Soma as the bridegroom. Although, the divine actors of the sacrificial ground are the following: Agni, Uṣas, Indra, and the Aśvins, the two main deities who are propitiated throughout paragraphs 9-11 and thus, brought in prominence are: the Sun God, Sūrya, and Agni, with the respective meters employed to bring prosperity and blessings to both the officiating priest — the Hotar and the commissioner of the sacrifice — Yajamāna. Alongside the main actors, there are also other deities that receive praises during this early morning ritual. Thus, the ritual is commenced by kindling fire (Agni) accompanied with the recitation of RV 6.15.18 and 10.18.8 to Agni, who is the deity that conveys the fire oblations (clarified butter etc.) to the gods; then Uṣas is praised as a precursor of the sunrise; then Indra is praised by RV 7.32.26; 7.32.22; 7.66.10; Sūrya by RV 10.158.1; 1.15, 1.115.1; 10.37.1 (it also includes obeisance to Mitra and Varuṇa); to Dyaus and Pṛthvī by RV 1.22.13 and 1.160.1; and it concludes with the propitiating of Bṛhaspati by RV 6.50.6 and 2.23.15⁴⁴ In order to analyse this legend, I will provide both the original Sanskrit text from Aufrecht's critical edition (1879), which I have improved by employing a proper IAST⁴⁵, and my translation consulting the two existing ones by Keith (1920) and Martin Haug (1863). Although, Keith fiercely

⁴⁴ See ĀŚS 6.5.; cf. ŚŚS 9.20. — both will be discussed in Chapter 3.

⁴⁵ Aufrecht's transliteration does not distinguish the IAST ś and ṣ; hence I have corrected all the instances, for instance, Aṣvins for Aśvins, āgachans for āgachams etc.

criticizes Haug's translation and faulty manuscripts he had in his possession, Haug's input is invaluable, in virtue of being an eye-witness of the rituals described in AitBr.

In Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇa division of chapters differs from that in AitBr, namely, there are no Pañcikās (books consisting of five chapters (Adhyāyas), instead it comprises 30 Adhyāyas. Hence, AŚ is described in Adhyāya 18.1-5 according to Keith (1920) and Bruno Lindner (1887), whereas the critical edition by Sreekrishna Sarma E.R. (1968) has not only one more paragraph added, but also the first paragraph contains 27 sentences. His edition provides a more detailed breakdown of paragraphs into numbered sentences, which are differently organized in paragraphs; it is also displayed in GRETEL; and thus, the nucleus of mythologeme is expounded in Adhyāya 18.1-6. Disparities of the contents between the Keith & Lindner's vs Sarma's edition begin with Paragraph 2.

AŚ of KB differs from AitBr not only with chronological sequence of the rites, but also in terms of the contents. It is mostly valuable for the reason it provides more details, when the ritual has to be conducted, i.e., when Soma is in abundance, which is a noteworthy indication for the research of Soma question, however, there is no room to expand on this. In contrast to AitBr, it narrates only a condensed legend of solar myth in *Khaṇḍa* (Paragraph) 1; thus, leaving room to explicate on the meters and number of the hymns employed for the invocation of the Aśvins. In his edition, Sreekrishna Sarma brings forward a newly discovered palm-leaf manuscript with extensive commentaries by the native commentator Udaya, which in turn, resulted in producing a new critical edition of KB that was based on the higher quality manuscripts, concomitantly admitting the shortcomings of Lindner's use of the Malayālam manuscript. Thus, the main body of critical apparatus consisted of five manuscripts with three supplementary ones⁴⁶ (Sreekrishna Sarma, 1968: v). Hence, for the discussion, I will employ and translate the excerpts from Sreekrishna Sarma's critical edition⁴⁷, namely, the sentences 1-18, because the sentences 19-27 explicate on the meters employed and their functions. The beginning of paragraph 2 provides reasoning on the necessity to propitiate the respective deities: Agni — to obtain the world, Uṣas — to obtain the world of atmosphere, the Aśvins to obtain the yonder world, Sūrya —to obtain the fourth world of gods, the water, Indra by means of Pragāthas to obtain cattle and Bṛhatī to secure exhalation and inhalation i.e., life, and finally, Bṛhaspatī to obtain support in life. Paragraphs 3-5 provide a very

⁴⁶ More details on MSS used see in (Sreekrishna Sarma, 1968: v–viii).

⁴⁷ Although the edition is protected by the copyright law under Berne Convention, it has an exclusion for research purposes, which corresponds to the purpose of this Master's thesis.

detailed explanation of the meters, number of verses, the exact timing for conclusion, namely, each constituent element or actor engaged in the ritual scene, and their respective functions.

Chapter 3: Some conjectures on astronomical dating of Vedic Solar mythologeme

Following to the aforementioned analyses of IE solar mythologeme and its representation in RV and two ancillaries Brāhmaṇas: AitBr and KB, it can be concluded that the solar myth or IE Dioskuric pattern was well known to the Vedic poets, and thus, well represented throughout RV, except for Maṇḍalas 2 and 3. Likewise, the gradual shifting from animal husbandry to agricultural farming was briefly sketched in subchapter 2.2, namely RV 4.57.

However, noteworthy is to draw attention to the stanzas of Maṇḍala 4 that comprise the oldest core of RV and also contain eulogies to the cosmic wedding of the Sun Maiden to the Aśvins. In great contrast to other “tales”, the stanzas: 4.43.2, 4.43.6, 4.44.1, 4.45.1 narrate the legend using Present tense, which overtly manifests that the narrators had “eye witnessed” the self-choice of the Sun Maiden and her cosmic bridal procession. As it was already discussed in the previous chapter, typically it was an astronomical phenomenon that served as the basis for solar and lunar myths to mark seasonal changes; and thereby, was conducive to the development of calendric systems.

As it has been noted by Mircea Eliade, most often the beginning of the New Year was celebrated across the world in March-April, or September, October, December-January to demarcate the beginning of seasons, with the aim to raise taboo on the harvest or ripening season for grains and fruit; and thus, periodic regeneration of life. Furthermore, lunar phases help to measure time and also to manifest “eternal return” (Eliade, 1954: 51–52; 86). It is perfectly expressed in RV 10.85.19, which, as mentioned earlier, is a rather late addition.

He becomes ever new as he is born; as beacon of the days he goes at the forefront of the dawns. He portions out their share to the gods as he comes here. The Moon extends his lifetime long (Jamison and Brereton, 2014: 1523).

Since the main actors of the Vedic mythologeme are the two Aśvins and the Sun Maiden, here we clearly speak of the solar phenomenon that was experienced by the Vedic people at or around dawn time, and shortly before the sunrise. Little or any doubt is left to assume the Aśvins represented the two appearances of planet Venus, which is the third brightest celestial body visible in the sky with naked eye. Furthermore, it is now known that if viewed from geocentric position, the motion of Venus is very rhythmical having eight-year cycle during which its trajectory “draws” a quasi-pentagram or else known as five petals of Venus, when it traverses between the sun and the earth. Over the eight years, each phenomenon – each relative position of Earth, Venus, and the sun – occurs five times. Hence, every eight years Venus returns to the same place in the sky on about the same date (Ottewel, 2023). However, in between eight years cycle the apparitions of Venus repeat roughly once every 1.6 years, taking place alternately in the morning and evening skies,

depending whether Venus lies to the east of the Sun or to the west. Transits of Venus occur in cycles of 243 years with the current pattern of transits being pairs of transits separated by eight years, at intervals of about 105.5 years or 121.5 (*The Nine Planets*, 2019). Nevertheless, on rare occasions Venus can be viewed in both its apparitions within 24 hours, namely after sunset and before sunrise. This scenario arises once in eight years, which is also known as its synodic period of 583.92 days (Williams, 2023), when Venus is at its maximum separation from the ecliptic and concomitantly at inferior conjunction. Then, its both apparitions — morning and evening — will be visible either in Northern or Southern hemisphere (McClure, 2017). Noteworthy to mention is that Mesopotamian goddess Inanna (Sumerian) also called Ishtar (Akkadian) was a divine representation of the planet Venus who was second in rank after the Moon God. Inanna was a winged warrior and sex goddess whose double nature was well reflected in Mesopotamian mythology; that draws to a certain parallelism with the Aśvins. Venus, alongside Mercury, Mars, and Jupiter were known to the ancient Babylonian astronomers ca. 1000 BCE (Black et al., 1992: 37; 109).

Now, it is necessary to find out in which season the ritual described in AŚ might have been celebrated originally. Although, the cosmic wedding of RV.10.85 provides calendric indication of the time for the most auspicious time to select a bride, i.e., modern day January-February (*Āghās*) and the time for the wedding is in *Arjunīs* i.e., modern day February-March. However, it is unlikely to be the original timing, taking into account that, first, Maṇḍala 10 is a rather late addition, and could also be just a slightly earlier composition compared to AitBr based on Michael Witzel's study of the Vedic dialects, where he asserts that Maṇḍalas 3,4 and 5 demonstrate hardly any cerebralization of the consonants i.e., retroflex consonants, compared to 8, where they are represented in abundance (Witzel, 1989, p. 26). Thus, leading to indirect conclusion that Maṇḍalas 3,4, and 5 belong to the oldest strata of the “family books.” Another counter argument is that at the time when the Vedic “newcomers” had already penetrated well into the Indian subcontinent, they encountered different climatic conditions and geography. For instance, the seasons mentioned in RV range from three to six. Thus, within one hymn that belongs to the oldest section of RV a poet recalls three seasons in 1.164.2;48 as well as mentions more contemporaneous experience — five and six seasons in 1.164.12.

Apart from these scanty accounts, the very nature and functions of the Aśvins can be telling and reveal the “original” seasonal timing. The Aśvins are frequently associated with abundance, fecundity (RV 1.157.5; 1.181.8; 7.67.6; 7.68.8), honey, and rain, which at times is expressed using the epithet of ghee (1.157.2-5; 1.181.9; 8.5.6; 19; 21), the latter two had served to consider them

as Rain Gods by Vodskov. Their chariot is loaded with honey (RV.182.2), they pour ghee (RV 10.36.6), they bring all kinds of goods, cattle and nourishment (1.92.16-17), they fill the rivers with water (1.112.12ab); all of which is a matter for craving after cold winter when there is scarcity of food. In essence, their relation to fecundity is unmistakably narrated in the legend that is fully preserved in AitBr, however, it is evident that it was known to the poets of RV, as fragmentary allusions are expressed here and there throughout RV (1.116.2cd). In the episode of the prize-race, the Aśvins chose a donkey as their draught animal, which perfectly describes the motion of the planet Venus in the sky, i.e., it slowly traverses the sky to quickly exit; it has a double nature — early morning (Morning Star) or late evening (Evening Star) apparition within 1,6 years cycle; and also, the spring time that brings more light and overall fecundity. In addition to all aforesaid, a particular idiosyncrasy has caught my attention, namely the warning of professional astronomers and organizations to never view partial or annual eclipse without specialized eye equipment, as it can cause permanent blindness (Davis and Carney, 2022). Why so? The reasons are two. First, KB instructs the Hotar that AŚ is to be recited before the sun rises.

Whenever the sun creeps over on to the front (of the oblation holder), whenever the Hotṛ himself can discern it, whenever its ruddiness comes on, whenever all its rays move out towards him, that is the time for the conclusion. (18.4.) [...] so regarding it, he should conclude. He should offer a libation to the shining one, when the sun cannot be discerned, he who is unsuited!; he becomes then revealed to them. (18.5) (Keith, 1920: 446–447)

Of all the wonders the Aśvins are famous for it is also their ability to return the sight to a blind one (RV 1.112.8; 10.39.3) i.e., to R̥jṛāśva who was blinded by his father (RV 1.112.16; 1.117.17-18). Here, it is noteworthy to mention that mythology tends to either exaggerate or at times even invert the instances that had been “experienced” by a distant ancestor of the narrator. Thereby, blindness effected by viewing the solar eclipse during Venus’s apparition at dawn time may have possibly given grounds to narrate the miracle as an inverted phenomenon, namely, the restoration of sight from blindness.

Thus, in the closing line the legend reveals that regardless of its slowness and lack of human edible milk, the donkey is potent with a double kind of semen, namely potent to inseminate both a she-ass and a mare. It is very likely that by incorporating in the story line a donkey, the creators of the legend wished to impart their astral observations. At first, the Aśvins are known to traverse the sky from one side to other (RV 8.528; 31), they are also as swift as thoughts (RV 1.117.15). As concerns the season of the year, RV 1.116.8 explicitly gives the account of snow either experienced in winter or early spring in a colder climate or mountainous terrain of Gandhāra land.

The beginning of astronomical spring falls onto vernal equinox, at about 21st of March; it is also significant time of the year as the subsolar point afterwards migrates north (Evers, 2023). Therefore, the time around vernal equinox oftentimes is celebrated to propitiate the respective deities for the upcoming fecundity. Therefore, regardless of the fact that apparitions of Venus can be observed also in autumn and winter, these options are dropped in the first place due to the reason that in autumn, is the time for harvest, namely, the result is already there, hence, no need to propitiate the deity for more. In addition, the days gradually become shorter and thus the light “is receding”. Another aspect in favour of spring time its brightest luminosity can be observed the longest, duration of which lasts from 80-160 minutes. Thus, considering the intricate trajectory and double cycle of Venus, within one year it can be observed as both Morning and Evening Star, where the flipping of its movement takes place either with 2-3- or 7-8-months distance in time. Moreover, if during one spring it can be observed as Morning Star, then within 1,6 years cycle its inverted apparition as Evening Star comes into play. Other arguments to corroborate the spring time hypothesis are pertinent to seasonal climatic changes and fauna. Springtime and summer are the mating time for most of the wild animals. The stimulus to mate is the result of a photoperiodic response, which is thought to be controlled by day length (*A Dictionary of Biology*, n.d.). These spring months in colder climates, in fact, demarcate the awaking of nature, from winter sleep and opening of fertility season with spring rains, thunder and lightning. Therefore, it could be assumed that at the early stages of the Vedic solar myth development the rituals to celebrate fecundity were conducted in spring months: March-April-May. Of similar views was also Hillebrandt who considered the *Agniṣṭoma* sacrifice that is also related to the Atirātra with Aś were originally conducted in the spring on full or new moon day. Keith, on the contrary rejects Hillebrandt’s assertion completely. Concomitantly, Hillebrandt placed Aś among the rituals that are held in autumn, which is certainly of later development. However, he, Ludwig and Krichenbauer considered Uṣas as the harbinger of spring or the Vedic New Year. (Hillebrandt, 1897: 77–78; 124–125, 1899: 26–27; Keith, 1998b: 327).

Another phenomenon to be considered in relation to the Aśvins is their wedding to the Sun Maiden, Sūryā, the accounts of which were given in Chapter 2. Thus, compared to all their main functions as wonder makers, saviours and healers, their wedding is narrated less frequently, the fact that is telling by itself. Namely, it “tells” the audience that it was quite an extraordinary cosmic event — solar or lunar eclipse. Bearing in mind that lunar myths are considerably older than solar ones, and also taking into account that solar eclipse, especially the one that lasts several minutes is a very spectacular and concomitantly frightening view, I dare to presume that the Vedic legends narrate

an astronomical phenomenon of solar eclipse, which might have been eye witnessed by the composers of RV hymns 4.43-45. The fact of eye witnessing is not just a mere conjecture based here on the choice of grammatical tense. For the Vedic language is complex and the use of grammatical tenses and forms is so sophisticated with very clear distinctions what has and what has not been eye witnessed by the narrator. Hence, this is a rather strong argument in favour of personal accounts considering the fact that solar eclipses occur every year ranging from two to five times. Now, the next step is to find the most plausible candidates of total and annual solar eclipses using the JavaScript solar eclipse explorer developed by NASA (The National Aeronautics and Space Administration), which is an independent U.S. agency (Espenak and O'Byrne, 2010). Now, the question arises: how to set the right timeframe? As the very name of the Aśvins suggests, they are related to horses, and thus their cult could have developed alongside or after the horse domestication, which began in Eurasia ca. 6000 years ago. Besides, it is known that a wild mare was used at initial stages of domestication to augment or even sustain the herd of horses.

Because stallions are inherently more difficult to handle than mares, the easiest way to maintain or grow herd sizes would have been to restock existing herds with wild females. Whereas the high levels of diversity and limited geographic structure in the horse mitochondrial genome may thus reflect the continued augmentation of domestic herds with wild mares from a wide geographic area, the observed low levels of Y chromosome variability might reflect the strong domestication bottleneck in western central Eurasia (Warmuth et al., 2012: 8204–8205).

The use of mares by the Vedic peoples is well attested throughout RV. Thus, the Aśvins replaced the lost leg of the mare Viśpalā with a metal shank (RV 1.116.15), Dawn is compared to a mare (RV 4.52.2) and she is rich in prize-mares (RV 1.48.16), the Sun God is often conveyed by one (RV 4.14.3) or seven mares (RV 1.50.8), etc.

Domestication of horses gives a starting date ca. 4000 BCE; however, NASA's JavaScript solar eclipse explorer provides reliably accurate data only starting from 1499 BCE; the nearest site to the ancient Gandhāra land, where the solar eclipse might have been observed by the Vedic peoples is modern day Islamabad in Pakistan, Latitude: 33° 42' 00" N/ Longitude: 73° 10' 00" E. As concerns the closing date, then it is calculated considering the approximate dating of AitBr, which puts us back by the latest to 700 BCE.

Considering all the aforementioned facts and arguments, the following criteria have been selected: 1) timeframe between 1499-700 BCE; 2) spring month: March; 3) the time: at around sunrise/sunset. Thus, based on the astronomical data, there were five partial solar eclipses in Gandhāra region within the timeframe from 15th-12th century BCE — the time that tentatively corresponds to the composing and codification of RV. Due to the limitations of this paper, only condensed results are presented here.

In conclusion, the longest and thus most spectacular partial eclipses that occurred in the month of March were the ones that took place at dawn, i.e., at the time when both AitBr and KB prescribe to conduct the early morning rituals to the mysterious celestial divinities — Aśvins. The ones that lasted more than one hour occurred in 1352, 1249, 832, and 795 BCE. And yet, the most spectacular and long lasting was the one that occurred exactly on vernal equinox, 21st March, 925 BCE, and lasted for 2 h 35 minutes, which is the most plausible candidate that marked the ontological turn and was immortalized as the wedding hymn RV 10.85.

Chapter 4: Invocation of Aśvins during Atirātra as described in the Śrauta Sūtras of Ṛgveda

This chapter deals with the compositions called *Sūtras* that are chronologically later than Brāhmaṇas. Their distinct feature that distinguishes them from the Brāhmaṇas is more instructive and condensed way of conveying the instructions to the officiating priests. The very word *sūtra* means a thread,

which is applicable to both the whole work and its individual sentences or paragraphs, has been variously explained, but there can be no doubt that it is taken from the image of weaving and of woven material made out of threads. A thread stretched out lengthwise as a warp to be crossed by the woof may continue — then *sūtra* becomes a name for the whole work — or it may be cut on both sides of the frame — then *sūtra* denotes the single paragraphs. (Gonda, 1977: 466)

There are two types of *Sūtras* — comprising the solemn rites — the *Śrauta Sūtras* and domestic rites named — the *Gr̥hya Sūtras*. Since *Gr̥hya Sūtras* do not contain Aś, therefore, in this chapter I will investigate at length the representation of Aś in the two Śrauta sūtras ancillary to RV, namely, *Āśvalāyana Śrauta Sūtra* (ĀŚS) that belongs to *Śākala* school and *Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra* (ŚŚS) that has affinity with *Bāṣkala* school. Based on epigraphical research by Louis Renou, geographically *Śāṅkhāyana* school (attested only in two epigraphs found in Kanauj and Māndhātā) was located in Gujarat and was evidently less popular than *Āśvalāyana*, the inscriptions and MSS of which were more dispersed; they were attested in Bengal, Jodhpur, in the South: regions of Godāvāri, Tinnevely, Kāncīpura, Tanjore and in the North Arcot, the kingdom of Vijayanagara (Renou, 1947: 56–57). As Hillebrandt points it out the titles of both the sūtras most likely are the family or clan names, and hence the actual authors are unknown. Moreover, according to him, the Śrauta compositions being derivations from *śruti* literature that are *per se* divine revelations (Mantra and Brāhmaṇa texts), have gained their prominence, in virtue of their instructions how to conduct the great sacrifices. Therefore, according to Jan Gonda for conducting these sacrifices three or more sacrificial fires are required that gave them the name *vaitānikas* (Gārhapatya⁴⁸, Āhavanīya⁴⁹ and Dakṣiṇa⁵⁰), whereas Keith claims that one out of the three fires can suffice (Keith, 1998b: 313). In order to conduct a sacrifice, each Veda school has their respective priests with

⁴⁸ *Gārhapatya* — the householder's fire that is acquired either by friction or borrowed from a wealthy man or a prominent sacrificer, which is established in the north with a round shape altar; in this fire oblations are prepared (Keith, 1998b: 316–317); cf. or received from his father and transmitted to his descendants (MONIER-WILLIAMS, 1899).

⁴⁹ *Āhavanīya* — consecrated fire taken from the householder's perpetual fire and prepared for receiving oblations; it is established in the east with a square shaped altar; in this fire the oblations are sacrificed (Ibid.).

⁵⁰ *Dakṣiṇa* — a fire that is established to the south from Gārhapatya and is shaped as half-moon; it is used for cooking offerings except for meat offerings (Ibid.).

three assistants, in total comprising 16 officiating priests that are all involved in the performance of the great sacrifice; or 17 according to Kauṣītakins, adding up *Sadasya* who is responsible for overseeing the entire *Sadas*⁵¹, and is mentioned in the expiation (*prāyaścitta*) section of KB. Apart from the priests, however, the involvement of other individuals to perform some minor actions can be necessitated (Keith, 1920: 48; 498, 1998b: 313). Hence, the Śrauta Sūtra of a particular Veda provides instructions only for the priests of its tradition, and therefore, these instructions are fragmented (Hillebrandt, 1897: 20). Thus, mantra part from RV falls under the responsibility of the Hotar (*Hotṛ*) with his assistants: *Maitrāvaruṇa*, *Acchāvāka*, and *Grāvastut*; the chanting part from Sāmaveda is the responsibility of the principal priest Udgātar (*Udgātṛ*) with the three assistants: *Prastotṛ*, *Pratihartṛ*, *Subrahmanya*; conducting the very sacrifice or *yajus* as explicated in Yajurveda is performed by the principal priest Adhvaryu with the three assistants: *Pratiprasthātṛ*, *Neṣṭṛ*, *Unnetṛ*; the observation of the entire process is performed by the principal priest Brahman who is affiliated to Atharvaveda, with his three assistants: *Brāhmaṇacchaṃsin*, *Agnīdhra*, *Potṛ* (ĀŚŚ 4.1-6). Hence, the precepts conveyed in ĀŚŚ and ŚŚŚ are actually the guidelines for the Hotar.

4.1. Locus of Aśvina Śastra within Atirātra ritual

Atirātra injunction is a Soma sacrifice that is a constituent of *Agniṣṭoma* or else named *Jyotiragniṣṭoma* ritual. Agniṣṭoma serves as a role model ritual for all Soma rituals the length and complexity of which vary considerably. They all, in turn, fall under a broader category titled Jyotiṣṭoma rituals.

With regard to the principal division of sacrifices AŚ is a *vikṛti* of Prātaranuvāka that, in turn, is its *prakṛti*. Following to a further classification, there are rites — *naimittika* — that are conducted occasionally to celebrate certain events, then there also the optional ones — *kāmya* — rites performed in order to acquire the desired favours, personal advantages etc.; they consist of the regular injunctions that are complemented by the addition of special formulas. And, finally — the obligatory rites called *nitya* that have to be performed at a certain time of the year. In its present day form the ritual prescribed in AŚ being a part of Atirātra belongs to *kāmya* rites, however, originally in a great likelihood, it might have been a *nitya* rite. Furthermore, AŚ being a Soma sacrifice constitutes a part in Agniṣṭoma ritual, which is a fundamental form of Soma sacrifice. Apart from this, the rituals can also be dichotomized as *iṣṭi* that require plant-based oblations i.e., rice, barley, cakes etc., and the animal sacrifices — *paṣubandha*, which existed either

⁵¹ *Sadas* — n., a shed erected in the sacrificial enclosure to the east of the Prācīnavamśa (MONIER-WILLIAMS, 1899).

independently or as an integral part of the Soma sacrifices. Other types of sacrifices, in contrast to Soma that do not involve *Sāman* singers, are called *Haviryajñas* (Gonda, 1977: 467–468; Keith, 1998b: 313; 316).

Rituals lasting only one day are named *ekāha*; other one-day interpolations — *savas* — the purpose of which is either to stimulate the sacrifice or connect the longer rites — *ahīnas* or *sattras* — the longer sacrificial sessions that can last from 13 up to 100 days; at times can even be extended to one or three years (Gonda, 1977: 467; 495; 663; Haug, 1863b: 283). See image No.5. In the introductory part of the translation of the two Brāhmaṇas: AitBr and KB, Keith claims that Atirātra is one of the four constituents of Jyotiṣṭoma sacrifices that form a long-lasting succession of Soma sacrificial sessions: Agniṣṭoma, Ukhtya, Ṣoḍaśin and Atirātra. However, in his later work he asserts that there are seven Agniṣṭoma sacrifices: Agniṣṭoma, Atyagniṣṭoma Ukhtya, Ṣoḍaśin, Vājapeya, Aitrātra, and Aptoryāma; of them Agniṣṭoma forms a generic name of Jyotiṣṭoma (Keith, 1920: 53, 1998b: 334). Whereas, Sreekrishna Sarma mentions additional three: Vājapeya, Atyagniṣṭoma, and Aptoryāma being derivatives of the three former ones (Sarma & Staal, 1983, p. 163). See image No. 6. Without substantiating his conclusions with the references to sources, Keith asserts that on the day of Atirātra ritual the victim animals are dedicated to goddess Sarasvatī, completely missing the point that it is an overnight ritual (Keith, 1920, p. 327). Generally, Atirātra is *ekāha* i.e., one-day rite, however, sometimes it is also considered as *ahīna* i.e., the rite conducted for more than one day; it commences a new day (more precisely a night), the fifth in succession, right after *Ṣoḍaśin*, and in essence is an overnight ritual that is divided into three rounds called *rātri-paryāya-śastras* conducted by the Hotar with his assistants. KB does not explicitly notify the deity to be propitiated that is Indra and Agni. All the sacerdots involved in these sacrificial sessions must stay awake throughout the night in order to ensure protection from evil spirits. Hence, during the third round AŚ is recited to grant prosperity pertaining to cattle and progeny of the *Yajamāna*.

This is the description of Atirātra narrated by Keith⁵²:

The Atirātra attains the number of twenty-nine Stotras and Śastras by adding a series of twelve of both, which are used to accompany three rounds, Paryāyas, each of four sets of goblets, which in turn are led off by that of the Hotr, Mairāvaruṇa, Brāhmaṇacchaṅsin, and Achāvāka. The offerings are made during this nocturnal carouse, which gives the name to the rite, to Indra Apiśarvara. When the cups have been duly offered and the priests have drunk, then the Sandhi Stotra is performed, while a cake is made ready for the Aśvins, the name of the Stotra being derived from the twilight, which is about to break. It has nine verses and is sung to the Rathantara tune. Then follows the Prātaranuvāka to the Aśvins, which must contain a thousand verses or more, or a thousand Brhati verses, made up artificially from other metres: the last verse is to be said after sunrise. Then the Adhvaryu takes the cup of the Hotr, the other assistants of

⁵² The orthography has been adjusted by applying IAST.

the Adhvaryu the rest, and with the Soma from the previous night, a cup is offered to the Aśvins, while the Pratiprasthātṛ offers the cake. There is also a fourth animal victim, a he-goat for Sarasvatī. The Atirātra might, it is clear, be performed without the Ṣoḍaśin cup and the corresponding Stotra and Śastra, but this is not the prevailing view. It lasted with its nocturnal continuation over the night, and so can be considered as the tail of the sacrifice, which laps over from the end of the month into the next month (Keith, 1998b: 335–336).

In 1975 Fritz Staal asserted that the Vedic traditions had survived in two areas of contemporary India: 1) western India with extensions to the north — Maharashtra, Saurashtra, and Uttar Pradesh, 2) in south India — Tamil Nad, Andhra Pradesh, and Mysore. Besides, the southern tradition is stronger. Staal’s fieldwork during which he documented the ritual — Atirātra-Agnicayana 12-day long Soma ritual performed by Nambudiri Ṛgveda brahmins of Chermukku (Ceṛumukku) Vaidikan families from Śukapuram *grāmam* (village) who belong to an isolated Kauṣītaki branch. Most interesting is the fact that out of all one-day (*ekāha*) Śrauta rituals, only two are performed by Nambudiris until today: Agniṣṭoma (ranking first) and Atirātra-Agnicayana (ranking fourth). According to Staal, combining Agnicayana with Atirātra ritual most likely is of a rather late development as well as the seven aforementioned types of Soma ritual. The very archaic schools of Jaiminīya Saṃhitā, to which Nambudiris belong, mention only two types, namely, Agniṣṭoma (after 3.5) and Atirātra (after 3.9). Moreover, it is only Atirātra that is once mentioned in RV 7.103.7 — in a satirical form, where the poet compares frogs during the rainy season with brahmins performing the Soma ritual Atirātra around the lake. The prescribed season by Nambudiri traditional scriptures to perform Atirātra with its constituent Aś is *vasanta* or ‘brilliant season’ i.e., spring, which originally might have been interpreted by Nambudiris as *māghādīpañca* or *five* months beginning with *Māgha* (January-February), *Phālguna* (February-March), *Caitra* (March-April), *Vaiśākha* (April-May), and *Jyaiṣṭha* (May-June), which perfectly corroborates with the discussion in Chapter 3, where the original time for Atirātra/Aś was conjectured to be in March during vernal equinox. The rituals have to be conducted within the bright half (*śuklapakṣa*) of the month, i.e., to begin on or after new moon (*amāvāsya*) and be over on or before full moon (*pūrṇimāvāsya*). In 1975, the first new moon was on 12 April, the first day of Caitra, and Aś was respectively performed on 11th day, 25 April⁵³, which was commenced at 2.30 A.M. and concluded at 6.30 A.M. (Staal et al., 1983: 171; 182; 184–185; 193–194; 680; 686).

⁵³ Watch a full documentray “Altar of Fire” available on Youtube (*Altar of Fire*, 1976).

Image No. 5. Vedic Sattra of 360 days — Gavām Ayana

Image No. 5 displays a graphic representation of the ritual sequence of the Vedic *sattra* — *Gavām Ayana* that lasts for 360 days. In totality, these are 37 days that the sacrificer (*Yajamāna*) devotes to the performance of the sequence of rituals in association with the officiating priests (Haug, 1863b: 279).

Image No. 6. The scheme of *Jyotiṣṭoma* rituals

The sequence and relationship of *Jyotiṣṭoma* rituals (Sarma and Staal, 1983: 163).

4.2. Aśvina Śastra — contents and locus et modus operandi of the Aśvins

Locus of Aś within Atirātra ritual in ĀśS is congruent to AitBr, namely, the interpolated Sandhi Stotra (*sandhistotra*) at the end of the last round (*pariyāya*) of Atirātra connects it to Aś; however, Nambudiris call it (*āśvinastuti*) – which is chanted by Sāmavedins (Staal et al., 1983: 680). Aś is further narrated in Chapter (*Kaṇḍikā*) 6.5-25.

4.3. Invocation of Aśvins – as described in Āśvalāyana Śrauta Sūtra.

Thus, in 25 sentences or short paragraphs⁵⁴, the Hotar receives very minute instructions on how to perform AŚ. ĀŚS being more closely affiliated to AitBr likewise is more descriptive on the spatial and physical movements of the Hotar within the sacrificial ground, which is the distinctive feature of AitBr and ĀŚS schools. Thus, sentences 2-5 instruct the Hotar to come out of Sadas following the route for an unconcluded sacrifice and offers six oblations into Āgnīdhrya fire while kneeling down on the right knee and reciting mantras to Agni, Uṣas, the Aśvins, Surya and Indra. Another distinction from ŚŚS is that the Hotar includes the refrain *svāhā*⁵⁵ at the end of each propitiating mantra, e.g., *uṣā ajvinī traiṣṭubhena chandasā tām aśyāntām anvārabhe tasyai mām avatu tasya svāhā* (ĀŚS 6.5.2b), which surprisingly cannot be identified with any hymns of RV. Then, sentence three instructs the Hotar to consume ghee (oblation) and to touch or sip water. Sentence four instructs to take a position of a bird that is about to fly up:

Having partaken (the *iḍā*) and moved back (to the Sadas) he (the Hotar) should sit behind his Dhiṣṇya hearth like a bird, which is about to take a flight, with the heels and thighs held together by means of the forehands and the central part with the two knees (Ranade, 1981: 179).

And, finally, sentence five orders the Hotar to recite AŚ while seated in the above-described posture. The following sentences 6-25 elaborate on the sequence of hymns to be selected from RV as well as the meters to employed in the recitation to each particular deity.

4.4. Invocation of Aśvins – as described in Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra.

Likewise, as in AitBr and KB, AŚ or the invocation of the Aśvins is incorporated within the Atirātra or overnight ritual, namely, it is the concluding part, when all three night-rounds have been completed. Being a Śrauta Sūtra that is ancillary to RV, it provides detailed and yet concise instructions for the Hotar who recites mantras from RV. It is described in Adhyāya 9 Kaṇḍikā 20.1-35, the full translation of which can be found in the Appendix 2. The Sūtra text justifies its name as it is completely technical, concise and instructive. Unlike the corresponding KB it does not contain any details of the solar mythologem. All in all, the 35 sentences in which the AŚ is expounded, they contain only the hints in the form of concise quotes from the particular RV hymns, which apparently were so well-known to the adherents of the Śāṅkhāyana school that a couple of words were sufficient to restore the entire hymn and to easily juggle with the particular stanzas and the meters in order to achieve the desired result of one thousand stanzas thus forming a bridal gift. However, there are some inconsistencies and discrepancies spotted with regard to the number

⁵⁴ Cf. Ranade's translation that has 24 sentences.

⁵⁵ *svāhā* – ind., hail to; an exclamation used in making oblations to the gods (Monier-Williams, 1899).

of stanzas and also the RV as the only source mentioned there. Thus, in spite of the fact that 9.20.6 instructs to recite only the mantras of RV, the line in 9.20.27 is clearly extracted from AitBr (IV.17.10.14), or the sentence 9.20.34 contradicts AitBr, namely, it states that the Hotar must perform an oblation accompanied with *Vaṣaṭ* call only with the Virāj meter, or the Triṣṭubh (9.20.35), whereas according to AitBr IV.17.11.18 *yatraivam vidvan gāyātryā ca virājāca vaṣaṭkuryāt*. Nonetheless, the most perplexing is the indicated number of stanzas by *Suparṇa* family or else known as 11 *Vāḷakhilya* hymns, namely, 103 — the number of stanzas that cannot be found in any known text. Therefore, the sentence 15 of ŚŚS informs that the missing stanzas ranging from 13-19 can be added; Caland provides reference to KB 18.4 and *Vāḷakhilya* hymns 1.2-12 in the edition by Isidor Scheftelowitz; cf. Scheftelowitz refers to Ṛgvidhāna 1.20.3 that mentions *sauparṇāni pavitrāṇi sūktāṇ ekādaśābhyāset [..]* and Bṛhaddevatā 3.119 that mentions *śaśvadādīni tu daśāvinān imānīti indrāvaruṇayo stutiḥ | sauparṇeyās tu yāḥ kāścin niptastutiṣu stutāḥ*; however, even Ṛgveda Khilāni contains only 84 stanzas. According to Scheftelowitz's study, the *Suparṇa* hymns are of a rather late composition, belonging to the new mantra pool, most likely added during the Maṇḍala 10 of RV (Scheftelowitz 1902, 192–199); cf. Jamison & Brereton who assert that *Vāḷakhilya* hymns were apocryphal hymns inserted in RV, hence the 11 hymns of RV 8.49-59 contain only 80 stanzas out of 103; they follow a certain pattern, namely, the hymns are organized into pairs that laud a particular deity, thus having a poetical or didactical method that is distinctive from the rest of RV (Jamison and Brereton 2014, I–III:1130); cf. Bronkhorst, who mentions 92 that are attested in *Śaiśirīya Saṃhitā* (Bronkhorst 2016, 353); cf. Staal who suggests number 33 instead of 103 (Staal et al., 1983: 685). This leads to an assumption that *Śāṅkhāyāna Saṃhita* possibly contained the full count of 103 stanzas composed by the *Suparṇa* family.

A full description of AŚ and the sequence of RV mantras that are recited by the Hotar as well as discussion on the omitted mantras can be found in Staal (Staal et al., 1983: 680–686).

Chapter 5: Conclusions

This long scholastic journey has convincingly demonstrated the evolution of the Vedic Aśvins from their initially prominent position of the bridegrooms to Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, to the eventually downshifting role of wooers; thus, being displaced by Soma, who ascended onto a position of the Moon God. To investigate the shifting agency of the old IE celestial deities, the Aśvins, the following primary sources have been studied applying diachronic approach: RV and its ancillary texts, namely its two Brāhmaṇas, AitBr and KB, and their respective Śrauta Sūtras: ĀŚS and ŚŚS.

In order to give comprehensive and all-encompassing study on the subject of the Vedic mythological deities — the Aśvins, the following fields of research have been investigated at length: linguistic, comparative mythology within IE milieu, corresponding Vedic ritual and last but not least the astronomical dimension.

Firstly, the linguistic study on the notion and the epithets applied to the name of the Aśvins has yielded 13 most frequently used epithets out of 176 mentioned throughout RV, namely, 1) Aśvinau or Aśvinā — possessors of horses (449 mentions); 2) Dasrā — wonder-makers (52 mentions), often in combination with 3) Hiraṇyavartanī — golden-pathed (six mentions); 4) Nāsatyā — ‘rescuer, saviour’ or ‘true and not false’ (na-asatya) (102 mentions); 5) Divo Napātā — Heaven’s sons or grandsons (six mentions); 6) Mādhvī — honey-loving ones (16 mentions); 7) Madhupau — honey-drinkers; also, Madhupātāmā — the ones who drink honey most (two mentions; more mentions in connection with honey drinking); 8) Madhuvarṇā — honey-hued (two mentions); 9) Śubhas patī — lords of beauty (21 mentions); 10) Rudravartanī — the only ones called ‘the red pathed’ or else ‘of Rudra’s path’ or ‘of terrible [chariot] path’ (four mentions); 11) Parijmānā — going round [the earth] (three times), 12) Rudrā — Rudras ; the red ones; the terrible ones (four mentions); 13) Vṛṣaṇā — bulls (four mentions). The study on etymology has led to a preliminary conclusion that the proper name of these deities i.e., the Aśvins, is a derivative of the Sanskrit (Vedic) notion *aśvin* within IE geographical and linguistic area, and beyond its boundaries. The notion of which, in turn, might have developed from a hissing sound of the swift motion of a stone age weapon. Eventually, it might have then been projected to the swiftness of the horse-ride; and hence, a domesticized horse acquired its denomination containing such basic morphemes as: *-as/-aś*; *-asv/-aśv-*. Another argument in favour of this hypothesis is the fact that initially the notion was designated to a mare, which is well attested in many IE languages and throughout RV; particularly frequently mentioned

as a prize mare(s). This corroborates the fact that a wild mare was used at initial stages of domestication to augment or even sustain the herd of horses. Furthermore, the research on reconstructing the origin and spread of horse domestication has evidences of the strong domestication bottleneck in western central Eurasia that began ca. 6000 years ago, which, in turn, gives an approximate starting date for the development of the Sanskrit notion *aśvin* that eventually evolved into proto-Vedic twin deities — the *Aśvins* — ca. 4000 years ago. The earliest archaeological finds of lightweight spoked chariot wheels as described in RV were found in the burial mounds alongside the horse sacrifices in the Sintashta-Arkaim culture of the Volga steppes and the southern Urals ca. 2000 BCE. This technology then rapidly spread across IE language areas and beyond thus being conducive to the further development of the deification of the two-men chariot team. Hence, the newly emerging twinship cult that integrated multifaceted functions gradually developed into the so-called Dioskuric pattern that is well attested in the ancient Greek, Baltic, Vedic and other cultures across IE language area. As a rule, they are horse patrons, and they drive a chariot that brings the sun and sunlight to all the living beings, hence, these celestial deities are considered the divinities of Light. Their chariot is also associated and seen above the water bodies; they function as rescuers, helpers, and wonder makers. They usually have different fathers/parents; one of them is Heaven (father), the other — mortal; thus, they are called Sons of God/Heaven. They have a bride/sister — the Sun Maiden, and sister — Dawn; in some traditions the dimension of incest and polyandria is also present, namely, the twin brothers may be also depicted as suitors or husbands of the Sun Maiden who is typically their sister. It can be concluded that despite of *communis opinio* to consider the Dioskuric pattern to consist of a triad — the divine twins and Sun Maiden, the Vedic pattern rather demonstrates a quartet: the divine twins *Aśvins*, the Sun Maiden and Dawn. Of the similarities one can point out the presence of incestuous and/or polyandrous relationship that are attested in all three traditions. Bride kidnapping is explicit in the Greek and Baltic traditions with only indirect sources giving reports on practicing it in ancient India.

There are several typical features that are distinctive to the Dioskuric pattern and thus present in the Vedic twin deities: 1) dual paternity where one of the fathers is a celestial divinity; 2) they manifest different character traits; and thus, explicitly are responsible for different functional areas; 3) twice they are mentioned separately, namely — *Nāsatya* — grammatically it is expressed in singular. Thus, describing only one of the twins.

4) they have different parents: 1) Heaven (father) and The River Sindhu as their mother; 2) The Vivasvant (father) and Saranyū (mother); 4) the *Aśvins* themselves are fathers of the *Pūṣan*; 5)

both bear one name either in Sg. or in Du.; 6) they are immortal; 7) Uṣas (Dawn) is their sister and companion; 8) the Aśvins have a bride and consort — Sūryā — the Sun Maiden.

Although, the Aśvins are among the four most prominent deities lauded in RV, the origin of their cult that became localized in the Vedic ritual milieu was covered in mystery even to the Indian earliest commentator Yāska, and thus fostered the diversity of theories proposed by the Western scholars over more than 200 years. Thus, 11 theories were proposed until the turn of 1900s, and only two with the original insights in the 20th century.

Thus, Yāska, who lived ca. 500-700 BCE expressed four possible options on what Aśvins might have represented: 1) Heaven & Earth; 2) Day & Night; 3) the Sun & the Moon; 4) the two benevolent kings.

The Western scholarship on the matter of the Aśvins begins with the discovery of the Dioskuric pattern by Max Friedrich Müller in 1868. A thorough study of the Latvian and Lithuanian folk songs allows Wilhelm Mannhardt to conclude that the Baltic folk materials contain a well-preserved solar mythologeme that is cognate to the Greek and Vedic solar myths, which was then furthered and functioned as a foundation for the development of Comparative Mythology by Müller. In 1870 based on Yāska's assumptions, Rudolf von Roth concludes that in Yāska's view the Aśvins represent Indra and the Sun (ādityaḥ). The most favoured Morning/Evening Star hypothesis among scholars was brought into limelight by Mannhardt in 1875. In 1887 Leopold von Schroeder expresses conjecture that the Aśvins could represent the Moon who marries the Sun Maiden. Another popular theory suggested by Albrecht Weber in 1862 was that the Aśvins represent the star constellation known in the Western world as Gemini, namely the two stars: Castor & Pollux, which later, however, did not gain support. Whereas, both Theodor Goldstücker and Karl F. Geldner (1897) were of the opinion that initially they were humans, the famous warriors and healers who were divinized, purely of Indian origin; not representing any astronomical phenomena visible in the sky.

In the same year Hans Sofus Vodskov views the Aśvins as the Rain Gods. In his earlier writings, Mannhardt based on his research on the Latvian solar mythologeme, concluded that the evening twilight and the morning twilight, and therefore also the evening and the morning gloaming, appear as a coherent, unified phenomenon. Of similar views was Laurentios Myriantheus (1876); the same assumption is maintained by Edward Hopkins in 1895. In 1863 and later in 1887 Müller still maintains the idea that the two Aśvins as male deities represent light and darkness as well as temporality representing all that happens during the day. Concomitantly, Mannhardt also considered the Aśvins to represent a double apparition as evening and morning star. The Aśvins

as the Sun & Moon was propounded by Alfred Ludwig in 1876. Similar view is also shared by in the early work by Müller in 1869, and in 1889 by Edmund Hardy. In 1896 Theodor Baunack introduces another view — they represent the releasing of the Sun from darkness. Among the theories proposed from 1900s up to present day they most remarkable are the two by Paul Thieme in 1960 and Asko Parpola's 2004. Thus, In 1960 Paul Thieme convincingly demonstrates the affinity of *Mitrā-Varuṇā*, *Indraḥ*, *Nāsatyā* with a warrior cult also attested in Mitanni-Hatti treaties where these Aryan deities were mentioned as the guardians of a contract in exactly the same order.

An original and so far unnoticed perspective in the Aśvins' research quest was cast by Asko Parpola in his voluminous study that demonstrated determinately the Aśvins cult firstly had represented dual kingship of a deified two-man chariot team in the Sintashta-Arkaim culture of the Volga steppes and the southern Urals ca. 2000 BCE, which was eventually spread to Proto-Greeks, Proto-Balts and to the Proto-Finno-Ugrians of the mid-Volga and mid-Urals, who were ruled by a Proto-Aryan-speaking elite and most plausibly their initial functions as saviours and funeral gods. Toshifumi Gotō in 2006, synthesizes previous research results and maintains Hesperus-Lucifer theory.

This theory is also maintained and furthered on by the author of this study, namely, that the most viable theory for the origins of the Aśvins deification is the two apparitions of the planet Venus as the Morning and Evening Star phenomenon observable with naked eye at dawn, briefly before the sunrise or a few hours after the sunset. The investigation of the solar and lunar myths in their most archaic variants demonstrate early calendric observations of waning and waxing moon, and thus resurrection of time, lifting taboos on the harvest etc. Having examined the Aśvins, one of their characteristic *modus operandi* that emerged was their affinity with fecundity, which, in turn, led to a conclusion that originally the Vedic rituals to propitiate the Aśvins most plausibly were conducted in spring time, at around vernal equinox, which marked the beginning of the Vedic New Year.

There are 52 hymns in RV dedicated to the Aśvins by various Rigvedic sages or divine poets. Out of them 18 hymns involve the solar mythologeme, where Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, mounts the chariot of the Aśvins thus demonstrating her self-choice (*svayamvara*) by selecting them as her husbands. An in-depth study and analyses of RV hymns celebrating the Aśvins pertinent to the solar mythologeme has demonstrated that in great likelihood the marriage of the Aśvins to Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, describes a rather regular astronomic phenomenon that occurs two to five times annually i.e., as partial or total solar eclipse. A strong argument in favour of this view is grammatical analyses of RV hymn 4.43-45, where the poets laud the wedding of Sūryā to the

Aśvins using the verb in present tense, which overtly narrates the phenomenon that has once been eye-witnessed by the poets. The data on prehistoric solar eclipses that were observable in the Gandhāra region were obtained from the JavaScript solar eclipse explorer developed by NASA. Thus, the most spectacular and long lasting was the one that occurred exactly on vernal equinox, 21st March, 925 BCE, and lasted for 2 h 35 minutes, which is the most plausible candidate that marked the ontological turn and was immortalized as the wedding hymn RV 10.85. This dating i.e., 21st March as the best candidate for the original celebration of the Atirātra with its constituent Aś finds a solid foundation in Fritz Staal's field work, where Aś was recited on 12 April, 1975 from 2.30 A.M. until 6.30 A.M.

To sum it up, the Aśvins were depicted as the central actors in the solar mythologeme in the oldest layers of mythopoetics of RV. Namely, they were the bridegrooms of Sūryā. Whereas, in RV 10.85 they are downshifted by the Moon God, Soma, who has just ascended to this new position. In fact, the entire hymn consisting of 47 stanzas is a mythopoetic archetype of wedding, where sacred and profane realms, divine and mundane planes are artistically interwoven to set the role model for human beings. Alongside with that, the hymn contains a plethora of hints marking the beginning of a new era of the Vedic peoples; or, in fact, the ontological turn that has been documented in this hymn.

The study of RV has demonstrated that only allusions and glimpses of a well-known IE solar mythologeme were narrated by the poets. Conversely, the extended myth is narrated in AitBr, whereas KB is more instructive and concise in its nature, thus just providing merely a synopsis of the myth. In AitBr, the two Aśvins, although, possess this invocation *per se* and are the quasi-protagonists of the ritual scene, they take merely the role of wooers, with Soma as the bridegroom; as it was established in RV 10.85. The divine actors of the sacrificial ground are following: Agni, Uṣas, Indra, and the Aśvins, the two main deities who are propitiated throughout are the Sun God, Sūrya, and Agni, with the respective meters employed to bring prosperity and blessings to both the officiating priest — the Hotar and the commissioner of the sacrifice — Yajamāna. Alongside the main actors, there are also other deities that receive praises during this early morning ritual. Thus, the ritual is commenced by kindling a fire (Agni), who is the deity that conveys the fire oblations (clarified butter etc.) to the gods; then Uṣas is praised as a precursor of the sunrise; then Indra, followed by praises to Sūrya, to Dyaus and Pṛthvī; and it concludes with the propitiating of Bṛhaspati.

Aś of KB differs from AitBr not only with chronological sequence of the rites, but also in terms of the contents. It is mostly valuable for the reason it provides more details, when the ritual has to

be conducted, i.e., when Soma is in abundance, and also explicates on the meters employed and their functions. The beginning of paragraph 2 provides reasoning on the necessity to propitiate the respective deities: Agni — to obtain the world, Uṣas — to obtain the world of atmosphere, the Aśvins to obtain the yonder world, Sūrya — to obtain the fourth world of gods, the water, Indra by means of Pragāthas to obtain cattle and Bṛhaṭī to secure exhalation and inhalation i.e., life, and finally Bṛhaspatī to obtain support in life. Paragraphs 3-5 provide a very detailed explanation of the meters, number of verses, the exact timing for conclusion, namely, each constituent element or actor engaged in the ritual scene, and their respective functions.

Already in the poetical milieu of RV, a rather distinct dichotomy emerges between ritual and mythopoetic realms, namely, a sacrificial ground with a typical entourage of deities and arena of *purely* cosmological or astronomical events that employ another set of deities. Thus, *purely* cosmological are the poetical narratives of the divine wedding between Sūryā, the Sun Maiden, to divine twins — the Aśvins, or later on Soma, the Moon God in RV 10.85. In contrast, Uṣas, when lauded together with Agni and the Aśvins, most often is invoked to the sacrificial ground to bestow wealth, children, protection, and long life to the sacrificer. Nonetheless, there are a few exceptions, when the divine participants of both realms intersect within the boundaries of one hymn, however, even then their areas of responsibility are dichotomized rather distinctly. The same dichotomy is maintained in both the Brāhmaṇas. Another remarkable feature that distinguishes the social and kinship roles of Uṣas from Sūryā, is the self-choice that is expressed by mounting the chariot of husbands to be. Although, Uṣas has been depicted as the maiden who goes to *svayamvara* (RV 1.124.8; 1.121.2cd), she never mounts the chariot of Aśvins, it is only Sūryā who mounts their chariot as a bride.

The Śrauta Sūtra of a particular Veda provides instructions only for the priests of its tradition. Hence, the precepts conveyed in ĀŚS and ŚŚS are actually the guidelines for the Hotar.

Atirātra injunction is an overnight Soma sacrifice that culminates with AŚ is recited to grant prosperity pertaining to cattle and progeny of the Yajamāna. Atirātra is *ekāha*, but sometimes can be treated as *ahīna* i.e., the rite conducted for more than one day, and it commences a new day (more precisely a night), the fifth in succession, right after *Ṣoḍaśin*.

ĀŚS instructs the Hotar on how to perform AŚ in 25 sentences. ĀŚS being more closely affiliated to AitBr likewise is more descriptive on the spatial and physical movements of the Hotar within the sacrificial ground, which is the distinctive feature of AitBr and ĀŚS schools. Another distinction from ŚŚS is that the Hotar includes the refrain *svāhā* at the end of each propitiating mantra.

AŚ is described in Adhyāya 9 Kaṇḍikā 20.1-35 of ŚŚS, and it does not contain any details of the solar mythologem. The 35 sentences in which the AŚ is expounded contain only the hints in the form of concise quotes from the particular RV hymns.

Although, the Aśvins lost their prominent role as Sūryā's bridegrooms, and eventually were also excluded from Soma sacrifice as they were physicians to the gods, according to *Maitrāyaṇī Saṃhitā* 4.6.1 (Hillebrandt, 1891: 241; cf. Keith, 1998b: 114) and consequently AŚ is not present in *Mānava Śrautasūtra*. Similarly, AŚ has not been included in Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa that is ancillary to Śukla Yajurveda; however, AŚ is still present in Jaiminīya Brāhmaṇa.

Noteworthy is also to mention that currently there are 20 microfilmed manuscripts located in the libraries across India titled: *Aśvinaśastraprayoga*, *Āśvinaśastrakṛpti*, *Āśvinaśastra*, *Āśvinasahasra*, *Āśvinahrāsapakṣa* and more than 40 that contain Atirātra ritual. The fact is telling by itself as it confirms that this ritual was frequently performed that necessitated to continually reproduce ever new copies of the manuscripts. Hence, a further step would be to produce a new critical edition of the Atirātra/AŚ considering the available MSS.

Appendix 1: English translation of selected Ṛgveda hymns by Jamison & Brereton

- ¹ With these come to us right away and swiftly, o Aśvins. Heal what is ailing (Jamison & Brereton, 2014, p. 1072).
- ² Born separately, faultless, you two together have come to kinship with us (Ibid., 755).
- ³ Born (one) here, (one) there, the two have always bellowed together with (one) flawless body but with their own (multiple) names (Ibid., 384).
- ⁴ One of you is lauded as the victorious patron of the good battler, the other as the son of heaven dispensing a good portion⁴ (Ibid.).
- ⁵ (what) to the earth-circling (chariot) of the Nāsatyas, for it to appear? What will you say, Agni, to man-smiting Rudra? (Ibid., 562).
- ⁶ You two — come here to receive this (offering) of mine, Indra and Nāsatyas — as two gods joined in greatest delight with the gods today (Ibid., 1084).
- ⁷ (Here are) the two holy ones who quicken thought, who provided the goods to (the mare) Viśpalā, the sons of heaven whose commandments are bright for the good performer (of ritual) (Ibid., 385)
- ⁸ Who are wondrous, whose mother is the River Sindhu, who are mindful of riches — the gods finding goods through insight. (Ibid., 157)
- ⁹ They hid her away, the immortal, from the mortals. Having made a female of the same appearance, they gave her to Vivasvant. And she was carrying the Aśvins (in the womb), as it happened, and she left behind the two, the paired ones [=Yama and Yamī?]—Saranyū. (Ibid., 1398)
- ¹⁰ When, o Aśvins, you two drove with a three-wheeled (chariot) to the wedding of Sūryā to ask for her, all the gods then gave assent to you two. The son Pūṣan chose you as his two fathers. (Ibid., 1522)
- ¹¹ You descend to the movement of the steed of wide flight [=ritual fire], the one belonging to men, foremost at the sacrifice, when your sister [=Dawn] will bring you, o you welcomed by all [...] (Ibid., 382)
- ¹² After you slept, Ṛbhus, you asked this: “Who awakened us here, o Agohya?” The billy-goat [=the Sun?] said the dog [=the Moon?] was the awakener. Here today, after a year, you opened your eyes (Ibid., 343).
- ¹³ “And knowing of your origin, o you whose treasure is victory’s prize, find exhilaration according to the ritual sequences, o Ṛbhus. The exhilarating draughts have gathered for you, (as has) Plenitude. Send here a wealth of good heroes for us (Ibid., 613).
- ¹⁴ Three times (bring) good fortune and three times acclamations for us. The daughter of the Sun mounted your chariot with its three standing places (Ibid., 140).
- ¹⁵ The Daughter of the Sun mounted your chariot, like one winning the finish-line with her steed. All the gods approved in their hearts, and, Nāsatyas, you two keep company with her splendor (Ibid., 270).
- ¹⁶ Your chariot did the Daughter of the Sun choose, Nāsatyas, together with its splendor (Ibid., 274).
- ¹⁷ Having become pleased, the young girl, the Daughter of the Sun, has now mounted your chariot, o men (Ibid., 276).
- ¹⁸ I sweeten the hot milk; your help comes in return. Ūrjānī [=Sūryā] has mounted your chariot, Aśvins (Ibid., 277).
- ¹⁹ When, contending with each another, they have clashed with one another for beauty—(those) innumerable combatants, victorious in battle— then your chariot appears ever brighter in its steep descent, when you convey the patron according to his will, Aśvins (Ibid.).
- ²⁰ For the sake of your marvel [=your chariot], Aśvins, two voices guided the chariot harnessed by you and its (cargo?) belonging to the warrior band [? =the Aśvins]. Having come to marriage to you for a partnership with you, the noble young girl chose you two as her husbands. (Ibid.)
- ²¹ O Pūṣan, the two gods, the Nāsatyas, as if making arrows ready for glory, (made ready) the bridal procession of Sūryā. Your lead horses, born in the waters, zig-zag along the wagon-treks as if over the worn (surfaces) of the vast Varuṇa [=the sea?] (Ibid., 387).
- ²² What swift chariot with speeding horses do they say is the one that the Daughter of the Sun chose? (Ibid., 625).
- ²³ Your speedy vehicle has just appeared, with which you two become the masters [/husbands] of Sūryā (Ibid., 627).
- ²⁴ (the chariot) that conveys Sūryā, providing her a standing place, the best of many, whose team is hymns, the one seeking goods (Ibid., 628).
- ²⁵ Three bringing nourishment [=Aśvins and Sūryā] are upon it [=the chariot] as a pair; a fourth, a skin-bag, teems with honey (Ibid., 629).
- ²⁶ When Sūryā mounts your ever swift-running chariot, your ruddy birds keep its [=the sun’s] glowing heat from burning (Ibid., 755).
- ²⁷ For splendor the Daughter of the Sun mounted your chariot provided with hundredfold help, o you who offer much enjoyment (Ibid., 861).
- ²⁸ O Aśvins, your chariot swift as thought rises forth across the airy spaces, bringing hundredfold help,

- speeding to us, o you who bring Sūryā as goods (Ibid., 968).
- ²⁹ Clasp the bride to itself, your chariot presses upon the boundaries of heaven with its tracks (Ibid., 970).
- ³⁰ The young woman — the daughter of the Sun — chose your glory at the decisive turn (Ibid.).
- ³¹ When the maiden [=Sūryā] mounted your chariot (Ibid., 1045).
- ³² I have called here this most wondrous chariot for help today, the one that you mounted for Sūryā, o Aśvins easy to call, you who follow the course of the Rudras [=Maruts] — (Ibid., 1073).
- ³³ for whom you arrange that his chariot, along with his wife, will be in front, o Aśvins good to invoke, you who follow the course of the Rudras [=Maruts] (Ibid., 1441).
- ³⁴ Drive here with your chariot swifter than thought, which the Ṛbhus made for you, o Aśvins, and at whose hitching up the Daughter of Heaven [=Dawn] is born and both bright-lit day halves of Vivasvant (Ibid.).
- ³⁵ We have clasped it to ourselves like a dashing youth a maiden, holding it close like our own son who continues our lineage. (Ibid.)
- ³⁶ And this god, the conqueror of the world, Tvaṣṭar, in concert with the Wives (of the Gods), will speed the chariot — Idā, Bhaga, Bṛhaddivā, and Rodasī; Pūṣan, Plenitude—and the Aśvins as husbands (Ibid., 446).
- ³⁷ Journeying early in the morning like heroes in chariots, like twin goats you follow what you choose; (Beautifying your bodies) like exchange-wives beautifying their bodies, like a married couple (in the presence of the people) you find (a common) resolve in the presence of the peoples (Ibid., 458).
- ³⁸ With the birds these two wander, along with the one (woman). They go abroad like exiles. [=Aśvins and Sūryā] (Ibid., 1090).
- ³⁹ When your sister [=Dawn] will bring you, o you welcomed by all, and (the singer) solemnly invokes you for victory's prize and for refreshment, o honey-drinkers (Ibid., 382).
- ⁴⁰ The smooth-rolling chariot rolls on as it goes toward earth, when you stand on it, resolved to fortify (us). Let this hymn here accompany the wonder with wonderment; you keep company with Dawn, the Daughter of Heaven (Ibid., 386).
- ⁴¹ The milk-cow [=Dawn?] is yielding the desirable milk of the age-old (semen); the son [=Agni] of the priestly gift acts as go-between. She whose course is beautiful carries brightness here; the praise song of Dawn has awakened the Aśvins (Ibid., 548).
- ⁴² Agni shines toward the face of Dawn. The words of inspired poets, traveling to the gods, have arisen (Ibid., 759).
- ⁴³ I have woken up with the goddess [=Dawn], simultaneously with my speech for the Aśvins (Ibid. 1048).
- ⁴⁴ Wake up the Aśvins, o Dawn — (wake them) up, o goddess, liberal and great, (wake them) up in due order, o The Hotar of the sacrifice [=Agni]. (Wake) up lofty fame for our exhilaration (Ibid.).
- ⁴⁵ When, o Dawn, you drive with your radiant beam, you shine together with the sun (Ibid.).
- ⁴⁶ With Agni, Indra, Varuṇa, and Viṣṇu, with the Ādityas, the Rudras, and the Vasus, in concert with Dawn and the Sun, drink the soma, o Aśvins (Ibid., 1101).
- ⁴⁷ Dawn has become the companion of the Aśvins (Ibid., 637).
- ⁴⁸ You are both the companion of the Aśvins, and you are also mother of cows (Ibid.).
- ⁴⁹ Agni has looked toward the vanguard of the Dawns—benevolent (Agni) toward the treasure-conferring of the radiant (Dawns). Drive, Aśvins, to the dwelling of the one of good action. The Sun, the god, goes up with his light (Ibid., 575).
- ⁵⁰ Jointly with all the gods, jointly with the Aśvins, with Dawn, drive hither, Agni. Take pleasure in the pressed soma, as (you did) at Atri's (Ibid., 726).
- ⁵¹ Upon Dadhikrā as the first, upon the Aśvins and Dawn, upon the kindled Agni and Bhaga, do I call for your sake for help (Ibid., 939).
- ⁵² you stole the wheel from the Sun, o Indra (Ibid., 604).
- ⁵³ And when for the mortal you let the Sun slip (Ibid.).
- ⁵⁴ That you smote a woman, the evilly angry daughter of Heaven (Ibid.).
- ⁵⁵ The daughter of Heaven: though she was honored as great, you, the great, crushed Dawn completely (Ibid.).
- ⁵⁶ Dawn ran away in fear from her cart, which was completely crushed, when the bull jabbed it down (Ibid.).
- ⁵⁷ This cart of hers lies, very completely crushed, here at the Vipāś (River). She has run into the far distance (Ibid.).
- ⁵⁸ When is the yoking of the prizewinning donkey, with which, Nāsatyas, you drive up to the sacrifice (Ibid., 140).
- ⁵⁹ The two fallow bays (of Indra) and the two dappled mares (of the Maruts) have become your yokemates. The prizewinning (horse) has taken his place at the chariot-pole of the (Aśvins') donkey (Ibid., 346).
- ⁶⁰ And the thousand chants, which (are performed?) at the quest for cattle—drive up to all those, to drink (the soma) (Ibid., 1140).
- ⁶¹ (With it) come here near to us with your thousands of cattle and horses (Ibid., 1169).
- ⁶² Do not overlook us with your thousands of cattle and horses (Ibid.).
- ⁶³ Hitch the donkey to the chariot whose parts are solid, o you who bring bullish goods (Ibid., 1183).

-
- ⁶⁴ You sent the smoke for him [=Namuci] down even on the two of the same name [=Aśvins]; you smashed (him) down, Indra, like the cart of Dawn (Ibid., 1503).
- ⁶⁵ When his wheel was sunk down in the waters. And that should seem just honey to him (Ibid.).
- ⁶⁶ By reality is the earth propped up; by the sun is heaven propped up. By truth do the Ādityas stand, and Soma is fixed in heaven (Ibid., 1521).
- ⁶⁷ When they take their first drink of you, god, after that you swell up again.
Vāyu is the guardian of Soma. The moon is the model of the years (Ibid., 1522).
- ⁶⁸ The praise songs were the crossbars, meter the veil and headdress.
The Aśvins were the wooers of Sūryā and Agni was the leader (Ibid.).
- ⁶⁹ Soma was the bridegroom; the Aśvins were both wooers, when Savitar gave Sūryā to her husband, as she pronounced (her vow) with her (whole) mind (Ibid.).
- ⁷⁰ When, o Aśvins, you two drove with a three-wheeled (chariot) to the wedding of Sūryā to ask for her, all the gods then gave assent to you two. The son Pūṣan chose you as his two fathers (Ibid.).
- ⁷¹ When you drove, you two lords of beauty, to Sūryā to woo her, where was your single wheel; where did you stand for the pointing out? (Ibid.).
- ⁷² A thousand-rayed [chariot], the acquirer of hundreds of riches. Obedient and bestowing vastness towards the enjoyment [of oblation] (Ibid., 277).

Appendix 2: English translation of the selected excerpts by the author
Solar mythologeme in Aitareya Brāhmaṇa IV.17.7-9

Translator's Note

The principal source I have relied on is the critical edition by Theodor Aufrecht (Aufrecht, 1879: 99–101).

The translation produced is as literal as grammatically and stylistically possible. In order to render the text in a readable and easy to perceive fluent contemporary speech, I have used square brackets to indicate the divine or profane actor of the ritual scene, when only pronouns or other allusions are used by the ancient authors. Similarly, parts of speech that have been implied in a concise manner, but not expressively stated, I have deciphered, and thus written them in square brackets.

Pañcikā IV. Adhyāya 17.

Khaṇḍa 7

**Prajāpatir vai Somāya⁵⁶ rājñe duhitaram prāyachat⁵⁷ (sic) Sūryāṃ Sāvitrīṃ tasyai sarve
devā varā āgachams, tasyā etat sahasraṃ vahatum anvākarod yad etad āśvinam ity
ācakṣate; 'nāśvinam haiva tad yad arvāksahasraṃ, tasmāt tat sahasraṃ vaiva śamsed
bhūyo vā / (17.7.1.)**

Verily Prajāpati bestowed Savitar's daughter Sūryā to Soma, the king; for her all the gods came as groomsmen. For her wedding he gave [as a bridal gift] this thousand [of verses], which they call Aśvina [śastra/invocation]. That is indeed not Aśvina [śastra], which is less than a thousand [verses], therefore he should recite either this thousand or more.

**prāśya ghr̥taṃ śamsed yathā ha vā idam ano vā ratho vākto vartata, evaṃ haivākto vartate
/ (17.7.2)**

After having consumed clarified butter, he should recite; indeed, just as this wedding cart or a chariot goes [well, when] smeared [with grease], in this very manner verily he goes [well, when] smeared [with grease].

⁵⁶ There is a typo in TITUS, *Somāyā*; cf. Aufrecht (1879).

⁵⁷ This must be either a scribal mistake or a typing mistake of a publisher, as the correct form is *prāyacchat*; cf. Aufrecht (1879); consequently the same mistake is found in TITUS; see: <https://titus.fkidg1.uni-frankfurt.de/texte/etcs/ind/aind/ved/rv/ab/ab.htm> [Accessed on 25 May, 2023].

śakunir ivotpatiṣyann āhvayīta / (17.7.3)

He should summon [hither] as if a bird [which is] about to fly up⁵⁸.

tasmin devā na samajānata: mamedam astu mamedam astv iti.

te saṃjānānā abruvann: ājim asyāyāmahai sa yo na ujeṣyati, tasyedam bhaviṣyatīti te

'gner evādhi gr̥hapater Ādityaṃ kāṣṭhāṃ akurvata,

tasmād āgneyī pratipad bhavaty āśvīnasyāgnir hotā gr̥hapatih sa rājeti / (17.7.4)

In that the gods were in disagreement with each other; [and they said]: “Let this be mine, let this be mine.” They having come into an agreement said: “Let us run the prize-race for it; he who wins our [prize], his will be this [prize].” “They made a course from this very Agni, [who is] a householder from above, to the sun; therefore, [that part] belonging to Agni is the beginning; Agni is the Hotar [and] the householder in Āśvina [śastra], he [is] the king”.

tad dhaika āhur: agnim manye pitaram agnim āpim ity etayā pratipadyeta / (17.7.5)

Thus, some have said: “Agni, I think, [is] a father, Agni [is] a friend,” with this [Agni’s part] he should begin.

divi śukraṃ yajataṃ sūryasyeti prathamayaiva ṛcā kāṣṭhāṃ āpnotīti / (17.7.6)

In the heaven, the brightness of the sun is worshipped, with [this] very first verse he reaches the goal.

tattan nādr̥tyaṃ ya enaṃ tatra brūyād: agnim-agnim iti vai pratyapādy, agnim āpatsyatīti,

śāsvat tathā syāt / (17.7.7)

Whosoever [said that] is not to be regarded, in that case, he should tell him [the Hotar]: [by propitiating verse to] “Agni [again and again] Agni” it was commenced, in that manner, should it happen continuously, he [the Hotar] will fall into fire [Agni]⁵⁹.

tasmād: agnir hotā gr̥hapatih sa rājeti etayaiva pratipadyeta; gr̥hapativatī prajātimatī

śāntā, sarvāyuh sarvāyutvāya / (17.7.8)

Therefore: “Agni [is] the Hotar [and] householder, he [is] the king,” with this very [Agni’s verse] he should begin; [Agni’s verse] contains [its quality as] as a householder, generative power, which is pacifying [fire], whose living is full for the fullness of life⁶⁰.

⁵⁸ “He then sits down behind his Dhishnya (sic *dhiṣṇya*; fire-place) in a peculiar posture, representing an eagle who is just about flying up. He draws up his two legs, puts both his knees close to each other, and touches the earth with his toes. I saw a priest, who had once repeated the Āśvina Śastra (there are scarcely more than half a dozen Brahmans living all over India who actually have repeated it), make the posture with great facility, but I found it didicult to imitate it well” (Haug, 1863b, p. 268).

⁵⁹ Cf. Keith (1920); cf. Haug (1863).

⁶⁰ Full life in Vedic cosmology implies 100 years.

sarvam āyur eti ya evaṃ veda / (17.7.9)

He attains a full life, who knows thus.

Khaṇḍa 8

**tāsāṃ vai devatānām ājīm dhāvāntīnām abhisṛṣṭānām Agnir mukham prathamah
pratyapadyata; tam Aśvināv anvāgachatām, tam abrūtām: apodihi, āvāṃ vā idam jeṣyāva
iti. sa tathety abravīt, tasya vai mamehāpyastv iti; tatheti; tasmā apy atrākurutām, tasmād
āgneyam āśvine śasyate / (18.8.1)**

[Among] these deities running the prize-race, [who] surrendered, [so that] Agni reached first to the front; the two Aśvins followed, [and] said to him: “Go away, we two will win it.” He [Agni], said: “Be it so,” “Kindly let then me have a [share] of yours here.” “Be it so,” [said the Aśvins]. For him [Agni] also they made a [share] here; therefore, a part to Agni is recited in Aśvina [śāstra].

**tā Uṣasam anvāgachatām, tām abrūtām: apodihi, āvāṃ vā idam jeṣyāva iti. sā tathety
abravīt, tasyai vai mamehāpyastv iti. tatheti. tasyā apy atrākurutām, tasmād uṣasyam
āśvine śasyate / (17.8.2)**

They both [the Aśvins] followed Uṣas, [and] said to her: “Go away, we two will win it.” She [Uṣas], said: “Be it so,” “Kindly let then me have a [share] of yours here.” “Be it so,” [said the Aśvins]. For her [Uṣas] also they made a [share] here: therefore, [a part] to Uṣas is recited in Aśvina [śāstra].

**tāv Indram anvāgachatām, tam abrūtām: āvāṃ vā idam maghavañ jeṣyāva iti. na ha taṃ
dadhr̥ṣatur apodihīti vaktuṃ. sa tathety abravīt, tasya vai mamehāpyastv iti. tatheti. tasmā
apy atrākurutām, tasmād aindram āśvine śasyate / (17.8.3)**

They both [the Aśvins] followed Indra, [and] said to him: “we two, o bountiful [Indra] will win it.” They did not dare to tell [him] “Go away.” He [Indra], said: “Be it so,” “Kindly let then me have a [share] of yours here.” “Be it so,” [said the Aśvins]. For him [Indra] also they made a [share] here: therefore, [a part] to Indra is recited in Aśvina [śāstra].

**tad Aśvinā udajayatām, Aśvināv āśnuvātām. yad Aśvinā udajayatām Aśvināv āśnuvātām,
tasmād etad āśvinam ity ācakṣate / (17.8.4)**

The Aśvins won it [the prize-race], the Aśvins obtained [the prize]; which [prize-race] the Aśvins won [that prize] the Aśvins obtained; therefore, [people] call it Aśvina [śāstra].

'śnute yad-yat kāmāyate ya evaṃ veda / (17.8.5)

He obtains [for himself] whatever he desires, who knows thus.

**tad āhur: yac chasyata āgneyam śasyata uśasyam śasyata aindram: atha kasmād etad
āśvinam ity ācakṣata ity. Aśvinau hi tad udajayatām, Aśvināv āśnuvātām. yad Aśvinā
udajayatām Aśvināv āśnuvātām, tasmād etad āśvinam ity ācakṣate / (17.8.6)**

Thus, some have said: “which is recited to Agni, [which] is recited to Uśas, [which] is recited to Indra, why then it is called Aśvina [śastra]?” Because the Aśvins won it [the prize-race], the Aśvins obtained it [the prize], which the Aśvins won, [which] the Aśvins obtained; therefore, this is called Aśvina [śastra].

'śnute yad-yat kāmayate ya evam veda / (17.8.7)

He obtains [for himself] whatever he desires, who knows thus.

Khaṇḍa 9

**aśvatarīrathenāgnir ājim adhāvat, tāsām prājamāno yonim akūlayat, tasmāt tā na
vijāyante / (17.9.1)**

Agni ran the prize-race with a she-mule drawn chariot; while driving forward, he [Agni] burnt their womb(s); therefore, they [she-mules] do not beget.

**gobhir aruṇair Uśā ājim adhāvat, tasmād Uśasy āgatāyām aruṇam ivaiva prabhāty, Uśaso
rūpam / (17.9.2)**

Uśas ran the prize-race with the ruddy bulls; therefore, when Uśas (Dawn) came, it shine(d) forth [with] ruddy [colour] exactly as [is] the colour of dawn.

**aśvarathenendra ājim adhāvat, tasmāt sa uccairghoṣa upabdimān kṣatrasya rūpam, aindro
hi sa / (17.9.3)**

Indra ran the prize-race with a horse drawn chariot; therefore, the intense roaring, the noise — that [is] the characteristic of power, because that belongs to Indra.

**gardabharathenāśvinā udajayatām, Aśvināv āśnuvātām; yad Aśvinā udajayatām Aśvināv
āśnuvātām, tasmāt sa sṛtajavo dughdohah, sarveṣām etarhi vāhanānām anāśiṣṭho;
retasas tv asya vīryam nāharatām, tasmāt sa dviretā vājī / (17.9.4)**

The Aśvins won with a donkey drawn chariot; the Aśvins obtained [it]; which [prize-race] the Aśvins won that [prize] the Aśvins obtained; therefore, nowadays, it [the donkey] is [the one] whose swiftness is gone [and] whose milk is milked out; from all the draught animals it is the slowest; however, they [the Aśvins] did not take away the virility of his semen; therefore, it [is] potent [with] two kinds of semen⁶¹.

⁶¹ What the ancient author perhaps implied was that a domesticated donkey was easily crossbred with a horse; and thus, they could impregnate both a female ass and a mare. Although, they were slow and did not yield human edible milk, they were very

**tad āhuḥ: sapta sauryāṇi chandāṃsi śaṃsed, yathaivāgneyaṃ yathoṣasyaṃ yathāśvinam;
sapta vai⁶², devalokāḥ, sarveṣu devalokeṣu rādhnotīti / (17.9.5)**

Then, they have said: “He should recite [in] seven meters [or: hymns] to Sūrya, just as to Agni, just as to Uṣas, just as to the Aśvins; indeed, seven are the worlds of gods, in all the worlds of gods he is successful.

**tattan nādr̥tyaṃ; trīṇy eva śaṃset; trayo vā ime trivṛito⁶³ (sic) lokā, eṣām eva lokānām
abhijityai / (17.9.6)**

Whosoever [said that] is not to be regarded; merely three [hymns; or: meters] he [the Hotar] should recite; indeed, three are these, the threefold worlds; for being victorious in these very worlds.

tad āhur: ud u tyam jātavedasam⁶⁴ iti sauryāṇi pratipadyeteti / (17.9.7)

Then, they have said: “Further up [take] this Jātavedas⁶⁵ [all-knowing; Agni],” he [the Hotar] should begin [with a part] to Sūrya.

tat-tan nādr̥tyaṃ; yathaiva gatvā kāṣṭhām aparādhnyāt, tādr̥k tat / (17.9.8)

Whosoever [said that] is not to be regarded; thereby that [is] as if having gone [to the goal] he would miss the goal.

**sūryo no divas pātv ity etenaiva pratipadyeta; yathaiva gatvā kāṣṭhām abhipadyeta, tādr̥k
tad / (17.9.9)**

“Let Sūrya protect us from the sky,” with this [verse] he should begin; thereby that [is] as if having gone [to the goal] he would seize the goal.

ud u tyam jātavedasam iti dvitīyaṃ śaṃsati / (17.9.10)

“Further up [take] this god Jātavedas,” — [this] he recites [as] the second.

**citraṃ devānām ud agād anīkam⁶⁶ iti traiṣṭubham; asau vāva citraṃ devānām udeti,
tasmād etac chaṃsati / (17.9.11)**

potent. “Just as donkeys don't seem to care who's in their herd, they also don't seem to be picky about who they breed with. In addition to other donkeys, they will breed with horses and zebras, producing hybrid offspring. A jack that mates with a female horse will produce an animal called a mule, while a jenny and a male horse produce a hinny, according to the University of Miami. When a zebra and a donkey mate, the result is called a zebroid, zonkey or zeedonk. Hybrids are almost always sterile and cannot produce offspring of their own” (Bradford, 2022).

⁶² There is a typing mistake in TITUS.

⁶³ There is a typing mistake in Auftrecht's edition (1879); the correct variant is *trivṛto*.

⁶⁴ This is a quote from RV 1.50.1a. Stanzas 1-9 of this hymn are addressed to Sūrya.

ud u tyam jātavedasam devam vahanti keṭavaḥ |

dr̥śe viśvāya sūryam ||

O rays of light, further up take this god Jātavedas,

For all [can] see the sun. (Hereinafter, all unquoted translations are conducted by the author; cf. Jamison & Brereton (2014).

⁶⁵ Jātavedas — all-knowing, also a frequently used epithet to address Agni in RV.

⁶⁶ This is a quote from RV 1.115.1.

[With this verse] composed in Triṣṭubh “The bright face of the gods has arisen”; assuredly, the yonder [Sun] rises up the brightness of the gods; therefore, he recites this [to the sun].

**namo mitrasya varuṇasya cakṣasa⁶⁷ iti jāgataṃ; tad v āśīḥpadam, āśīṣam evaitenāśāsta
ātmane ca yajamānāya ca / (17.9.12)**

[With this verse] composed in Jagatī meter “Obeisance to the eye of Mitra [and] Varuṇa”; that now [is] the line of a stanza containing the blessing, indeed the blessing by it [the line] he desires for himself and for the Yajamāna [the commissioner].

*cītram devānām ud agād anīkaṃ cakṣur mītrasya varuṇasyāgneḥ |
āprā dyāvāpṛthivī antarikṣam sūrya'ātmā jagatas taṣthuṣaś ca ||*

⁶⁷ This is a quote from RV 10.37.1.

*namo' mītrasya varuṇasya cakṣaṣe maḥo devāya tad ṛtam saparyata |
dūredṛṣe' devajātāya keṭave' divas puṭrāya sūryāya śamsata ||*

Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇa, Adhyāya 18, Khaṇḍa 1

Translator's Note

The principal two sources I have relied on are the critical edition by an Indian Indologist E.R. Sreekrishna Sarma (Sreekrishna Sarma, 1968: 84) that is also available online by Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL) (*Kauṣītakibrāhmaṇa*, 2020) and Bruno Lindner (Lindner, 1887); the secondary source is the text input in the IAST by GRETIL, which I have critically verified against the Sarma's edition. In order to compare and verify the translation, I have consulted the English translations by Arthur Berriedale Keith (Keith, 1920: 444–445).

The translation produced is as literal and as grammatically and stylistically possible. In order to make the text and its context more comprehensible for the contemporary reader, I have used square brackets to indicate the divine or profane actor of the ritual scene, when only pronouns or other allusions are used by the ancient authors; or else inserted other relevant information that has been omitted by the author, and yet meant implicitly. Similarly, parts of speech that have been implied in a concise manner, but not expressively stated, I have deciphered, and thus written them in square brackets.

atirikta somo vā⁶⁸ eṣa yad āśvinam / (18.1.1)

Soma [is] indeed in a surplus, when [there is] this Aśvina [invocation].

yad vai yajñasya atiricyate / (18.1.2)

Indeed, when the deprivation of the sacrifice is surpassed.

bhrātr̥vyas⁶⁹ tena yajamānasya pratyudyamī bhavati / (18.1.3)

By [help of] that [sacrifice/Soma] the rival of Yajamāna counterbalances [him].

Atha yat parastād aśvinau yajati / (18.1.4)

Now, because of that, hereafter he sacrifices to both Aśvins.

Aśvinau vai devānām bhiṣajau / (18.1.5)

The two Aśvins indeed are the physicians of the gods.

bhaiṣajyam eva tat kurute / (18.1.6)

This very remedy ceremony then he prepares [for himself].

Atha yatra ha tat savitā sūryāṃ prāyacchat somāya rājñe / (18.1.7)

Now, on this occasion then Savitar gave [his daughter] Sūryā to Soma, the king.

⁶⁸ There is typing mistake in GRETIL, cf. Lindner (1887); cf. Sreekrishna Sarma (1968).

⁶⁹ There is typing mistake in Sreekrishna Sarma's edition (1968), *bhātr̥vyas* (*sic*); cf. Lindner (1887).

Yadi vā prajāpateḥ / (18.1.8)

Or as if [she was] Prajāpati's

Tat sahasram anvākarod duhitra ūhyamānāyai / (18.1.9)

This thousand [of verses] he [Savitar] gave as a bridal gift for the daughter who was being carried away for a marriage.

tad āsāṃ devatānām āsīt / (18.1.10)

It was in the possession of these deities.

Tā abruvann ājim āyāma asmint sahasra iti / (18.1.11)

They [deities] said: “Let us run a prize-race for this thousand.”

Tā ājim āyan / (18.1.12)

[And] they ran the race.

Tasmād bahvyo devatāḥ śasyante / (18.1.14)

Therefore, many deities are praised.

Atha āśvinam ity ākhyāyate / (18.1.15)

Now, [it] is named Aśvina [śastra].

tata u ha etad uta rāsabho na sarvam iva javaṃ dhāvati / (18.1.16)

And for this reason, now, this donkey does not run as swiftly as everyone else.

Sṛtam mayā iti hataṃ manyamānaḥ sahasraṃ śaṃset / (18.1.17)

“I have run [the race]”, thinking to himself [said] the exhausted [donkey]; [therefore]: “a

thousand he should recite”.

sahasram hy udajayatām / (18.1.18)⁷⁰

For a thousand they both [Aśvins] won.

⁷⁰ Here ends Kaṇḍā 1 in Keith (1920), Lindner (1887); cf. Sreekrishna Sarma (1968), in his edition there are 27 sentences.

Adhyāya 9 Kaṇḍikā 20.1-35 of the Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra

Translator's Note

The principal two sources I have relied on are the critical edition by Alfred Hillebrandt (Hillebrandt 1888, 1:101–102) and the commentary on Āśvina Śastra by *Varadattasuta Ānartīya* in the third volume of Hillebrandt's edition (Hillebrandt 1897, 3:16–21); the secondary source is the text input in the IAST by Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL) (*Śāṅkhāyanaśrautasūtra*, 2020), which I have critically verified against the Hillebrandt's edition. Nevertheless, I have adopted GRETIL's division of the sentences as it is more suitable and more logical to begin Kaṇḍikā 20 (the sub-chapter) of Adhyāya (Chapter) 9 with “samsthāpya rātri paryāyān”. Whereas, in the Hillebrandt's edition this sentence belongs to Kaṇḍikā 19. In order to compare and verify the translation, I have consulted the reprint of Willem Caland's English translation (Caland 1980, 240–244), which was first published post mortem by Lokesh Chandra in 1953. Unfortunately, Caland's notes on many of his translations in *Kleine Schriften* series (M. Witzel, 1990) does not reveal anything related to the selected passages of ŚŚS.

The translation produced is as literal and as grammatically and stylistically possible. In order to make the text and its context more comprehensible for the contemporary reader, I have used square brackets to indicate the divine or profane actor of the ritual scene, when only pronouns or other allusions are used by the ancient authors; or else inserted other relevant information that has been omitted by the author, and yet meant implicitly. Similarly, parts of speech that have been implied in a concise manner, but not expressively stated, I have deciphered, and thus written them in square brackets.

samsthāpya rātriparyāyān āśvināya stoṣyamāṇeṣu pravṛtāhuṭī juhoti / (9.20.1)

Having made the night-rounds accomplished, when they [the chanters of Sāmaveda] are about to praise for the invocation of the Āśvins, he [the Hotar] sacrifices two butter oblations for the choosing [of two Adhvaryu priests].

samaya vācā śamset / (9.20.2)

He [the Hotar] should recite in an even voice.

uttarottariṇyā vā / (9.20.3)

Or with increasingly higher [voice].

yaḥ prātaranuvākastadāśvinam / (9.20.4)

The invocation of the Aśvins is that one, which is recited early in the morning.

tasya vikāraṃ⁷¹ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ / (9.20.5)

We will explain its modification.

yathāchandasaṃ⁷² śāstram / (9.20.6)

[It is] just like a praise of the sacred text [of the Veda].

bārhatīnāṃ⁷³ pratipadāṃ⁷⁴ prathamamprathamam⁷⁵ pragātham⁷⁶ punarādāyam⁷⁷

kakupkāram / (9.20.7)

[The Hotar] repeats the first triplet stanza of the introductory parts in the Bṛhatī meter, [and then] again undertaking the hymn in the Kakubh [meter].

agnirhotā gr̥hapatiriti⁷⁸ pratipadāporevatīmuddhṛtya / (9.20.8)

“Agni is the the Hotar [and] householder,” [this is] an introductory stanza, having excluded “abundant water⁷⁹.”

caturdaśa gāyatrāduddharati / (9.20.9)

He [the Hotar] excludes fourteen from [the hymns composed] in the Gāyatrī metre.

ānuṣṭubhāddve / (9.20.10)

From [the hymns composed] in the the Anuṣṭubh metre — [he excludes] two.

traiṣṭubhātrayodaśam⁸⁰ śatam / (9.20.11)

From [the hymns composed] in the Triṣṭubh metre — [he excludes] one hundred and thirteen.

nityāni kākṣīvatānyāgastyāni ca / (9.20.12)

The [hymns] composed by Kakṣīvat and Agastya [are] the obligatory ones.

⁷¹ There is a typing mistake in GRETEL; missing *anusvāra*.

⁷² See note No. 81.

⁷³ There is a typing mistake in GRETEL; missing *anusvāra*.

⁷⁴ See note No. 83.

⁷⁵ See note No. 83.

⁷⁶ See note No. 83.

⁷⁷ See note No. 83.

⁷⁸ This is a quote from RV 6.15.13.

agnir hotā gr̥hapatīḥ sa rājā viśvā veda janimā jātavedāḥ |
devānām ūta yo martyānām yajīṣṭhaḥ sa pra yajatām ṛtāvā ||

⁷⁹ This phrase “āpo revatīḥ”, strangely enough is present in RV 10.30.8d and 10.30.12a.

⁸⁰ See note No. 83.

prathamam⁸¹ tu kākṣīvatam⁸² śastvā kārādhaddhotriyā^{83 84} nava / (9.20.13)

But having recited first [the hymns] composed by Kakṣīvat, he shall perform the nine, which belong to the the Hotar.

ūrdhvamāgastyebhyastrīśatam suparṇam / (9.20.14)

After [the hymns] composed by Agastya [he recites] one hundred and three Suparṇa [stanzas].

anyāsām⁸⁵ vā āśvinīnām⁸⁶ tāvat / (9.20.15)

Or other ones in the same number addressed to the Aśvins.

samidhaścidityi⁸⁷ tisra uddharati / (9.20.16)

“Even [when] enkindled,” he excludes three [stanzas from this hymn].

ayam⁸⁸ vām⁸⁹ madhumattama ity⁹⁰aṣṭau yathāsthānam / (9.20.17)

“This most honey-filled [Soma] for both of you,” [the Hotar recites] eight [stanzas] as [it] stands [by the tradition].

ekādaśauṣṇihāt / (9.20.18)

From [the hymns composed] in the Uṣṇih metre [he excludes] eleven.

tathāgneyājḡatāt / (9.20.19)

The same [number] from [the hymns] related to Agni composed in the Jagatī metre.

uttamena pāṅktena pādena udayam⁹¹ kāṅkṣet / (9.20.20)

With the most excellent Pāda composed in the Paṅkti metre he would wait for the rising [of the sun].

⁸¹ See note No. 83.

⁸² See note No. 83.

⁸³ Special Sandhi rule is applicable here; see § 163 in (Whitney, 1950, p. 56).

⁸⁴ hotriya — the correct spelling.

⁸⁵ See note No. 83.

⁸⁶ See note No. 83.

⁸⁷ This is a quote from RV. 10.150.1

samidhaś cīt sam idhyase devebhyo' havyavāhana |
ādityai rudrair vasubhir na ā gahi mṛṅkāya' na ā gahi ||

⁸⁸ See note No. 83.

⁸⁹ See note No. 83.

⁹⁰ This is a quote from RV 1.47.1.

ayam vām madhumattamaḥ suṭaḥ soma' rtāvṛdhā |
tam aśvinā pibatam tīroahnyam dhattam ratnāni dāśuṣe' ||

⁹¹ See note No. 83.

udite sauryāṇi / (9.20.21)

When [the sun] has risen, [he recites the hymns] addressed to the sun.

udu tyam⁹² jātavedasamiti⁹³ nava / (9.20.22)

“Further up [take] this Jātavedas,” [the Hotar recites first] nine [stanzas].

citraṃ⁹⁴ devānām⁹⁵ / (9.20.23)

“The bright [face] of the gods”.

namo mitrasya⁹⁶ / (9.20.24)

“Obeisance to [the eye] of Mitra”

indra kratumiti⁹⁷ pragāthaḥ / (9.20.25)

“O Indra, [bring your] intention,” [the Hotar recites this] triplet stanza.

mahī dyauriti⁹⁸ tisraḥ / (9.20.26)

“[Let] the two great ones, Heaven [and Earth, mix this sacrifice for us],” [the Hotar recites] three [stanzas].

viśvasya devī mṛṣayasya⁹⁹ (sic) janmano na yā roṣāti na grabha¹⁰⁰ iti¹⁰¹ dvipadā / (9.20.27)

“The goddess of everything, of mortal beings, who shall not be enraged with [us], nor seize us [for the destruction],” [the Hotar recites] a stanza consisting of two Pādas.

⁹² See note No. 83.

⁹³ This is a quote from RV 1.50.1. Stanzas 1-9 of this hymn are addressed to Sūrya.

ud u tyam jātavedasam devam vahanti keṭavaḥ |
dṛśe viśvāya sūryam ||

O rays of light, further up take this god Jātavedas,

For all [can] see the sun. (Hereinafter, all unquoted translations are conducted by the author; cf. Jamison & Brereton (2014).

⁹⁴ See note No. 83.

⁹⁵ This is a quote from RV 1.115.1.

citraṃ devānām ud agād anīkaṃ cakṣur mītrasya varuṇasyāgneḥ |
āprā dyāvāpṛthivī antarikṣam sūrya ātmā jagatas taṣthusāś ca ||

⁹⁶ This is a quote from RV 10.37.1.

namo mītrasya varuṇasya cakṣāse maḥo devāya tad ṛtam saparyata |
dūredṛśe devajātāya keṭave divas puṭrāya sūryāya śamsata ||

⁹⁷ This is a quote from RV 7.32.26.

indra kratum na ā bhāra pītā puṭrebhyo yathā |
śikṣā no aśmin puruhūta yāmani jīvā jyotir aśimahi ||

⁹⁸ This is a quote from RV 1.22.13

mahī dyauḥ pṛthivī ca na imam yajñam mimikṣatām |
pipṛtām no bhārimabhiḥ ||

Let the great ones, Heaven and Earth, mix this sacrifice for us.

Let them carry us through with their support. (Jamison & Brereton, 2014, p. 115)

⁹⁹ mṛcayasya.

¹⁰⁰ Irregular Sandhi.

¹⁰¹ This is a slightly corrupted quote from AitBr Pañcīkā IV, Adhyāya 17, Khaṇḍa.10.14
viśvasya devī mṛcayasya janmano na yā roṣāti na grabhad iti dvipadām śamsati | 14 |

br̥haspate¹⁰² ati yadaryo arhāditi¹⁰³ paridadhāti / (9.20.28)

“O Br̥haspati, that which will be made beyond the worth of an enemy,” he concludes [with this stanza].

pratipade cāhāvaḥ paridhānīyāyai ca / (9.20.29)

“Let us two invoke¹⁰⁴ [says the Hotar to Adhvaryu],” for the beginning [stanza] and for the concluding stanza.

tatsaṃpadā¹⁰⁵ br̥hatīśahasraṃ¹⁰⁶ saṃpadyate¹⁰⁷ / (9.20.30)

That one [Āśvina Śastra] is completed by adjusting Br̥hatī [stanzas] to one thousand.

ime somāsastiroahnāsa¹⁰⁸ iti¹⁰⁹ puronuvākyā / (9.20.31)

“These Soma plants of the day before yesterday,” [this is] an introductory stanza.

hotā yakṣadaśvinā somānāṃ¹¹⁰ tiroahnānāmiti¹¹¹ praiṣaḥ / (9.20.32)

“Let the Hotar sacrifice to both Aśvins by the Soma plants of the day before yesterday¹¹²,” [this is] an invitatory stanza [for the Hotar to begin the sacrifice].

¹⁰² Irregular Sandhi, namely the absence of *avagraha* at the beginning of the following word.

¹⁰³ This is a quote from RV 2.23.15

br̥haspate_ati_yad_aryo_arhād_dyumad_vibhāti_kratumaj_janeṣu |
yad_dīdayaḥ_chavaśa_ṛtaprajāta_tad_aśmāsu_draviṇam_dhehi_citram ||

Br̥haspati! That which will be worth more than what belongs to the stranger, (that which) will radiate among the peoples with brilliance and purpose,
and that which will shine by means of your power, o you born through the truth—set that shimmering possession among us. (Jamison & Brereton, 2014, p. 434).

¹⁰⁴ Here by sacrificing is meant fire oblation that typically is ghee.

¹⁰⁵ See note No. 83.

¹⁰⁶ See note No. 83.

¹⁰⁷ See note No. 83.

¹⁰⁸ Ahnyāsa; cf. Hillebrandt (1897); cf. ĀŚS 6.5.23 (“ime somāsas tiro ahnyāsas [..]”).

¹⁰⁹ This line is also present in ĀŚS 6.5.24 (23?) and a part of it in ŚŚS 15.8.20 (Bloomfield, 1906, p. 236).

¹¹⁰ See note No. 83.

¹¹¹ This line is also present in ĀŚS 6.5.24; cf. variants “hotā yakṣad aśvinā chāgasy [..]” a.o. in Kāṭhaka Saṃhitā (18.21), “hotā yakṣad aśvinau sarasvatīm [..]” Maitrāyaṇī Saṃhitā (3.11.4; 4, 12.4), Mānava Śrauta Sūtra, Taitirīya Brāhmaṇa etc. (Autores Varii, 2022; Bloomfield, 1906, p. 1073).

¹¹² What is apparently meant here, that the Soma plants (stalks) had been prepared already the day before yesterday, and its had been brewing already for more than one day. Perhaps, in order to have a more concentrated concoction with stronger inabrating properties.

**ubhā pibatam¹¹³ pra vāmaṁdhāmsī¹¹⁴ adhyardhāṁ saṁdhāyārdharcena vaṣaṭkaroti
/(9.20.33)¹¹⁵**

“Drink, both of you, [Aśvins...],” “The [exhilarating] soma stalks [have come] forth for you,” having joined together the first half of the stanza [from RV hymn 1.46.15.] with the half of stanza [from RV hymn 7.68.2] he [the Hotar] utters “Vaṣaṭ”.

virājaiveti¹¹⁶ kauṣītakiḥ / (9.20.34)

“Only by the Virāj [he should sacrifice],” says Kauṣītaki [Brāhmaṇa].

aśvinā vāyuneti¹¹⁷ vā / (9.20.35)

Or else by [this stanza]: “O Aśvins, together with the Wind [..]”.

¹¹³ This is a quote from RV 1.46.15.

ubhā pibatam aśvinoḅhā naḥ śarma' yacchatam |
avidriyābhīr ūtibhīḥ ||

“Aśvins, both of you—drink! Both of you—offer protection to us through your unbreakable help! (Jamison and Brereton 2014, I–III:158).

¹¹⁴ This is a quote from RV 7.68.2

pra vāṁ andhāmsi madyāny asthuṛ arāṁ gantam haṁṣo' vīṭaye' me |
tīro aṛyo havānāni śruṭam naḥ ||

“The exhilarating soma stalks have come forth for you. As is right, come to pursue my offering across the calls of the stranger. Hear our (calls).” (Jamison and Brereton 2014, I–III:968)

¹¹⁵ This sentence is missing in GRETIL.

¹¹⁶ This line is a quote from KB 18,4.23.

Virājā eva yajed iti ha sma āha kauṣītakiḥ /

¹¹⁷ This is a quote from RV 3.58.7.

aśvinā vāyunā yuṁam sudakṣā nijudbhīṣ ca sajoṣasā yuvānā |
nāsatyā tīroahnyam juṣāṇā somam pibatam aśridhā sudānū ||

O well-skilled Aśvins, youthful ones, together with the Wind and along with your teams, drink the day-old soma, taking pleasure and never faltering, o Nāsatyas who bring good gifts. (Jamison & Brereton, 2014, p. 549) And also in AitBr IV.2.17; KB 18.5 (Bloomfield, 1906, p. 129).

Bibliography

Primary Sources

Aufrecht, T., Simon. (1879). *Das Aitareya Brāhmaṇa. Mit Auszügen aus dem Commentare von Sāyaṇācārya und anderen Beilagen.* Adolph Marcus.

Hillebrandt, A. (1888). *The Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra (Śrautasūtra) together with the commentary of Varadattasuta Ānartīya* (Vol. 1). Asiatic Soc. of Bengal.

Kauṣītakibrāhmaṇa (2020) SUB Göttingen: Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL). Available at: https://gretil.sub.uni-goettingen.de/gretil/corpustei/transformations/html/sa_zAGkhAyanazrautasUtra.htm (accessed 24 June 2023).

Lindner, Bruno (1887) *Das Kaushītaki Brāhmaṇa.* Jena: Hermann Costenoble.

Sreekrishna Sarma, E. R (1968) *Kauṣītaki-Brāhmaṇa.* Verzeichnis der orientalischen Handschriften in Deutschland Supplementband 9,1. Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner.

Śāṅkhāyanaśrautasūtra (2020) SUB Göttingen: Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages (GRETIL). Available at: http://gretil.sub.uni-goettingen.de/gretil/corpustei/transformations/html/sa_zAGkhAyanazrautasUtra.htm (accessed 29 July 2021).

Secondary Sources

Aufrecht, Theodor, S. (1879) *Das Aitareya Brāhmaṇa. Mit Auszügen aus dem Commentare von Sāyaṇācārya und anderen Beilagen.* Bonn: Adolph Marcus.

Autores Varii (2022) GRETIL - Göttingen Register of Electronic Texts in Indian Languages. VEDA. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.6466317.

Baunack, Theodor (1896) Ueber einige Wunderthaten der Aśvin. *Harrassowitz Verlag* 50(2): 263–287.

Baunack, Theodor (1898) Bhujyu, ein Schützling der Aṣvin. *Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht* 35(4): 485–563.

Black, Jeremy A., Green, Anthony and Rickards, Tessa (1992) *Gods, Demons, and Symbols of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Illustrated Dictionary.* London: Published by British Museum Press for the Trustees of the British Museum.

Bollensen, Friedrich (1887) Beiträge zur Kritik des Veda. *Harrassowitz Verlag* 41(No. 3): 494–507.

Brereton, Joel P. and Jamison, Stephanie W. (2020a) *The Rigveda: A Guide.* Guides to sacred texts. New York: Oxford University Press.

- Brereton, Joel P. and Jamison, Stephanie W. (2020b) *The Rigveda: A Guide*. Guides to sacred texts. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Eliade, Mircea (1954) *Cosmos and History. The Myth of the Eternal Return*. New York: Harper & Brothers.
- Eliade, Mircea (1961) *Images and Symbols. Studies in Religious Symbolism*. London: Harvill Press.
- Elizarenkova, Tat'jana Ja (ed.) (1999) *Rigveda. 1/4: Mandaly I - IV*. Izd. 2., ispr. Moskva: Nauka.
- Gamkrelidze, Thomas V., Ivanov, Vjačeslav V. and Winter, Werner (1994) *Indo-European and the Indo-Europeans: A Reconstruction and Historical Analysis of a Proto-Language and Proto-Culture*. Berlin; New York: De Gruyter.
- Geldner, Karl Friedrich (1951) *Der Rigveda. Aus dem Sanskrit ins Deutsche übers. und mit einem laufenden Kommentar versehen von Karl Friedrich Geldner. Erster Teil*. Harvard Oriental Series. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Gonda, J. (1977) *The Ritual Sūtras. A History of Indian literature; Veda and Upanishads v. 1: fasc. 2*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Gotō, Toshifumi (2006) *Ásvin and Nāsatya in the Rigveda and their Prehistoric Background*. In: *Proceedings of the Pre-symposium of RHIN and 7th ESCA Harvard-Kyoto Round Table* (eds Toshiki Osada, Harvard University, and N. Hase), Kyoto, 2006, pp. 253–283. RHIN library. Manohar Publishers & Distributors.
- Gotō, Toshifumi (2009) *Ásvin and Nāsatya in the Rigveda and their Prehistoric Background*. In: Osada, Toshiki, Harvard University, and Sōgō Chikyū Kankyōgaku Kenkyūjo (eds) *Ásvin and Nāsatya in the Rigveda and Their Prehistoric Background*. Rev. ed. RHIN library no. 8, 2009. New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, pp. 199–226.
- Goto, Toshifumi (n.d.) *Ásvin and Nāsatya in the Rigveda and their Prehistoric Background*. In: *Linguistics, archaeology and human past in South Asia* (eds Toshiki Osada and Sōgō Chikyū Kankyōgaku Kenkyūjo). RHIN library.
- Grassmann, Hermann (1876) *Rig-Veda*. Leipzig: F. A. Brockhaus.
- Grassmann, Hermann (1877) *Rig-Veda*. Leipzig: F. A. Brockhaus.
- Güntert, Hermann (1925) *Der arische weltkönig und heiland; bedeutungsgeschichtliche untersuchungen zur indo-iranischen religionsgeschichte und altertumskunde*. Halle,: Max Niemeyer.
- Hardy, Edmund (1893) *Die Vedisch-Brahmanische Periode Der Religion Des Alten Indiens*. Darstellung aus dem Gebiete der nichtchristlichen Religionsgeschichte. Münster: W., Aschendorff.
- Haug, Martin (ed.) (1863b) *The Aitareya Brahmanam of the Rigveda*. Bombay: Government Central Book Depot.

- Heywood, Paolo (2017) Ontological Turn, The. Stein, Felix (ed.) *Cambridge Encyclopedia of Anthropology*. DOI: 10.29164/17ontology.
- Hillebrandt, Alfred (1888) *The Śāṅkhāyana Śrauta Sūtra (Śrautasūtra) Together with the Commentary of Varadattasuta Ānartīya*. Calcutta: Asiatic Soc. of Bengal.
- Hillebrandt, Alfred (1891) *Vedische Mythologie*. Breslau: Wilhelm Koebner.
- Hillebrandt, Alfred (1897) *Ritual-Litteratur vedische Opfer und Zauber*. Strassbourg: Trübner.
- Hillebrandt, Alfred (1899) *Vedische Mythologie*. Breslau: Verlag von M & H Marcus.
- Hillebrandt, Alfred (1902) *Vedische Mythologie*. Breslau: Verlag von M & H Marcus.
- Hoffmann, Karl (1967) *Der Injunktiv Im Veda. Eine Synchronische Funktionsuntersuchung*. Heidelberg: Winter.
- Hopkins, Edward Washburn (1895) *The Religions of India*. Jastrow, Morris (ed.). Handbooks on the History of Religions. Boston, USA, London: Ginn & Company.
- Iloanusi, Obiakoiza A. (1984) *Myths of the Creation of Man and the Origin of Death in Africa, A Study in Igbo Traditional Culture and Other African Cultures*. European University Studies XXIII Theology. Frankfurt am Main, Bern, New York, Nancy: Peter Lang.
- Jamison, Stephanie W (2001) The Rigvedic Svayaṃvara? Formulaic evidence. 94: 303–316.
- Jamison, Stephanie W (2003) Vedic vŕ̥: Evidence for the Svayaṃvara in the Rig Veda? In: Schmidt, Hanns-Peter and Adhami, Siamak (eds) *Paitimāna: Essays in Iranian, Indo-European, and Indian Studies in Honor of Hanns-Peter Schmidt*. Costa Mesa, Calif: Mazda Publishers, pp. 39–56.
- Jamison, Stephanie W (2010) Sūre Duhitár's Brother, the 'Placer of the Sun': Another Example of -e <*-as in Rigvedic Phrasal Sandhi. In: Kim, Ronald I., Oettinger, Norbert, Rieken, Elisabeth, et al. (eds) *Ex Anatolia Lux: Anatolian and Indo-European Studies in Honor of H. Craig Melchert on the Occasion of His Sixty-Fifth Birthday*. Ann Arbor: Beech Stave Press, pp. 159–166.
- Jamison, Stephanie W and Brereton, Joel P (2014) *The Rigveda: The Earliest Religious Poetry of India*. South Asia Research. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Keith, Arthur Berriedale (1920) *Rigveda Brahmanas: The Aitareya and Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇas of the Rigveda*. Harvard oriental series. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Keith, Arthur Berriedale (1998a) *The Religion and Philosophy of the Veda and Upanishads. 1: Chapters 1 - 19*. Authorized repr. Harvard oriental series 31. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Keith, Arthur Berriedale (1998b) *The Religion and Philosophy of the Veda and Upanishads. 2: Chapters 20 - 29*. Authorized repr. Harvard oriental series 32. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Kielhorn, F. (1880) *A Grammar of the Sanskrit Language*. Second, revised. Bombay: Government Central Book Depot.

- Larson, Jennifer (2007) *Ancient Greek Cults: A Guide*. New York: Routledge.
- Lazaridis, Iosif, Alpaslan-Roodenberg, Songül, Acar, Ayşe, et al. (2022) The genetic history of the Southern Arc: A bridge between West Asia and Europe. *American Association for the Advancement of Science* 377(6609). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abm4247>.
- Ludwig, Alfred (1876) *Der Rigveda; oder, Die heiligen Hymnen der brâhmana*. Prag: Verlag von F. Tempsky.
- Ludwig, Alfred (1883) *Commentar Zur Rigveda Übersetzung*. Prag: Verlag von F. Tempsky.
- MacDonell, Arthur Anthony (1897) *Vedic Mythology*. Grundriss der Indo-arischen Philologie und Altertumskunde 1A. Strassburg: Trübner.
- Macdonell, Arthur Anthony (1910) *Vedic Grammar*. Grundriss der indo-arischen Philologie und Altertumskunde (Encyclopedia of Indo-Aryan research) I. Bd -- 4. Heft.) 4. Strassburg: The Clarendon Press.
- Mannhardt, Wilhelm (1875a) Die lettischen Sonnenmythen. (Fortsetzung). *Dietrich Reimer Verlag GmbH* 7. Bd.: 209–244.
- Mannhardt, Wilhelm (1875b) Die lettischen Sonnenmythen. (Schluss). *Dietrich Reimer Verlag GmbH* 7. Bd.: 281–329.
- Mannhardt, Wilhelm (1875c) Die lettischen Sonnenmythen. (Schluss). *Dietrich Reimer Verlag GmbH* 7. Bd.: 329–330.
- Matsumura, Kazuo (2019) Theories of Diffusionism: Myth and/or Science? *Journal of the International Association for Comparative Mythology* No. 5(No. 1): 44–54.
- Mayrhofer, Manfred (1986) *Etymologisches Wörterbuch des Altindoarischen*. Indogermanische Bibliothek. II. Reihe, Wörterbücher. Heidelberg: C. Winter.
- Muir, John (1870) *Original Sanskrit Texts on the Origin and History of the People of India, Their Religion and Institutions*. London: Trübner & Co.
- Müller, Friedrich Max (1868) *Chips from a German Workshop. Essays on Mythology, Traditions, and Customs*. Second edition. London: Longmans, Green, and Company.
- Müller, Friedrich Max (1869) *Rig-Veda Sanhita*. London: Trübner.
- Müller, Friedrich Max (1897) *Contributions to the Science of Mythology*. London: Longmans, Green and Co.
- Müller, Friedrich Max (1909) *Comparative Mythology: An Essay*. London; New York: George Routledge and Sons; E.P. Dutton & Co.
- Narasimhan, Vagheesh M., Patterson, Nick, Moorjani, Priya, et al. (2019) The formation of human populations in South and Central Asia. *Science* 365(6457): eaat7487. DOI: [10.1126/science.aat7487](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat7487).

- Oldenberg, Hermann (1988a) *The Religion of the Veda =: Die Religion Des Veda*. 1st ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Oldenberg, Hermann (1988b) *The Religion of the Veda =: Die Religion Des Veda*. 1st ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Parpola, Asko (2005) The Nasatyas, the chariot and Proto-Aryan religion. *University of Helsinki* 2004–2005(16 & 17): 1–63.
- Parpola, Asko (2015) *The Roots of Hinduism: The Early Aryans and the Indus Civilization*.
- Pischel, Richard S. and Geldner, Karl Friedrich (1897) *Vedische Studien*. Stuttgart: W. Kohlhammer.
- Ranade, R. H. (1981) *Āśvalāyana Śrauta-Sūtram*. First. Ranade publication series. Poona: R. H. Ranade.
- Renou, Louis (1947) *Les écoles védiques et la formation du Veda*. Cahiers de la Société asiatique 9. Paris: Imprimerie nationale.
- Sarma, E. R. Sreekrishna and Staal, Frits (1983) The Atirātra According to the Kauṣītaki Brāhmaṇa. In: *Agni, The Vedic Ritual Of The Fire Altar*. Berkeley: Asian Humanities Press, pp. 161–167.
- Schroeder, Leopold von (1895) Bemerkungen zu H. Oldenbergs Religion des Veda. 9: 109–132.
- Staal, Frits, Somayajipad, C. V., Itti Ravi Nambudiri, M., et al. (1983) *Agni, the Vedic Ritual of the Fire Altar*. Berkeley: Asian Humanities Press.
- Thieme, Paul (1960) The ‘Aryan’ Gods of the Mitanni Treaties. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 80(4): 301. DOI: 10.2307/595878.
- Trzaskoma, Stephen, Smith, R. Scott, Brunet, Stephen, et al. (eds) (2004) *Anthology of Classical Myth: Primary Sources in Translation*. Indianapolis: Hackett Pub.
- Vodskov, Hans Sofus (1897) *Sjæledyrkelse Og Naturdyrkelse. Bidrag Til Bestemmelsen Af Den Mytologiske Metode. Første Bind: Rig-Veda Og Edda Eller Den Komparative Mytologi*. Kjobenhavn: I kommission hos Lehmann & Stage.
- Ward, Donald (1968) *The Divine Twins: An Indo-European Myth in Germanic Tradition*. University of California publications: Folklore studies 19. Berkeley and Los Angeles: Univ. of California Press.
- Warmuth, Vera, Eriksson, Anders, Bower, Mim Ann, et al. (2012) Reconstructing the origin and spread of horse domestication in the Eurasian steppe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109(21): 8202–8206. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1111122109.
- Weber, Albrecht (1862) *Indische Studien: Beiträge für die Kunde des indischen Alterthums*. Berlin: Ferd. Dttmmler’s Verlagsbuchhandlung. Harrwitz and Gofsmann.

Wikander, Stig (1957) Nakula et Sahadeva. Gren, Erik (ed.) 6: 66–96.

Witzel, E.J. Michael (2018) Vedic Gods (Indra, Agni, Rudra, Varuṇa, etc.). Brill's Encyclopedia of Hinduism Online: Koninklijke Brill NV. DOI: 10.1163/2212-5019_BEH_COM_1030010.

Witzel, Michael (1989) Tracing the Vedic Dialects. Caillat, Colette (ed.) *Dialects dans les littératures indo-aryennes. Actes du Colloque International organise par UA 1058 sous les auspices du C.N.R.S avec le soutien du College de France, de la Fondation Hugot du College de France, de l'Universite de Paris III, du Ministre des Affaires Etrangères, Paris (Fondation Hugot) 16-18 Septembre 1986. Paris (College de France, Institut de Civilisation Indienne): 97–265.*

Witzel, Michael (2003) Vedas and Upaniṣads. In: Flood, Gavin D. (ed.) *The Blackwell Companion to Hinduism*. Blackwell companions to religion. Malden, MA: Blackwell Pub, pp. 68–101.

Yāska (1942) *The Nirukta of Yāska (with Nighantu) Ed. with Durga's Commentary by H.M. Bhadkamkar, Assisted by R.G. Bhadkamkar*. 1st ed. Bhadkamkar, R. G. (ed.). Bombay Sanskrit and Prakrit Series LXXXV. Bombay, The Department of Public Instruction: The Department of Public Instruction.

Zeller, Gabriele (1990) Die vedischen Zwillingsgötter. Untersuchungen zur Genese ihres Kultes. Band 24. Freiburger Beiträge zur Indologie, hrsg. von Ulrich Schneider.

Online Sources

A Dictionary of Biology (n.d.) Breeding Season. Encyclopedia.com. Available at: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/science/dictionaries-thesauruses-pictures-and-press-releases/breeding-season> (accessed 5 June 2023).

Altar of Fire (1976) Documentary, Educational Resources. The Film Study Center at Harvard University. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RYvkYk7GvJ0> (accessed 6 September 2022).

Biblissima Toolkit (n.d.) Eulexis-web Lemmatiser for ancient Greek texts (online app). Available at: <https://outils.biblissima.fr/en/eulexis-web/index.php> (accessed 28 February 2023).

Böhtlingk, Otto and Roth, Rudolph von (1855) *Sanskrit Wörterbuch. herausgegeben von der kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften*. XML edition. St-Petersburg: Eggers. Available at: <https://www.sanskrit-lexicon.uni-koeln.de/scans/PWGScan/2020/web> (accessed 14 May 2023).

Braginskaja, N.V. (2008) Kalendarj. Tokarev, S.A. (ed.) *Mifi narodov mira*. Electronic edition. Moskva: Sovetskaja enciklopedija. Available at: https://www.indostan.ru/biblioteka/knigi/2730/3412_1_o.pdf (accessed 14 May 2023).

Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2012) Hesperus. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Hesperus-Greco-Roman-mythology> (accessed 22 March 2023).

- Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2020) Saint Elmo's fire. Atmospheric phenomenon. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Hesperus-Greco-Roman-mythology> (accessed 1 May 2023).
- Coleridge, Edward P. (tran.) (1938) *Euripides. The Complete Greek Drama, Edited by Whitney J. Oates and Eugene O'Neill, Jr.* New York: Random House. Available at: <http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:greekLit:tlg0006.tlg014.perseus-eng1:1495-1511> (accessed 1 May 2023).
- Dainu skapis* (n.d.) The Cabinet of Folksongs. Available at: <http://dainuskapis.lv/> (accessed 10 November 2020).
- Davis, Phil and Carney, Steve (2022) Eye Safety During a Solar Eclipse. Available at: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/eclipses/safety/> (accessed 9 June 2023).
- Edholm, Kristoffer af (2021) List of Vedic Texts and Translations into English, German, and French. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/37593741/List_of_Vedic_Texts_and_Translations_into_English_German_and_French_Version_7_2021_ (accessed 3 June 2022).
- Espenak, Fred and O'Byrne, Chris (2010) JavaScript solar eclipse explorer. Available at: <https://eclipse.gsfc.nasa.gov/JSEX/JSEX-AS.html> (accessed 3 June 2023).
- Evers, Jeannie (ed.) (2023) Equinox. National Geographic Society. Available at: <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/equinox/> (accessed 5 June 2023).
- Frame, Douglas (2020) The Myth of Return in Early Greek Epic, 6: Evidence for the Meaning of the Indo-European Root *nes-. https://chs.harvard.edu/publications.sec/online_print_books.ssp/. Available at: <https://chs.harvard.edu/douglas-frame-the-myth-of-return-in-early-greek-epic-6-evidence-for-the-meaning-of-the-indo-european-root-nes/> (accessed 1 March 2023).
- Hesiod (2021) *Hesiod's Theogony*. Open Access Poetry Archive: Poetry in Translation A. S. Kline's. Available at: <https://www.poetryintranslation.com/PITBR/Greek/HesiodTheogony.php> (accessed 3 May 2023).
- Homer (1924) *Homer. The Iliad with an English Translation by A.T. Murray*. Cambridge, MA.,; London: Cambridge, MA., Harvard University Press. William Heinemann, Ltd. Available at: <http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:greekLit:tlg0012.tlg001.perseus-eng1:11.1-11.46> (accessed 3 May 2023).
- Homer (2004) *Homer: The Odyssey*. Open Access Poetry Archive: Poetry in Translation A. S. Kline's. Available at: <https://www.poetryintranslation.com/PITBR/Greek/Odhome.php> (accessed 3 May 2023).
- Jamison, Stephanie W. and Brereton, Joel P. (n.d.) Book 8. Available at: http://rigvedacommentary.alc.ucla.edu/?page_id=27 (accessed 8 March 2023).

- Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology (2012) Castor, the 6-star System - A3 poster. Available at: https://d2pn8kiwq2w21t.cloudfront.net/original_images/infographicsuploads/infographics_full10884.jpg (accessed 6 March 2023).
- Kelk, Christopher (tran.) (2020) *The Homeric Hymns*. Open Access Poetry Archive: Poetry in Translation A. S. Kline's. Available at: https://www.poetryintranslation.com/PITBR/Greek/HomericHymns.php#anchor_Toc58440013 (accessed 3 May 2023).
- Lal, Avantika (2018) Chariots in Ancient Indian Warfare. Available at: <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/1269/chariots-in-ancient-indian-warfare> (accessed 3 May 2023).
- Latviešu tautas ticējumi* (1997) Zirgs. LU MII Mākslīgā intelekta laboratorija. Available at: <http://http://valoda.ailab.lv/folkloraticejumi/valoda.ailab.lv/folkloraticejumi> (accessed 26 February 2023).
- Lawrence, Pete (2023) Castor and Pollux, the twin stars of Gemini. Available at: <https://www.skyatnightmagazine.com/advice/castor-pollux-stars-gemini/> (accessed 6 March 2023).
- Livonijas Indriķis (1993) *Indriķa hronika. No latīņu valodas tulkojis Ā. Feldhūns; Ē. Mugurēviča priekšvārds un komentāri*. Rīga: Zinātne. Available at: http://old.historia.lv/alfabets/I/In/Indrika%20hronika/indrika_hronika.htm (accessed 26 February 2023).
- McClure, Bruce (2017) Venus after sunset and before sunrise! Available at: <https://earthsky.org/astronomy-essentials/venus-after-sunset-and-before-sunrise-march-2017/> (accessed 9 June 2023).
- Monier-Williams, Monier (1899) *A Sanskrit-English Dictionary: Etymologically and Philologically Arranged with Special Reference to Cognate Indo-European Languages*. Oxford: The Clarendon Press. Available at: <https://www.sanskrit-lexicon.uni-koeln.de/scans/MWScan/2020/web/index.php> (accessed 14 August 2022).
- Ottewel, Guy (2023) The 5 petals of Venus and its 8-year cycle. In: *Astronomy Essentials*. Available at: <https://earthsky.org/astronomy-essentials/five-petals-of-venus/> (accessed 4 June 2023).
- Plato (1921) *Cratylus. Plato in Twelve Volumes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press; London, William Heinemann Ltd. Available at: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0172%3Atext%3DCrat.%3Asection%3D406e> (accessed 10 September 2022).
- Pokorny, Julius (2007) *An Etymological Dictionary of the Proto-Indo-European Language. A Revised Edition of Julius Pokorny's Indogermanisches Etymologisches Wörterbuch*. The Dngnu Association. Available at: [H T T P : / / D N G H U . O R G /](http://www.dngnu.org/) (accessed 29 April 2023).

Rubinstein, R.I. (2008) Egipetskaja mifologija. Tokarev, S.A. (ed.) *Mifi narodov mira*. Electronic edition. Moskva: Sovetskaja enciklopedija. Available at: https://www.indostan.ru/biblioteka/knigi/2730/3412_1_o.pdf (accessed 14 May 2023).

Society, Asia (2015) Map of Gandhara. *World History Encyclopedia*. Asia Society. Available at: <https://www.worldhistory.org/image/3943/map-of-gandhara/> (accessed 22 March 2023).

Spektors, Andrejs (2009) Electronic dictionary Tezaurs. *Tezaurs*. Available at: <https://tezaurs.lv> (accessed 26 February 2023).

The Nine Planets (2019) Venus Facts. Available at: <https://nineplanets.org/venus/> (accessed 9 June 2023).

Williams, David R. (2023) Venus Fact Sheet. Available at: <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/venusfact.html> (accessed 9 June 2023).